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**Kinetic and Fluid Modelling of Plasmas:
Energetic Beams and Tilt Stability
in Field Reversed Configurations — THESIS**

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KINETIC AND FLUID MODELLING OF PLASMAS:
ENERGETIC BEAMS AND TILT STABILITY IN
FIELD REVERSED CONFIGURATIONS

APPROVED BY
DISSERTATION COMMITTEE:

Supervisor:

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John Winston Cobb
1993

Dedicated to my joy, Lynda
my mother, Eulalia and
my Father, Lewis

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ENERGETIC BEAMS AND TILT STABILITY IN
FIELD REVERSED CONFIGURATIONS**

by

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DISSERTATION

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Plasma problems include features on disparate scales. One example is the dynamical coupling of the microscopic details of individual particle motion to the macroscopic plasma flow. A small energetic particle component can modify the low frequency fluid response of a plasma. This work extends fluid models to include a minority component of energetic kinetic particles and applies it to the study of the tilt mode in Field Reversed Configurations (FRC's), an advanced fusion concept with high β , a natural divertor, and a non-linked-to-coil geometry.

A model is presented which treats the majority plasma in an extended magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) approximation (MHD plus viscous, resistive, and Hall effects) while maintaining a kinetic representation of the minority energetic component. The model is applied to simulations of FRC's. Several different computational techniques for fluids and particles are used. Some are melded together for self-consistent fluid and kinetic simulations. Two separate

fluid algorithms, the semi-implicit FLX algorithm [D. C. Barnes, R. C. Bishop, R. D. Milroy, and D. D. Schnack accepted by J. Comp. Phys.; R. D. Milroy, D. C. Barnes, R. C. Bishop, and R. B. Webster Phys. Fl. B 1 p. 1225 (1989)] and a Lax-Wendroff algorithm, and a kinetic algorithm (Particle-in-Cell) are used. Additional non-self-consistent simulations treat particle effects as given. The algorithms numerically solve initial value problems with starting conditions given by the output of two different equilibrium solvers. One solver uses cubic splines with direct banded matrix inversion. The other is an iterative conjugate gradient solver of a finite difference formulation.

Four problems are addressed; realistic capture of injected energetic neutral beams, tilt mode stabilization of an injected neutral beam, tilt mode stabilization by equilibrium profile modification, spin-up and viscous angular momentum transport in an FRC. Results indicate that energetic particles can change both the equilibrium and stability characteristics of FRC's. It is shown that energetic beams decrease tilt activity from two effects, equilibrium modification and beam dynamical interaction. Further simulations find a new equilibria regime that is tilt stable even without beams. The implication is that that tilt instabilities may be avoidable or suppressible and that such effects can be reproduced with the simplified model used here.

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Chapter 1

Introduction and Motivation

1.1 Field Reversed Configuration (FRC) Concept

Fusion energy offers the unique promise of an energy supply that is not limited by its supply of fuel, as opposed to fission or fossil fuels which are. Additionally, fusion energy can be used for large scale centralized power stations which are more difficult for some alternatives such as solar power or conservation. This advantage is offset by the extreme technological complexity of fusion power.

Currently, the U.S. magnetic fusion program has concentrated its efforts on a single concept, the tokamak. Serious, perhaps insurmountable, obstacles exist to economically competitive power production in tokamaks. Some of these are discussed in § (1.2). However, other magnetic fusion concepts can address some of these obstacles. One such concept is the Field Reversed Configuration or FRC.[1]

The FRC is an example of a compact toroidal confinement concept.[1] The external field is that of a cylindrical solenoid. However, large diamagnetic currents create a reversed magnetic field near the z -axis (symmetry axis). This forms a closed topologically toroidal magnetic field structure. The toroidal direction is θ . The poloidal plane is the r - z plane. The external solenoid field may vary in strength as a function of z so that the total external field be a

PSI COUTOURS IN R-Z PLANE
 AT T = 0.00 AT TIME = 0.
 MIN=-1.918E+05 MAX= 1.600E+06

-1.73E+05	-7.67E+04	-1.92E+04	0.	2.30E+05	9.22E+05
-1.20E+05	-4.32E+04	-4.80E+03	5.76E+04	5.18E+05	1.44E+06

Figure 1.1: FRC Equilibrium Poloidal Flux Contours.

mirror field. The FRC is sometimes called a “Reversed Biased Theta Pinch” from a particular formation technique. FRC’s have no toroidal magnetic field. Rather, gradients in the poloidal field are balanced by a large plasma pressure gradient, and to a smaller extent, field line curvature.

Fig. (1.1) shows a set of flux contours for a FRC equilibrium. The magnetic axis is at the O-point. This is also the location of the pressure maximum. Since the toroidal magnetic field is zero, the magnetic field vanishes at the O-point. The local β defined as $8\pi P/(B^2 + 8\pi P)$, is 1. Note the traditional definition of $\beta = 8\pi P/B^2$ is not used since it diverges at the O-point. The average β can be in the range of 0.6 to 0.9. This is in comparison to present day tokamaks which have β limits in the 0.1 to 0.15 range. This is a direct consequence of the lack of a toroidal magnetic field.

The magnetic field is divided into regions of open and closed field lines, with the boundary marked by a separatrix. Plasma is contained on the closed

field lines. The open field line plasma is of much lower density, although some lines near the separatrix contain a significant amount of plasma. The separatrix is roughly elliptical shaped. The elongation, E , is defined as the ratio of the half-length of the separatrix to its radius. For typical experiments, E is between 3 and 10. The exact shape of the separatrix is not experimentally observable[2, 3] but can be inferred from magnetic field measurements. The separatrix shape may depart from a strict elliptical shape. Theoretical and numerical equilibria have been found where the shape is elliptical, circular, or “racetrack” shaped, meaning that the curvature is concentrated near the ends of the device.[4, 5, 6, 7, 3, 8]

1.2 Some Obstacles to Fusion Energy Production

In this section some of the well known obstacles to feasible fusion power production are sketched. These issues are analyzed in terms of the current tokamak based magnetic fusion energy program. § (1.3) explains how FRC's can naturally avoid some of these problems.

The principal goal of the magnetic fusion effort is the production of a feasible and economical power source.[9] The technical possibility of constructing a fusion reactor based on a tokamak concept that reaches ignition is fairly certain.[10] Even the construction of a power producing reactor seems well within the realm of technical feasibility.[9] A reactor that produces electric power, does not necessarily meet the goals of the magnetic fusion program. The critical issue is economic feasibility.

What are the economic factors that any alternative energy source must meet? The first is the basic cost of energy. It must supply energy that is

price competitive. When considering the commitment of scarce research and development dollars, the price analysis must include the possibility of other alternative energy sources and conservation strategies that will be available in a changing pricing environment.

Secondly, the alternative energy candidate must fit into an appropriate niche in the energy economy. Magnetic fusion energy will be limited to central power station production. This is in contrast to some current and alternative energy resources which can be utilized in a decentralized fashion. Therefore economic feasibility of magnetic fusion will require comparison to other centralized power stations. This will include analysis of short and long term direct costs from pollution production and resource utilization. This analysis may be skewed to the extent that some of these costs continue to be externalized. Examples of such include, military intervention to secure free access to petroleum reserves, or economy-wide costs from specific pollution sources. Other centralized electrical production technologies include the currently utilized coal, oil, or natural gas fired plants, as well as hydropower and current light water fission reactors. It also includes technologies that are, or will be, available but are not yet widely utilized such as advanced fission reactors, wind farms, and central solar power station schemes.

Third and finally, any alternative energy production technology must surmount a negative presumption of change. This consideration is often dubbed "one in the hand, two in the bush". Since new energy sources are by definition untried, there is inherent cost and reliability uncertainty. Further, proponents often oversell a program. So a negative presumption is almost always justified. For magnetic fusion energy, this presumption is magnified for three reasons:

First, most of the cost of energy production is front-loaded in the capital costs of construction. Second, exact knowledge of plant lifetimes, including crucial components such as first wall, divertor plate, and superconducting coils, are uncertain, particularly in the light of the large magnetic, mechanical, and thermal stresses and material deterioration due to neutron embrittlement. Third, reliability, as measured by percentage up-time, is unknown and uncertain considering the complexity of commercial reactor designs.

If the recent directions of the U.S. tokamak fusion program are analyzed in hindsight, it is apparent that much of the previous analysis has, at some level, been internalized. Considerable effort in the last decade has gone into improving confinement,[11, 12] improved edge and divertor operation[13, 14] improving marginal stability boundaries[14, 15] and even searching for new modes of operation.[16, 17]

Nevertheless, the tokamak as a controlled magnetic fusion concept has many, perhaps insurmountable, problems achieving economic feasibility. While there are many difficulties, there are two problems that are particularly troublesome and cannot be overcome without a radically different approach to fusion. The first is the problem of coil geometry. Current tokamaks have low toroidal β , the ratio of plasma pressure to magnetic field pressure. Therefore strong D.C. toroidal field coils are needed. These coils are topologically linked with the plasma torus. These coils must be shielded from neutron heating and neutron damage. However, if the coils are moved away from the first wall to accommodate shielding, then the magnetic field in the plasma is reduced. If they are moved close, shielding becomes difficult. This is a particular problem on the inboard side of the plasma torus where space is at a premium. It is further

exacerbated by other optimization schemes that are driving designs toward low aspect ratio, high elongation plasma shapes.[14] This problem can only be alleviated by increasing the toroidal β of the device. However there is a maximum possible toroidal β in tokamaks beyond which magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) stability is lost.

The second problem concerns the deuterium-tritium (D-T) fuel cycle. This fusion reaction is usually considered since it is easiest to achieve. The cross section peak is at a lower energy. However, the fusion products are ^4He and a neutron. The high flux of high energy neutrons leads to several technological problems. It creates severe materials design problems. The design criteria for withstanding high mechanical and thermal stresses must be coupled with equally stringent resistance to neutron embrittlement. Total neutron flux reduces the lifetime of critical components. Several shutdown and refurbishing cycles will be required during a plant's life.[18, 19] Since a high flux 14 MeV neutron source is not yet available, total flux limits have a high degree of uncertainty. This hurts the prospects for fusion energy because it increases the cost of energy produced and it also creates a higher wall of negative presumption since the neutron questions are unresolved. Moreover, the neutron carries the majority of the fusion energy. Since the neutron is uncharged, this energy can only be recovered by thermal means. The neutron power flux through the first wall will be even larger than the nominal generating power due simply to thermodynamic efficiency.

However, advanced fusion fuel cycles that can reduce or eliminate neutrons. One example is the Deuterium-Helium-3 (D- ^3He) fuel cycle. Because Helium is doubly charged, the ignition temperature and Lawson criterion are

higher.[18] The direct fusion products are non-radioactive, a 14 MeV proton and ^4He . The 14 MeV proton can undergo direct energy conversion because it is charged.[18] The efficiencies can be higher than possible from a thermal cycle. $\text{D}-^3\text{He}$ is lower in radioactivity, although not radiation free. The principal source of radiation is from neutrons from side reactions where a deuteron fuses with another deuteron to form a triton. The Triton then fuses with another deuteron in a traditional D-T reaction giving a neutron. The total neutron power is 1 to 2 orders of magnitude lower than in tokamaks.[18] This will relax reactor neutron damage design considerations significantly. However, the vessel will still not be available for direct handling.

Traditional tokamak designs are not well adapted for advanced fuel operation. The low β requirement of present day tokamaks imply that synchrotron radiation energy losses will quench ignition of advanced fuels.[20] Even though some workers in the field have offered designs to address some problems,[21, 22] the possibility must be considered that commercially feasible fusion power may never be produced from a tokamak plasma. However, this does not imply that magnetic confinement fusion cannot produce a commercially attractive power plant design. These types of ideas are the force behind the arguments for alternative approaches to magnetic confinement fusion.

1.3 FRC Relevance to Magnetic Fusion Energy

FRC's offer several reactor advantages over tokamaks such as high β , coil geometry not linked with plasma torus, ease of plasma translation, no symmetry axis shielding, and an inherent separatrix that could serve as a natural divertor for high efficiency direct electric conversion of thermal and energetic fusion

products.[18] High β reduces synchrotron radiation since the internal magnetic field is smaller. This allows advanced fuel ignition. With advanced fuels comes reduced neutron radiation and higher plant efficiency. This along with the non-linked coil geometry, and lower power load on the first wall will ease design constraints for the first wall and main coils. Low aspect ratio allows for a smaller overall plant size and cost which reduces the negative presumption. Finally, a modular burn chamber can be designed for easy repair and replacement because the non-linked coil geometry allows FRC translation. Moreover, replacement will be inexpensive since it will not require disassembly and/or replacement of other vital components.[18]

1.4 FRC physics issues

However, the FRC, as a reactor concept, possesses many unanswered questions and obstacles of its own. One obstacle is transport. It has been studied both theoretically[23, 24, 25] and experimentally.[26, 27, 1] Empirical scalings have been constructed, but a clear and complete understanding has not yet emerged. Current devices are too small to allow reliable extrapolation to reactor sized devices. This is in contrast to tokamak devices where over 20 years of intense international effort have allowed fairly detailed construction of transport scalings based on different modes of operation which can offer fairly reliable predictions of transport of reactor sized devices. The very open question of FRC transport is beyond the scope of this work and will not be discussed.

There is another set of even more alarming obstacles to a successful FRC reactor concept. The question of MHD, or fluid, stability is still open. That MHD stability is an issue can be intuitively understood when note is taken

that the field line curvature is bad everywhere inside the plasma separatrix. This can be seen in Fig. (1.1). The pressure is maximum at the O-point. The potentially most dangerous mode is the internal tilt mode. It is an internal perturbation characterized by rotation of the plasma about an axis perpendicular to the symmetry axis. Ideal Magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) theory predicts instability. Intuitively, the plasma is a current dipole with its moment aligned anti-parallel to the external field. A rigid rotation could potentially be unstable. This rigid rotation, or external tilt mode may be stabilized by magnetic compression if conducting walls are nearby.[28, 29] However, a slightly different form of the instability exists even when the plasma perturbation is restricted to the interior of the separatrix.[30] The tilt mode is ideal MHD unstable for plasma elongations greater than a critical value, usually near 1. Analytic stability analysis is possible for a particular analytic equilibrium called the Hill's vortex.[30] In this stability analysis, there is a competition between the necessary magnetic compression to allow rotation without disturbing the separatrix and the unstable driving force to flip the dipole in the field. These forces scale differently with elongation, with the stabilizing compression decreasing with increasing elongations. The instability growth time is predicted to be on the order of the axial Alfvén transit time,[28, 30, 7, 31]

$$\gamma_{\text{tilt}}^0 = \frac{C V_{\text{Alfvén}}}{b}, \quad (1.1)$$

where $V_{\text{Alfvén}}$ is an average Alfvén velocity, C is a constant, on the order of unity and b is the separatrix half-length.

Fig. (1.2) shows the evolution of the plasma pressure and the magnetic field lines of a fluid simulation for conditions similar to previously published

Figure 1.2: Evolution of the Tilt Mode in FRC for Magnetic Field Lines, Ψ , and Pressure Contours, P .

results.[6, 32, 33, 30] A small $n = 1$ perturbation grows. The tracings of magnetic field lines soon begin to change from closed to open because of the $n = 1$ perturbation's destruction of axi-symmetry. When the field lines open, the plasma is quickly lost out the ends of the device by means of rapid motion parallel to the magnetic field. This can be clearly seen in the late time pressure contours. Each frame is spaced about one growth time apart, so the entire sequence covers about 6 axial Alfvén transit times.

External stabilization is difficult since perturbations are primarily confined to inside the separatrix, as has been verified in fluid simulations.[1, 6] Non-linear simulations see no saturation mechanism before total disruption.[33, 32] Subsequent single fluid theory has been unable to find stability for equilibria of experimental interest. While toroidal rotation can stabilize the mode,[7] the required rotation rate is much higher than observed in experiments.

The theoretical and simulational pessimism has not been matched by experimental devices. With only a few recent exceptions,[34, 35] experiments do not observe tilt instabilities for times greater than tens of Alfvén transit times.[36, 37, 1] Experimental lifetimes are determined either by resistive flux loss or a less violent (and ultimately controllable) $n = 2$ rotational mode.

This apparent contradiction has been traditionally resolved by appealing to physical effects which are not captured in the ideal MHD limit. Two extensions are the Hall term[38] and gyroviscous effects.[39] They indicate that for very high elongation stability can be achieved. This leaves two critical elongations, a minimum and a maximum. If the elongation is between the two it is tilt unstable. If it is less than the lower value (the ideal critical elongation) then it is stable because magnetic compression overwhelms the unstable driv-

ing motion. For elongations greater than the higher value (the Hall critical elongation), the non-ideal effects can stabilize the tilt mode. Recent analytic results indicate the Hall critical elongation can be decreased by as much as 30% by varying the equilibrium separatrix shape, even for flat pressure profiles.[40] Flat profiles are defined as pressure profiles that are a linear function of the poloidal flux, Ψ . This together with improved analysis has led to the claim that most experimentally stable results can be explained.

Another non-ideal stabilization mechanism is the inherently kinetic response of the plasma.[41] The fluid approximation relies on a small gyro-radius in order to validate the local approximations. However, many orbits in the FRC are not small and are quite complex, resembling neither drifting Larmor orbits[42] nor betatron orbits.[43] This is a result of the lower magnetic field in the plasma and especially to vanishing of the magnetic field at the O-point. Most experiments (with two recent exceptions[34, 44]) are of such a size that kinetic effects can increase the instability growth time to longer than the FRC lifetime.[41, 45, 43] A third exception is a cool FRC with high collisionality.[35] In that case the plasma may be so collisional ($\nu_{\text{coll}} > \Omega_{\text{cyc}}$) that fluid-like behavior is seen even in small devices.

However, this traditional view implies that machines with a larger radius compared to the ion gyroradius will be tilt unstable since both the Hall effect and the kinetic behavior will be reduced. This has dire implications for reactor scale FRC's. Extrapolation to reactor sized devices predicts observable tilt instability.

Recent FRC experiments in large devices have given provocative and diverse results. Tuszewski *et al.* have reported evidence of a tilt-like perturba-

tion and strong correlation of this tilt activity with degraded confinement.[34] This was explained as an effect of operating the device in a fluid-like region of parameter space. Good agreement was found with probe signals predicted from fluid simulations and the actual observed signals. Results on the LSX experiment [44] have not seen correlation between tilt-like signals [B_θ $n = 1$ axially even probe measurements] and confinement, although LSX is expected to behave in an even more fluid-like manner. While both experiments are FRC's, they differ in other aspects, such as mirror fields and formation methodologies. The fact that LSX appears to be tilt stable but FRX-C/LSM is not suggests that there may be another mechanism that affects tilt stability.

There is a suggestion for such a mechanism. A minority population of energetic particles may stabilize the tilt mode. Current experiments may have an embedded beam as a consequence of the formation process. This is interesting since previous kinetic analysis shows that tilt stability depends on the 4'th velocity moment of the distribution function. Thus a very small, but energetic beam can have a significant stabilizing effect.[41] Estimates indicate that the required beam energy and total current are substantial but may not be unrealistic.[46, 47, 48] Preferential trapping of fusion products may provide a large amount of the required current in reactor designs.[49]

The second suggestion is that tilt instability is not a universally unstable mode, but depends on the equilibrium choice. A particular set of equilibrium profiles, called hollow profiles, may be tilt stable.[50, 51] Moreover, there may exist dynamical mechanisms that force FRC's to these types of equilibria.

Given this situation, the goal of this work is to derive a model of plasma behavior that describes the evolution of a kinetically behaving energetic minor-

ity component with a fluid-like majority plasma component. Then computer simulation techniques will be adapted or developed for this coupled fluid and kinetic algorithm.

Although the kinetic component is small in particle numbers, its effects upon equilibrium and dynamics are non-trivial. This is very different from more usual kinetic effects which come in two effects. In one they occur as corrections to fluid results. These corrections become smaller as the plasma becomes more fluid-like. The other effects are of a type that has no fluid counterpart, such as resonant particle interactions. In stability analysis these forms are seen as either kinetic corrections to fluid derived growth rates or as the existence of intrinsically kinetic unstable modes that vanish in the fluid limit. In FRC's, however, the kinetic effect may be of a different character. It may contribute to a kinetic "correction" to the growth rate that is not small, but is large even for conditions that are superficially very fluid-like. These kinetic "corrections" to the tilt mode growth rate can be as large or larger than the fluid terms, even for reactor sized FRC's! The focus is on those aspects of kinetic behavior that can have lowest order effects on plasma dynamics. For pragmatic reasons, approximations are made that will incorrectly model some higher order kinetic effects, particularly, the modelling of energy transport.

Although the main focus is the kinetic corrections to fluid behavior, the simulation techniques will also allow for the exploration of fluid effects that are independent of any kinetic effect, such as profile stabilization.[51, 52] The simulation methodology will include equilibrium solvers along with fluid and kinetic techniques. Allowance must be made for the fluid and equilibrium aspects to vary greatly because results from the beam simulations often suggest

directions for purely fluid research that have not yet been explored. Just such an example will be presented in Ch. (5).

While the models and simulation techniques will be applied to problems in FRC's, They are actually of general applicability. While not explored here, it these techniques can be used for several problems in mainstream tokamak simulations such as injected beam induced rotation, runaway electrons, and ignition produced alpha particle dynamics. These methods could also be applied to astrophysical problems such particle motion in the earth's magnetotail[53] or some energetic particle acceleration scenarios in bow shocks. Some of these cross-applications will be modelled with less than desired accuracy, however. For instance, the neglect of velocity space diffusion will be a severe limit on the correct modelling of 4 MeV alpha particle dynamics in tokamaks.

What is crucial about the models presented here is that the kinetic effects enter most prominently in the momentum equations as opposed to particle or energy conservation relations. For instance, an energetic beam can have a number density orders of magnitude smaller than the background plasma and still have a total current as large or larger than the background. This can drastically change normal plasma concepts. For instance, the magnetic field is now decoupled from the background plasma current. The energetic beam can create part of the confining field for the background plasma. The $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force term is important in determining momentum balance. An energetic beam can modify this term significantly. These problems could be simulated by completely kinetic methods, but the computational resources required are very large.[45] While the rapid advances in computer architectures tends to reduce this barrier daily, it will always be valuable to have a simulation techniques that can

faithfully reproduce the same results with much less CPU use. The price that will be paid for this advantage is that accurate modelling of many aspect of energy transport will be sacrificed.

This dissertation is organized as follows. Ch. (2) presents a deductive derivation of a physical model appropriate for describing FRC's that contain an energetic beam. It concludes with a set of model equations that is a superset of the simulation algorithms that are implemented in the other chapters. Ch. (3) present results from different studies of FRC behavior in a coupled fluid and beam algorithm. It is used to simulate the capture of a realistic beam from a high current short pulse neutral beam and their effects on tilt stability. Ch. (4) presents results of purely fluid simulations of the possibility of equilibrium modifications leading to tilt stabilization. Ch. (5) discusses some of the consequences of preferentially trapped fusion products in an ignited, advanced fueled FRC. It models the internal spin up from slowing down collisions between the beam and the background plasma as well as the associated external field line spin up and possible jet formation. Finally, Ch. (6), discusses the implications of the work presented in this dissertation and elsewhere on the future directions for FRC research. It details a list of problems that are naturally next extensions of this work.

Chapter 2

Derivation of Physical Models

2.1 Preliminaries — Basic Kinetic Equations

This chapter presents the derivation of the various mathematical models of physical plasma behavior used in other chapters. The goal is to justify the various reduced descriptions from first principles. Most formulations are not new, although some new aspects, are presented. The emphasis is on the explicit statement of the required approximations and their justification. It lists the approximations and limits required for the models used. It also shows whether these limits have validity based in physical reality or whether they are ad hoc invocations required for simplicity and tractability.

The core of this work is computational simulation. There are two broad categories of plasma simulation, particle and fluid. Particle models the kinetic plasma behavior contained in individual particle motion while fluid simulation models the coarse grained, aggregate behavior only. While particles can be more accurate, complete particle descriptions require much greater computational resources. FRC plasmas are primarily fluid in nature, but several crucial, inherently kinetic effects must be considered in order to get a first order accurate description of either their equilibria or dynamics. Fluid plasma models usually rely on a small gyro-radius compared to length scale of interest for

validity but this may be violated in some regions of an FRC. Additionally, energetic particles such as fusion reaction products or injected energetic beams will exhibit complex large Larmor radius motion. The computational approach here is to couple the fluid and particle (kinetic) descriptions into a single model that will be amenable to efficient computational simulation. The purpose of this chapter is to highlight, the assumptions necessary to derive this hybrid model and to discuss their regions of validity. Some approximations will be made for the sake of tractability. The extent to which they are physically justified will be examined. Those simulation effects which are suspect will be identified. If simulation results are dependent on such effects, it will be an indication that the underlying physical mechanism driving the dynamical behavior is not accurately modelled. However, if the results are insensitive to these errors, then a good the results are probably valid since the inaccurately modelled physics is not driving the phenomena under study.

The starting point is the plasma Fokker-Planck equation plus additional collisional terms besides classical Coulomb collisions.

$$\frac{\partial f_\alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot (\nabla f_\alpha) + \mathbf{a}_\alpha \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} f_\alpha = G_\alpha, \quad (2.1)$$

where $f_\alpha \equiv f_\alpha(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$ is the single particle distribution function for particles of type α .

$$\mathbf{a}_\alpha \equiv \frac{e_\alpha}{m_\alpha} \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \right) \quad (2.2)$$

is the acceleration of particles of type α due to the electric and magnetic field in the mean field approximation. G_α is the change of f_α due to collisions and other physical effects which rely on second or higher order correlations. Let N_α be the total number of different types of particles, or species.

Eq. (2.1) describes a flow in phase space. f_α evolves by following the single particle trajectories in phase space. The particle motion is given by,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} \equiv \mathbf{v}, \quad (2.3)$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} \equiv \mathbf{a}. \quad (2.4)$$

These equations are given a species subscript. The G_α term represents the rate of change of f_α in the frame of reference moving with the phase-space flow given by $\mathbf{a}_\alpha$.

Several approximations are required for Eq. (2.1) to be valid. When G_α consists solely of Coulomb collisions from two particles correlations, then Eq. (2.1) can be rigorously derived canonical particle dynamics through a BBGKY hierarchy.[54] This requires the assumption that particles interact by means of binary collisions. That is the Hamiltonian can be expressed as the sum of terms involving single particle variables and the sum of terms involving variables of pairs of particles but does not include triples, quadruples, etc. This is a good approximation for diffuse plasmas. However, the n 'th level equation in the BBGKY hierarchy still requires knowledge of the $n + 1$ particle distribution function. Some closure approximation must be introduced. Only the first equation in the chain is presented here. The two particle distribution function is approximated as the product of single particle distribution functions. This approximation neglects the effect of discrete inter-particle forces on the distribution of particle correlations. It is accurate for a diffuse plasma. The quantitative error scales as the inverse of the number of particles in a Debye sphere. However, this ordering breaks the time symmetry of the dynamics. That is, the BBGKY hierarchy is symmetric under time reversal but the single

particle truncation breaks this symmetry. It is at this point that macroscopic irreversibility is introduced into the system. This approximation has sometimes been referred to as the “Boltzmann Stollzansatz” or the “assumption of molecular chaos”.

When this approximation is used, G_α can then be directly estimated from knowledge of Coulomb collisions.[55] However here the discussion will be generalized a small amount by also allowing for changes in the distribution function due to effects other than simple Coulomb collisions. In practice, the separation of dynamical terms into the acceleration terms, $\mathbf{a}_\alpha$, and collision terms, G_α , contains some arbitrariness. The separation reflects the assumed ordering of large amplitude low frequency dynamics (mean field acceleration) and smaller amplitude higher frequency dynamics (Coulomb collisions). One such effect might be averaged high frequency micro-turbulence. In this work G_α is considered to include both self-consistent Coulomb collisions as well as externally specified effects. Such extra effects could include external particle sources such as fueling or fusion reactions as well as momentum and energy sources. It should be noted that these extra terms do necessarily obey the symmetry principles of the Coulomb collision operator terms. In general, G_α will be split into two parts, a Coulomb collision part, and an external part,

$$G_\alpha \equiv C_\alpha + H_\alpha \equiv \sum_{\beta} C_{\alpha\beta} + H_\alpha \quad (2.5)$$

When $H_\alpha = 0$, Eq. (2.1) can be formally derived from the exact particle dynamics in the appropriate approximation. However, when $H_\alpha \neq 0$ the situation is more complex. For example, if H_α is supposed to represent some net external source of particles, then the Hamiltonian structure of the exact

particle dynamics is corrupted. In fact, the total number of dynamical degrees of freedom is not constant. A formal derivation of Eq. (2.1) seems to require a classical equivalent of a second quantization formalism. Such an exposition is beyond this work and, I believe of only peripheral importance.

The Coulomb collision term, C_α , expresses the change in f_α due to collisions. Particles of type α are scattered by collisions with particles of all types. This process is linear. Therefore the collision operator can be represented as the sum of collisions with each species, $C_\alpha \equiv \sum_\beta C_{\alpha\beta}$. $C_{\alpha\beta}$ is the rate of change of the species α distribution function, f_α , from collisions with particles of species β . $C_{\alpha\beta}$ can be directly calculated from considerations of two particle interaction force. The result is[55, 56],

$$C_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \frac{\gamma_{\alpha\beta}}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{m_\alpha} \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} (f_\alpha \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \otimes \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} G_\beta^r) - 2 \left(\frac{1}{m_\alpha} + \frac{1}{m_\beta} \right) \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} (f_\alpha \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} H_\beta^r) \right\}, \quad (2.6)$$

where $\gamma_{\alpha\beta}$ is the Coulomb scattering coefficient,

$$\gamma_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \frac{4\pi e_\alpha^2 e_\beta^2}{m_\alpha} \ln \Lambda, \quad (2.7)$$

and $\ln \Lambda$ is the Coulomb logarithm. The notation, $\otimes$ indicates tensor product. That is the tensor product of two vectors, $\mathbf{V} \otimes \mathbf{W}$, is a second rank tensor (sometimes called a dyadic). G_β^r and H_β^r are the Rosenbluth potentials defined as,

$$H_\beta^r(\mathbf{v}) \equiv \int d^3 v' f_\beta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}') \frac{1}{u}, \quad (2.8)$$

$$G_\beta^r(\mathbf{v}) \equiv \int d^3 v' f_\beta(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}') u, \quad (2.9)$$

where $\mathbf{u} \equiv \mathbf{v} - \mathbf{v}'$.

The Coulomb collision operator contains symmetries that reflect the symmetries of Coulomb collisions. Specifically, mass, momentum, and energy

are conserved in the process. Coulomb collisions scatter particles in velocity space. In real space, the collisions are local. Therefore spatially local conservation laws can be found when the collision operators are multiplied by special functions and velocities and integrated over velocity space. For each species, they are,

$$\int d^3v C_{\alpha\beta} = 0, \quad (2.10)$$

$$\int d^3v m_\alpha \mathbf{v} C_{\alpha\beta} = - \int d^3v m_\beta \mathbf{v} C_{\beta\alpha}, \quad (2.11)$$

and

$$\int d^3v \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2 C_{\alpha\beta} = - \int d^3v \frac{1}{2} m_\beta v^2 C_{\beta\alpha}. \quad (2.12)$$

When summed over species, total conservation relations are found.

$$\sum_{\alpha,\beta} \int d^3v m_\alpha \mathbf{v} C_{\alpha\beta} = 0, \quad (2.13)$$

and

$$\sum_{\alpha,\beta} \int d^3v \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2 C_{\alpha\beta} = 0. \quad (2.14)$$

$C_{\alpha\beta}$ takes the form of a Fokker-Planck collision operator. Fokker-Planck interactions are characterized by multiple small scattering events. In a plasma, the dynamics is dominated by such effects. Since Coulombic forces are long range, the overwhelming majority of interactions are large distance, small momentum transfer events.

The external source terms, H_α , in Eq. (2.5) do not necessarily respect these symmetries. The resulting macroscopic dynamical equations will have extra terms which would vanish if H_α respected these symmetries.

2.2 Multi-Fluid Formulation

Maxwell's equation and Eq. (2.1) along with the expressions for C_α and the external specification of H_α completely specify a dynamical model evolution. This is a very detailed and complicated view which can often be simplified for cases of interest. A common simplification is to integrate over the velocity space dependence. It reduces the number of independent variables from 6 to 3, but increases the number of dependent functions, called velocity moments. Extra equations can be derived to describe the time evolution of each velocity moment, but each equation requires knowledge of a new velocity moment. At some point the system must be truncated by a closure approximation. Often this approximation is very accurate.

This process is accomplished by multiplying Eq. (2.1) by certain functions of velocity and integrated over all velocities. Define functions which are velocity integrals of f_α which will become the new dependent variables. For notational convenience, define,

$$\langle s(\mathbf{v}) \rangle \equiv \int d^3v s(\mathbf{v}), \quad (2.15)$$

as a shorthand for velocity space integration. The density of particles of type α is given by,

$$n_\alpha \equiv \langle f_\alpha \rangle. \quad (2.16)$$

The average macroscopic velocity of particles of type α is given by,

$$\mathbf{V}_\alpha \equiv \frac{1}{n_\alpha} \langle \mathbf{v} f_\alpha \rangle. \quad (2.17)$$

The pressure tensor is,

$$\vec{P}_\alpha \equiv \langle m_\alpha (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha) \otimes (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha) f_\alpha \rangle. \quad (2.18)$$

The pressure scalar is defined as,

$$P_\alpha \equiv \frac{1}{3} \sum_i \vec{P}_{\alpha ii}. \quad (2.19)$$

The temperature is defined as,

$$T_\alpha \equiv P_\alpha / n_\alpha. \quad (2.20)$$

The pressure tensor can be separated into isotropic and anisotropic parts,

$$\vec{P}_\alpha = \vec{I} P_\alpha + \vec{\Pi}_\alpha. \quad (2.21)$$

Finally, the heat flux is defined as:

$$\mathbf{D}_\alpha \equiv \left\langle \frac{1}{2} m_\alpha (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha)^2 (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha) f_\alpha \right\rangle. \quad (2.22)$$

It is possible to continue this definition process, but subsequent closure approximations will not require consideration of higher velocity moments.

Additional quantities are necessary to express various combinations of the Coulomb and external collision operators. Consider first Coulomb collision effects. The friction force on particles of species α from collisions with particles of type β is given by,

$$\mathbf{R}_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \langle m_\alpha (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha) C_{\alpha\beta} \rangle. \quad (2.23)$$

The total friction force on particles of type α is simply the sum over β ,

$$\mathbf{R}_\alpha \equiv \sum_\beta \mathbf{R}_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (2.24)$$

Eq. (2.11) then implies,

$$\mathbf{R}_{\alpha\beta} = -\mathbf{R}_{\beta\alpha} \quad (2.25)$$

and Eq. (2.13) implies,

$$\sum_{\alpha} \mathbf{R}_{\alpha} = 0. \quad (2.26)$$

Similarly the change in energy of species α due to collision with particles of type β is defined as,

$$W_{\alpha\beta} \equiv \left\langle \frac{1}{2} m_{\alpha} (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_{\alpha})^2 C_{\alpha\beta} \right\rangle, \quad (2.27)$$

and the total energy exchange is,

$$W_{\alpha} \equiv \sum_{\beta} W_{\alpha\beta}. \quad (2.28)$$

Eq. (2.12) then implies,

$$W_{\alpha\beta} = -W_{\beta\alpha} + (\mathbf{V}_{\beta} - \mathbf{V}_{\alpha}) \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha\beta} \quad (2.29)$$

and Eq. (2.14) implies,

$$\sum_{\alpha} (\mathbf{V}_{\alpha} \cdot \mathbf{R}_{\alpha} + W_{\alpha}) = 0. \quad (2.30)$$

Also define velocity integrals of the external source term, H_{α} . The net particle source, S_{α} is defined by,

$$S_{\alpha} \equiv \langle H_{\alpha} \rangle. \quad (2.31)$$

The net external momentum source is defined as,

$$\mathbf{T}_{\alpha} \equiv \langle m_{\alpha} (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_{\alpha}) H_{\alpha} \rangle. \quad (2.32)$$

Finally, the external source of internal energy is defined as,

$$X_{\alpha} \equiv \left\langle \frac{1}{2} m_{\alpha} (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_{\alpha})^2 H_{\alpha} \right\rangle. \quad (2.33)$$

With these definitions, Eq. (2.1) can be projected from a 6-dimensional phase space to 3-dimensional real space. The projection operator, $\mathcal{P}$, acting on a function, $A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})$, is simply

$$\mathcal{P}[A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})] \equiv \langle A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) \rangle = \int d^3v A(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}). \quad (2.34)$$

$\mathcal{P}$ [Eq. (2.1)] leads to the particle continuity equation,

$$\frac{\partial n_\alpha}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n_\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha) = S_\alpha. \quad (2.35)$$

$\mathcal{P}[m_\alpha \mathbf{v} \text{Eq. (2.1)}] - m_\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha \mathcal{P}[\text{Eq. (2.1)}]$ leads to the equation for the conservation of momentum,

$$m_\alpha n_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_\alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V}_\alpha \cdot \nabla \mathbf{V}_\alpha \right) = -\nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{P}_\alpha + e_\alpha n_\alpha \mathbf{E} + e_\alpha n_\alpha \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{V}_\alpha \times \mathbf{B} + \mathbf{R}_\alpha + \mathbf{T}_\alpha. \quad (2.36)$$

$\mathcal{P}[\frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2 \text{Eq. (2.1)}] - m_\alpha \mathbf{V}_\alpha \mathcal{P}[\mathbf{v} \text{Eq. (2.1)}] + (\frac{1}{2} m_\alpha v^2 - \frac{3}{2} T) \mathcal{P}[\text{Eq. (2.1)}]$ leads to the equation for energy conservation,

$$\frac{3}{2} n_\alpha \left(\frac{\partial T_\alpha}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V}_\alpha \cdot \nabla T \right) + \overset{\leftrightarrow}{P}_\alpha : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_\alpha + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}_\alpha = W_\alpha + X_\alpha - \frac{3}{2} T_\alpha S_\alpha. \quad (2.37)$$

These 3 projection operations give 5 equations for each species.

The dynamics of each species are coupled principally by their electromagnetic interactions, and secondarily by their collisional interactions (via $R_{\alpha\beta}$ and $W_{\alpha\beta}$ terms). The electromagnetic interactions are described via Maxwell's equations,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -\frac{1}{c} \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.38)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J} + \frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t}, \quad (2.39)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{E} = 4\pi\sigma, \quad (2.40)$$

$$\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0. \quad (2.41)$$

The charge density, σ , and current density $\mathbf{J}$ is the sum of the charges and current of each species,

$$\sigma \equiv \sum_{\alpha} e_{\alpha} n_{\alpha}, \quad (2.42)$$

$$\mathbf{J} \equiv \sum_{\alpha} e_{\alpha} n_{\alpha} \mathbf{V}_{\alpha}. \quad (2.43)$$

Eq. (2.1) requires the solution of N_{α} equations plus Maxwell's equations to determine the N_{α} distribution functions. Eq. (2.35), Eq. (2.36), and Eq. (2.37) together form $5N_{\alpha}$ equations. A reduction in the number of independent variables required from 6 to 3 has been accomplished as the expense of multiplying the number of equations that must be solved.

This multiplication of entities is more severe. $5N_{\alpha}$ fluid equations are derived but $13N_{\alpha}$ new functions must be specified, n_{α} , $\mathbf{V}_{\alpha}$, $\vec{P}_{\alpha}$, and $\mathbf{D}_{\alpha}$. There is also a need to specify an additional $4N_{\alpha}$ collision integrals ($\mathbf{R}_{\alpha}$ and W_{α}). This is the fluid closure problem. The multi-fluid moment equations (Eq. (2.35), Eq. (2.36), and Eq. (2.37)) are, formally, just as accurate as the kinetic Fokker-Planck equation (Eq. (2.1)) but are not closed, or self-contained.

The multi-fluid formalism also requires the specification of the external source terms; S_{α} , $\mathbf{T}_{\alpha}$, and X_{α} . Conceptually, this is not a problem, since their specification is no more arbitrary than the introduction of H_{α} in Eq. (2.1).

Thus no approximations have been made in this section. However, approximations are inevitable if any simplification is to be achieved. Relevant approximations and required assumptions will be discussed in the next section.

Finally, the reduction from a kinetic description (Eq. (2.1)) to a fluid moment description (Eq. (2.35), Eq. (2.36) and Eq. (2.37)) can be implemented

or withheld on a species by species basis. Some species can be described as fluids and others as kinetic distributions without damaging the validity of the physical description. Of course the definitions of charge and current densities (Eq. (2.42) and Eq. (2.43)) must be modified accordingly.

2.3 Reduction to One-Fluid MHD Plus Hall Terms Plus Beam Terms

In this section the model equations are further reduced to apply to the specific problems at hand. The goal is to further rearrange equations and variables to the point that the model resembles ideal MHD[57, 58] with several non-ideal extensions. Principally among these will be Hall term effects and energetic beam effects. Choose $N_\alpha = 3$ and consider electrons, ions, and beam particles, $\alpha = \{e, i, b\}$. The beam particles will also be ions, but the beam ions will generally be of higher energy. The electrons and ions will be treated as fluids while the description of the beam will retain a kinetic character.

When the beam is treated kinetically, the charge and current of the beam is defined in terms of its distribution function,

$$\sigma_b \equiv \langle e_b f_b \rangle, \quad (2.44)$$

and

$$\mathbf{J}_b \equiv \langle e_b \mathbf{v} f_b \rangle. \quad (2.45)$$

The moments of the beam distribution still exist and are well defined, but they are not considered fundamental dynamical functions but instead functionals of the beam distribution function, which will be considered a fundamental dynamical variable.

This section will make four additional physical assumptions, the Darwin approximation, small electron mass, quasi-neutrality, and specific ion and electron charge. The Darwin approximation assumes, that the displacement current in Eq. (2.39) is much smaller than current from particle motion,

$$\frac{1}{c} \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \ll \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}. \quad (2.46)$$

Eq. (2.39) then reduces to,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}. \quad (2.47)$$

This approximation eliminates electromagnetic radiation. It relaxes the numerical CFL condition associated with light-wave propagation. Any relevant physical effects from particles interacting with electromagnetic radiation are lost. They can be reintroduced (less accurately) in the H_α term in Eq. (2.1), if desired. This approximation also eliminates the dynamical evolution of the electric field. Another equation is now necessary to specify the electric field at each instant of time. Such a relation will be found below in a generalized Ohm's law below.

The assumption of small electron mass, $m_e = 0$, again allows lengthening of the computational time step by eliminating rapid electron motion as well as waves that rely on finite electron inertia. Again this advantage is gained at the cost of eliminating real physical effects such as electron polarization drift. This assumption signifies that the electrons respond instantly to any force acting upon them.

The third assumption is quasi-neutrality. The net charge at each point in space, which is the sum of the signed charges from all three species, is

assumed negligible.

$$e_i n_i + e_e n_e + \sigma_b = 0. \quad (2.48)$$

This is a good approximation for the plasma dynamics under study. It restricts the dynamics to time scales long compared to the plasma frequency and length scales long compared to the Debye length. Any charge uncovering and recovering will occur on a time scale short compared to the physics under study. However, this approximation will eliminate plasma oscillations. This is a computational advantage since the time step will not be required to resolve fast dynamics. If transport effects from Langmuir turbulence or other charge uncovering modes are of physical interest they must be reproduced in ad hoc collision terms H_α and anomalous heat conduction D_α .

A fourth approximation is that $e_i = -e_e \equiv e$. This approximation has little physical or computational significance and is not absolutely required. In fact for the problems studied in this work, the questions of impurities are not considered so this approximation is exact. It makes the following algebra simpler to follow and the results more straightforward. The assumptions of quasi-neutrality and small electron mass are also not required until later but they will simplify the algebra and leave the resulting equations less cluttered.

The strategy is to introduce a set of “single-fluid” or “one-fluid” variables that are combinations of the electron and ion moments or collision integrals. Specific sums of multiples of the moment equations are examined. The goal is to arrive at a set of equations where all physical quantities are stated in terms of single-fluid variables and quantities related to the beam distribution function or the external sources. This is only partially possible. Some explicit

electron moments will remain that will only be removed by means of further approximations.

It is useful to define δ as,

$$\delta \equiv \frac{\sigma_b}{e_i n_i}. \quad (2.49)$$

δ expresses the charge weighted ratio of the local beam density to the local ion density. When no beam is present, $\delta = 0$. Finite δ terms are connected with the addition of the beam.

Now define the One-fluid variables,

$$\rho \equiv m_i n_i + m_e n_e = m_i n_i, \quad (2.50)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_p \equiv \frac{m_i n_i \mathbf{V}_i + m_e n_e \mathbf{V}_e}{\rho} = \mathbf{V}_i, \quad (2.51)$$

$$\sigma_p \equiv e_e n_e + e_i n_i = e(n_i - n_e), \quad (2.52)$$

$$\mathbf{J}_p \equiv e_e n_e \mathbf{V}_e + e_i n_i \mathbf{V}_i = e(n_i \mathbf{V}_i - n_e \mathbf{V}_e), \quad (2.53)$$

$$\vec{\vec{P}}_p \equiv \vec{\vec{P}}_e + \vec{\vec{P}}_i, \quad (2.54)$$

$$P_p \equiv P_e + P_i, \quad (2.55)$$

$$\vec{\vec{\Pi}}_p \equiv \vec{\vec{\Pi}}_e + \vec{\vec{\Pi}}_i, \quad (2.56)$$

$$T_p \equiv T_e + T_i, \quad (2.57)$$

$$\mathbf{D}_p \equiv \mathbf{D}_e + \mathbf{D}_i, \quad (2.58)$$

$$W_p \equiv W_e + W_i. \quad (2.59)$$

We will also need to define One-fluid combinations of some integrals over external source functions.

$$S_p \equiv m_i S_i + m_e S_e = m_i S_i, \quad (2.60)$$

with the implicit assumption that S_e and S_i are of the same order in the small electron mass perturbation parameter. Additionally,

$$S_\sigma \equiv e_e S_e + e_i S_i = e(S_i - S_e), \quad (2.61)$$

is the net source of plasma charge. Finally the net external plasma momentum source and the net external plasma energy source are defined as,

$$\mathbf{T}_p \equiv \mathbf{T}_e + \mathbf{T}_i, \quad (2.62)$$

$$X_p \equiv X_e + X_i - \frac{3}{2}T_e S_e - \frac{3}{2}T_i S_i, \quad (2.63)$$

respectively.

The electron and ion moments can be expressed in terms of the single-fluid variables. The expressions for the electron density and electron velocity are,

$$n_e = (\rho/m_i)(1 + \delta) = n_i(1 + \delta), \quad (2.64)$$

$$\mathbf{V}_e = \frac{1}{1 + \delta} \left(\mathbf{V}_p - \frac{m_i}{e\rho} \mathbf{J}_p \right). \quad (2.65)$$

In the limit of no beam, the electron number density equals the ion number density. It has a finite beam correction. This expression is a result of quasi-neutrality. However, even in the limit of no beam, the electron velocity differs from the ion velocity. This is called a Hall effect. This effect is approximated away in One-fluid MHD. The electron velocity also has a finite beam correction.

The mass conservation equation is obtained by multiplying the particle continuity equation, Eq. (2.35), for ions by m_i ,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V}_p) = S_\rho. \quad (2.66)$$

The addition of the particle conservation equations, Eq. (2.35), multiplied by charge for ions and electrons yields,

$$\frac{\partial \sigma_p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_p = S_\sigma, \quad (2.67)$$

for charge continuity. However, Eq. (2.67) is not used since σ_p will not be followed dynamically. Instead $\sigma_p = -\sigma_b$ is assumed at each instance as required by quasi-neutrality (Eq. (2.48) and Eq. (2.52)). Nevertheless, Eq. (2.67) must be respected. This requires

$$S_\sigma = -e_b S_b, \quad (2.68)$$

when one notes that Eq. (2.47), Eq. (2.43), Eq. (2.45) and Eq. (2.53) imply that $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_p = -\nabla \cdot \mathbf{J}_b$. In practice, Eq. (2.68) can be easily satisfied by adjusting S_e as necessary to assure quasi-neutrality, since S_e will not appear anywhere else in the model.

A generalized Ohm's law can be derived by examining the momentum equation, Eq. (2.36) for electrons. One obtains,

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{1 + \delta} \left\{ \frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{V}_p \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{m_i}{e\rho} \left[\frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla \cdot \vec{P}_e + \mathbf{R}_e + \mathbf{T}_e \right] \right\}. \quad (2.69)$$

This equation provides an instantaneous relation for the calculation of $\mathbf{E}$ which is needed since the Darwin approximation, Eq. (2.46), eliminated the dynamical evolution of $\mathbf{E}$. $\mathbf{E}$ is now regarded as a functional of the other one-fluid variables. Eq. (2.69) allows for a non-zero $\mathbf{E}$ while we have assumed zero total charge. This is the reason for the prefix "quasi" in the quasi-neutrality approximation.

This generalized Ohm's law contains a finite beam correction in the form of the $1/(1 + \delta)$ factor as well as the Hall term (the term in square brackets).

This Hall term includes the electron friction force and external electron momentum sources. While these terms are usually neglected, they are important for accurately modelling current drive effects on the evolution of trapped flux. It is also useful to note that the $m_e = 0$, massless electron, approximation does not necessarily imply $\vec{P}_e = 0$. Even though the electron mass is small, the electron thermal velocity is large enough to make $\vec{P}_e$ comparable to $\vec{P}_i$ from the equi-partition principle.

That this is a consistent approximation is fairly subtle. Electrostatic motion from any net charge would cause motion much more violent than normal plasma motion. The motion would quickly relax until the electrostatic forces are the same magnitude as the other forces in a plasma. With this heuristic, a scaling estimate can be made. Assume $\mathbf{E} \sim \phi/L \sim T/L$, that is the electrostatic potential is as large as the internal plasma energy, as might be expected from equi-partition. Define the local charge density to number density ratio, δ_λ , as $(e_i n_i + e_e n_e + \sigma_b)/e_i n_e$. A scaling argument then gives,

$$\delta_\lambda \sim \frac{v_t^2}{L^2 \omega_{pi}^2}, \quad (2.70)$$

where $v_t \equiv \sqrt{2T/m_i}$ is a thermal (sound) velocity. Therefore δ_λ is small for time scales where the plasma frequency is large compared to the frequency of sound waves. For plasma parameters used in Ch. (3), Ch. (4), and Ch. (5), the value of δ_λ is on the order of 5.0×10^{-10} . Therefore, when $\mathbf{E} \sim T$, $\delta_\lambda = 0$ is a very good approximation. However, Poisson's equation, Eq. (2.40), is no longer respected. This is not a problem, since the right-hand-side is approximated as 0 and Ohm's Law, Eq. (2.69), gives as an expression for $\mathbf{E}$.

The one fluid momentum equation results from multiplying the momen-

tum equation, Eq. (2.36) by m_i obtaining,

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V}_p \cdot \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p \right) = -\nabla \cdot \vec{P}_p - \sigma_b \mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_b + \mathbf{T}_p. \quad (2.71)$$

σ_p was replaced by $-\sigma_b$ from quasi-neutrality. Likewise, momentum conservation of Coulomb collisions, Eq. (2.26), allows $\mathbf{R}_p \equiv \mathbf{R}_e + \mathbf{R}_i$ to be replaced by $-\mathbf{R}_b$.

Finally, the one fluid energy equation is obtained by adding the energy moment equations, Eq. (2.37), for ions and electrons giving,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{3}{2} \frac{\rho}{m_i} \frac{dT}{dt} - \frac{3}{2} \frac{1}{e} \frac{1}{1+\delta} \mathbf{J}_p \cdot \nabla T_e + \frac{3}{2} \frac{\rho}{m_i} \delta \left(\frac{\partial T_e}{\partial t} - \frac{1}{1+\delta} \mathbf{V}_p \cdot \nabla T_e \right) + \\ \vec{P}_p : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p - \frac{1}{1+\delta} \vec{P}_e : \nabla \otimes \left(\frac{m_i}{e\rho} \mathbf{J}_p \right) - \frac{\delta}{1+\delta} \vec{P}_e : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}_p = \\ W_p + X_p, \end{aligned} \quad (2.72)$$

where $\frac{d}{dt} \equiv \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V}_p \cdot \nabla$ is the Lagrangian derivative in the single-fluid velocity frame.

Maxwell's equations, Eq. (2.38)-Eq. (2.41), reduce to a single dynamical equation,

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -c \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.73)$$

and an instantaneous relation,

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_b, \quad (2.74)$$

which expresses the relationship between the magnetic field and the beam current and plasma current. The δ corrections in Eq. (2.69) and Eq. (2.72) express the beam's effect in terms of its number density compared to the ion number density. Eq. (2.74) expresses the other principal beam effect — the decoupling

of the shape of the magnetic field from the plasma current. In this regard, the beam can be regarded as an interpenetrating current. The two other Maxwell's equations are not explicitly needed.

Eq. (2.66), Eq. (2.69), Eq. (2.71), Eq. (2.72), Eq. (2.73), and Eq. (2.74) define the one-fluid model. The model is not yet self-contained. First there is the need to supply information about both the beam quantities and the other external sources that arise from integrals of H_e and H_i . Second there is a need to specify higher order one-fluid velocity moments, such as $\vec{P}_p$, W_p , and D_p , in terms of lower moments. Third, there are still uncalculated collision integrals, R_p and W_p . Finally there are remnants of electron multi-fluid variables in Ohm's law, Eq. (2.69), and the energy, equation, Eq. (2.72).

2.4 Low Beam Density Limit

The single fluid equations (Eq. (2.66), Eq. (2.69)-Eq. (2.74)) are still quite complex. They are valid for arbitrary δ . The equations are greatly simplified when the $\delta = 0$ limit is taken. The dynamical equations reduce to,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V}_p) = S_p, \quad (2.75)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{V}_p \times \mathbf{B} + \frac{m_i}{e\rho} \left[\frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla \cdot \vec{P}_e + \mathbf{R}_e + \mathbf{T}_e \right], \quad (2.76)$$

$$\rho \left(\frac{\partial \mathbf{V}_p}{\partial t} + \mathbf{V}_p \cdot \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p \right) = -\nabla \cdot \vec{P}_p + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_b + \mathbf{T}_p, \quad (2.77)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\rho}{m_i} \frac{dT}{dt} - \frac{3}{2e} \mathbf{J}_p \cdot \nabla T_e + \vec{P}_p : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p - \vec{P}_e : \nabla \otimes \left(\frac{m_i}{e\rho} \mathbf{J}_p \right) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{D}_p = W_p + X_p, \quad (2.78)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -c \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.79)$$

and

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_b. \quad (2.80)$$

It should be noted that approximating $\delta = 0$ does not imply $\mathbf{J}_b = 0$ when the beam energy is much greater than the plasma temperature. In that case a very low density beam can still contribute a large current.

Also, the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term in the momentum equation, Eq. (2.77), has been neglected. The reason for this approximation is due to numerical considerations rather than physical considerations. One would expect that this term would be of order δ in comparison to the other fluid terms. The actual ordering is δ/ϵ where ϵ is some other small parameter. This term is sometimes important, but may present numerical problems. The beam affects the fluid in three ways: First, it decouples the shape of the magnetic field from the value of the plasma current, Eq. (2.79). Second, it allows a collisional coupling to transfer momentum from the beam. Third, it allows an extra electrostatic force that gives a non-collisional momentum transfer from beam to fluid mediated by the electric field. The $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term embodies this third effect. However, its effect is not easy to predict in general and therefore it presents potential numerical difficulties.

The magnitude of the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term is estimated by comparing it to the $\frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ term in Eq. (2.77). A scaling comparison of the perturbed values of these 2 terms gives three terms, $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}_1$, $\frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{J}_{p1} \times \mathbf{B}_0$, and $\frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{J}_{p0} \times \mathbf{B}_1$, where the subscripts 0 and 1 stand for the equilibrium and perturbed quantities, respectively. The perturbed magnetic field can be estimated from Eq. (2.79) as Ekc/w , where k is a characteristic variation (radial) scale length. $\mathbf{J}_{p0}$ the diamagnetic current (equilibrium force balance) is kPc/B . $\mathbf{J}_{p1}$ is estimated as the polarization current.[59] It scales as $\mathbf{J}_{p1} \sim nm_i c^2 E\omega/B^2$. The requirement

that $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}_1 \ll \frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{J}_{p0} \times \mathbf{B}_1$ leads to,

$$\delta \ll \frac{k^2 v_t^2}{\omega \Omega_i}, \quad (2.81)$$

where Ω_i is the ion cyclotron frequency and $v_t \equiv \sqrt{sT/m_i}$ is the ion thermal (sound) velocity. The right-hand of this expression, is itself a small parameter. So to neglecting $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ requires that δ be small compared to another small parameter, and not just small compared to 1. For FRC's which are discussed in the following chapters, the right-hand-side is about 0.064, which places a fairly low upper limit on δ . The polarization current limit, places an even lower requirement on δ . It implies,

$$\delta \ll \frac{\omega}{\Omega_i}. \quad (2.82)$$

For the FRC's shown in later chapters, $\omega/\Omega_i \approx 0.00625$. In order to stabilize the tilt mode, a minimum amount of beam is required. In order to obtain enough current to stabilize the tilt mode, the number of beam particles is large enough to invalidate Eq. (2.82) for the configuration parameters considered. This issue may be important in understanding the results of Ch. (3).

2.5 Maxwellian Ions and Electrons

This section will further approximate the electron and ion distribution functions as local, time varying Maxwellians. This allows the estimation of the higher order velocity moments and collision integrals. These approximations imply the physics under study occur at a time after plasma formation that is long compared with a characteristic collision time. In this limit, collisions will have driven the plasma species toward thermodynamic equilibrium, or at least local thermodynamic equilibrium. The beam is not necessarily assumed

to have reached thermal equilibrium for two reasons. First, its energy is large enough that the energy dependence of the collision cross-section has reduced the beam collisionality sufficiently that the beam equilibration time may be long compared to the time of interest. Second, the origin of the beam may be after formation (such as energetic neutral beams) or even after ignition (fusion product produced beam). In actuality, the onset time for tilt perturbations should be on an MHD time scale after formation. Therefore the assumption of local thermodynamic equilibrium is not as valid as one would wish. Nevertheless, the assumption of Maxwellian distributions will serve as a representative set of solutions which are both realistic and pertinent. However, it will neglect possible real and observable effects from non-thermal populations. Since the tilt mode is predicted to exist, even for local Maxwellians, this approximation seems justified, at least as an initial approach.

Assume the electron distribution function is given by,

$$f_e(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) = f_e^0 + \tilde{f}_e = \frac{n_e(\mathbf{r})}{\pi^{3/2} v_{te}^3} \exp \left\{ \frac{-(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_e(\mathbf{r}))^2}{v_{te}^2} \right\} + \tilde{f}_e(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}), \quad (2.83)$$

where v_{te} is the electron thermal velocity defined by,

$$v_{te} \equiv \sqrt{2T_e(\mathbf{r})/m_e}, \quad (2.84)$$

and $\tilde{f}_e(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) \ll f_e^0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$ is the departure from a local Maxwellian.

The ion distribution is similarly assumed to be near a local Maxwellian,

$$f_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) = f_i^0 + \tilde{f}_i = \frac{n_i(\mathbf{r})}{\pi^{3/2} v_{ti}^3} \exp \left\{ \frac{-(\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_i(\mathbf{r}))^2}{v_{ti}^2} \right\} + \tilde{f}_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}), \quad (2.85)$$

where v_{ti} is the ion thermal velocity defined by,

$$v_{ti} \equiv \sqrt{2T_i(\mathbf{r})/m_i}, \quad (2.86)$$

and again a $\tilde{f}_i(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}) \ll f_i^0(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v})$ ordering is assumed. As mentioned above, $T_e \sim T_i$ is assumed. This implies that $v_{te} \gg v_{ti}$.

A perturbation series can be constructed where the lowest order is a Maxwellian and next order is given by $\tilde{f}_e$. If n_e , $\mathbf{V}_e$, and T_e are constant in space and time, then f_e^0 is in the null space of the operator on the left-hand side of equation Eq. (2.1). Therefore, G_e acting on a spatially and temporally uniform f_e^0 is also 0. If n_e , $\mathbf{V}_e$, and T_e depend on time and space, then the left hand side of Eq. (2.1) is not 0, but can also be expanded in a perturbation series in terms of characteristic lengths and times, such as the ratio of Larmor radius to gradient scale length. These can then be used to estimate the action of G_e on f_e in a Chapman-Enskog process.[60] This process will allow the calculation of the higher order velocity moments and collision integrals. This Maxwellian closure process can, in principle be carried out to any order, although in practice it is difficult and tedious. Here all zeroth order terms and some of the first order terms are retained. First order terms that appear only in the energy equation, Eq. (2.78), are neglected.

This assumption is not *a priori* justified. In fact it may not even be justified *a posteriori*. It is a simplicity assumption. Energy transport will not be modelled in as accurate detail as momentum and induction. Detailed energy transport is not the focus of this work. Accurate descriptions of energy transport would require the inclusion of many other effects, such as anomalous transport, which have already been neglected. On a practical level, this is an appropriate approximation. The tilt mode and the beam's effect upon it are manifested primarily through the momentum equation and the induction equation. Nevertheless, on a formal level, these perturbation expansions are now

inconsistent in that some first order terms are kept while others are discarded. This is particularly true for the energy equation itself where first order terms which also appear in other equations will be retained for completeness while other terms of the same order in the perturbation series are dropped.

This same approximation philosophy will be used in other cases below. The focus will be on the physics intended for study. For those terms whose physical effects are peripheral to the problems under study, approximate expressions are used. The justification is that an approximation error from a term which is designed to be of secondary physical importance should not destroy the integrity of the physical model or simulation. These approximations will be leading order accurate and simple. A more rigorous methodology would either neglect the term entirely or express it correctly in detail. In this sense, this model carries along terms similar to neglected errors and in that manner this model will have "probes" to test the validity of neglected errors. For example, the full gyroviscosity is approximated by a simple dynamical viscosity below. The strength of the dynamic viscosity coefficient is used to test whether the simulation results are sensitive to the viscosity. If they are not then there is some justification for neglecting the details of gyroviscosity.

Now lets calculate those quantities in the one-fluid model which can be specified by this closure scheme; $\mathbf{R}_e$, $\vec{P}_e$, $\vec{P}_p$, W_p , and $\mathbf{D}_p$. First consider the zeroth order terms arising from f_e^0 and f_i^0 . One finds,

$$\vec{P}_e = \vec{I} n_e T_e, \quad (2.87)$$

$$\vec{P}_p = \vec{I} \rho T_p / m_i, \quad (2.88)$$

and

$$\mathbf{D}_p = 0, \quad (2.89)$$

for the higher order moments. Neglect the first order term in $\mathbf{D}_p$ since it only appears in the energy equation.

The first order expressions for P_e and P_p are traceless. Both are complex with coefficients that depend on collisionality and magnetic field strength.[60] Since this term is small, it is replaced with its hydrodynamic counterpart, the dynamic viscosity. Under this approximation, the full pressure tensors (zeroth and first order) are expressed as

$$\vec{P}_e = \vec{I} n_e T_e + \vec{\Pi}_e, \quad (2.90)$$

with

$$\vec{\Pi}_e = -(\nabla \otimes \mu_e \mathbf{V}_e) - (\nabla \otimes \mu_e \mathbf{V}_e)^T + (\nabla \cdot \mu_e \mathbf{V}_e) \vec{I}, \quad (2.91)$$

and

$$\vec{P}_p = \vec{I} \rho T_p / m_i + \vec{\Pi}_p, \quad (2.92)$$

with

$$\vec{\Pi}_p = -(\nabla \otimes \mu_p \mathbf{V}_p) - (\nabla \otimes \mu_p \mathbf{V}_p)^T + (\nabla \cdot \mu_p \mathbf{V}_p) \vec{I}. \quad (2.93)$$

Both μ_p and μ_e will be specified in terms of global Reynolds numbers instead of physical values. This will allow modelling of anomalously high viscosity easily. It should be emphasized here and below, that $\vec{P}_\alpha$ in Eq. (2.93) is not a gyroviscosity. The gyroviscosity is physical. The hydro-dynamical viscosity will only be an order of magnitude estimate of viscous effects. If the details of the viscosity are important, then more accurate modelling will be required.

$\mathbf{R}_e$ consists of two parts, $\mathbf{R}_e = \mathbf{R}_{ei} + \mathbf{R}_{eb}$. $\mathbf{R}_{eb} = -\mathbf{R}_{be}$, will require knowledge of the beam distribution and therefore is not yet closed. However, $\mathbf{R}_{ei}$ can be directly integrated from f_e^0 and f_i^0 obtaining,

$$\mathbf{R}_{ei} = \frac{\rho e}{m_i} \eta \mathbf{J}_p, \quad (2.94)$$

where η is the resistivity defined as[61]

$$\eta \equiv \frac{m_e m_i}{\rho e^2 \tau_{ei}} = \frac{16\sqrt{\pi} e^2 \ln \Lambda}{3 m_e v_{te}^3} \quad (2.95)$$

The collisional energy exchange, W_p consists of two parts, collisions between electrons and ions and collisions between the beam and electrons or ions. Eq. (2.28), Eq. (2.14), Eq. (2.12), Eq. (2.59), and Eq. (2.94) together imply,

$$W_p = \eta \mathbf{J}_p^2, \quad (2.96)$$

when the beam plasma collision terms, W_b , $\mathbf{R}_{bi}$ and $\mathbf{R}_{be}$, are neglected since they are in the energy equation.

For additional ease let us also assume that the plasma source terms, Eq. (2.60), Eq. (2.32), Eq. (2.62), and Eq. (2.63), are absent, which is the case for the problems examined here. Take $S_\rho = 0$, $\mathbf{T}_e = 0$, $\mathbf{T}_p = 0$ and $X_p = 0$.

With these further approximations, the dynamical equations, Eq. (2.75)-Eq. (2.80), reduce to,

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V}_p) = 0, \quad (2.97)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{V}_p \times \mathbf{B} + \eta \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{m_i}{e\rho} \left[\frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla P_e - \nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi}_e - \mathbf{R}_{be} \right], \quad (2.98)$$

$$\rho \frac{d\mathbf{V}_p}{dt} = -\nabla P_p - \nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi}_p + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_b, \quad (2.99)$$

$$\frac{3}{2} \frac{\rho}{m_i} \frac{dT}{dt} - \frac{3}{2e} \mathbf{J}_p \cdot \nabla T_e + P_p \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V}_p + \vec{\Pi}_p : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p - \vec{P}_e : \nabla \otimes \left(\frac{m_i}{e\rho} \mathbf{J}_p \right) = \eta \mathbf{J}_p^2, \quad (2.100)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -c \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.101)$$

and

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_b. \quad (2.102)$$

2.6 Complete Fluid Plasma Closure

A few more approximations are now apparent. The justification is that certain terms in Eq. (2.97)–Eq. (2.101) are small and that they contain within them terms, some of which are even smaller. In this vein, the term in brackets in Eq. (2.98) is small compared to $\frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{V}_p \times \mathbf{B}$. Within the brackets, $\vec{\Pi}_e \ll \nabla P_e$ and will be neglected. Similarly the $\vec{P}_e$ term in the energy equation is small compared to the P_p and $\vec{\Pi}_p$ terms. Since the entire energy equation is regarded as a small term in that it is only zeroth order accurate, the $\vec{P}_e$ term can be neglected. Likewise the $\frac{3}{2e} \mathbf{J}_p \cdot \nabla T_e$ is small compared to the $\frac{3}{2} \frac{\rho}{m_i} \frac{dT}{dt}$ term.

ρ often enters in the combination ρ/m_i . It is useful to use $n_p \equiv n_i$ as the dynamical variable.

The energy equation is transformed into an equation for the entropy density since it is conserved under adiabatic motion. Define,

$$S_p \equiv n_p^{\gamma-2} T_p, \quad (2.103)$$

as an entropy density. When $\gamma = 5/3$, Eq. (2.100) becomes

$$\frac{\partial S_p}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (S_p \mathbf{V}_p) = (\gamma - 1) n_p^{1-\gamma} \left(\eta \mathbf{J}_p^2 - \vec{\Pi}_p : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V}_p \right). \quad (2.104)$$

Lastly, P_e must be obtained. P_e only remains in the Hall correction term to Ohm's law, Eq. (2.98), but it is a leading order term in the Hall correction and thus cannot be neglected. A very simple assumption is,

$$P_e \equiv f_{te} P_p = f_{te} n_p T_p, \quad (2.105)$$

where f_{te} is a chosen constant. f_{te} is chosen to match experiments. This is an *ad hoc* approximation, even if it is chosen to match empirical values.

At this level we have obtained a set of dynamical equations that are closed with respect to fluid plasma variables. The only external parameters are the effects of the beam on the plasma in form of $\mathbf{J}_b$ and $\mathbf{R}_{be}$ and $\mathbf{R}_b$ terms. Therefore let me restate the dynamical equations in their final form. The p subscript is omitted as understood, except as a subscript to the current.

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n\mathbf{V}) = 0, \quad (2.106)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{-1}{c} \mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B} + \eta \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{1}{en} \left[\frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - f_{te} \nabla(nT) - \mathbf{R}_{be} \right], \quad (2.107)$$

$$m_i n \frac{d\mathbf{V}}{dt} = -\nabla P - \nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_b, \quad (2.108)$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (S\mathbf{V}) = (\gamma - 1) n^{1-\gamma} \left(\eta \mathbf{J}_p^2 - \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi} : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V} \right). \quad (2.109)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -c \nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.110)$$

and

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{B} = \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_p + \frac{4\pi}{c} \mathbf{J}_b. \quad (2.111)$$

It should also be recalled that $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi}$ had been approximated as a hydro-dynamic viscosity in Eq. (2.108) and not a full gyroviscosity.

2.7 Beam Closure

The fluid dynamical equations, Eq. (2.106)–Eq. (2.110), still require specification of the beam terms. One simple, and first step is to assume that the beam terms have given forms which are fixed in time, externally specified, or specified in terms of the plasma variables, or some option of all three. This type of model will recover some of the aspects of the beam's effect on the plasma which is important. However, to study self-consistent evolution of the effect of fluid motion on the dynamics of the beam will require a model that allows for dynamical evolution of the beam.

The beam is modelled dynamically using a kinetic description, Eq. (2.1). Since the electrons and ions are assumed to be Maxwellian with comparable temperatures, C_{be} and C_{bi} can be explicitly stated in terms of f_b and the Maxwellian variables, n_e , V_e , T_e , n_i , V_i , and T_i . For a Maxwellian target species, α , the Rosenbluth potentials, Eq. (2.8) and Eq. (2.9), simplify to [56],

$$H_\alpha^{Mr} = \frac{n_\alpha}{v_{t\alpha}\zeta_\alpha} \text{erf}(\zeta_\alpha), \quad (2.112)$$

$$G_\alpha^{Mr} = \frac{n_\alpha v_{t\alpha}}{2\zeta_\alpha} \left[\zeta_\alpha \text{erf}'(\zeta_\alpha) + (1 + 2\zeta_\alpha^2 \text{erf}(\zeta_\alpha)) \right], \quad (2.113)$$

where

$$\zeta_\alpha \equiv \frac{\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_\alpha}{v_{t\alpha}}, \quad (2.114)$$

for $\alpha = i$ or e , and

$$\text{erf}(x) \equiv \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x dy \exp -y^2, \quad (2.115)$$

and

$$\text{erf}'(x) \equiv \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp -x^2. \quad (2.116)$$

Once G_b , the beam source term, is specified the beam dynamics are completely specified and the coupled fluid beam system is closed.

$C_{b\alpha}$ requires calculation of second velocity derivatives of the distribution function. However, f_b is represented with a fixed weight particle-in-cell (PIC) simulation. Calculation of such a force is not possible in a PIC simulation. Moreover, such a force acting on a particle in the simulation does not respect the particle's integrity. Diffusive forces attempt to smear the simulation particle over larger areas in velocity space, but the particle's size is fixed.

$C_{b\alpha}$ is approximated by a form that is amenable to PIC simulation. First note that the second velocity derivatives of f_b only occur in collision terms connected with the velocity-space diffusion potential, G_β^{Mr} in Eq. (2.6). Secondly, the G_β^{Mr} term of the collision operator does not contribute to $\mathbf{R}_{b\alpha}$. This can be seen by inserting the RMJ form of the collision operator, Eq. (2.6), into the definition of the friction force, Eq. (2.23). Even after integrating by parts, the term containing G_β^{Mr} is still a total velocity derivative. Since the limits of integration are infinite, the boundary term contribution vanishes. Therefore, the friction force is solely a consequence of the drag potential, H_β^{Mr} and independent of the diffusion potential, G_β^{Mr} .

Consequently, the diffusion part of the collision operator is neglected in favor of the drag term. This approximation is the opposite of the often used Lorentz-gas approximation.[60, 56] When the thermal velocity of the projectile and target are similar, then diffusion is the principal scattering mechanism. However, when the beam velocity is much greater than the thermal velocity, the opposite holds. For the problems of interest in FRC's, the beams will be very energetic. For example, current size experiments will require neutral

beams with an energy of ≈ 100 KeV while the plasma temperature is ~ 1 KeV. In ignition scenarios the plasma temperature is of the order of 50-80 KeV and the proton energy is 14 MeV. In this limit, the beam velocity is the same magnitude as the electron thermal velocity. Collisions will consist of both diffusion and slowing down motion. That is the physical problems of interest lie between the drag approximation used here and the Lorentz-gas approximation.

Completely neglecting the diffusive effects of collisions is problematic. I would hesitate to make this approximation if it were not imposed upon me by the confines of the fixed weight PIC algorithm. It may be possible to include diffusion effects in future PIC formulations, but that is beyond this investigation. As a first approximation of collisional effects this assumption is useful. It allows investigation of self-consistent beam distribution functions where the beam source (either from neutral beam guns or fusion reactions) can be balanced by losses from collisions with the fluid plasma.

With this approximation the collision operator reduces to,

$$C_{b\alpha} = \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} (\mathbf{d}_{\alpha} f_b), \quad (2.117)$$

where $\mathbf{d}_{\alpha}$ is the drag coefficient defined as,

$$\mathbf{d}_{\alpha} \equiv K_{\alpha} \frac{\zeta_{\alpha}}{\zeta_{\alpha}^2} \kappa(\zeta_{\alpha}), \quad (2.118)$$

with,

$$K_{\alpha} \equiv \frac{\gamma_{b\alpha} n_{\alpha}}{v_{t\alpha}^2} \left(\frac{1}{m_b} + \frac{1}{m_{\alpha}} \right), \quad (2.119)$$

and

$$\kappa(\zeta_{\alpha}) \equiv \frac{-dH^M r_{\alpha}(\zeta_{\alpha})}{d\zeta_{\alpha}} = \frac{1}{\zeta_{\alpha}^2} \text{erf}(\zeta_{\alpha}) - \frac{1}{\zeta_{\alpha}} \text{erf}'(\zeta_{\alpha}). \quad (2.120)$$

With this form, the kinetic equation for the beam, Eq. (2.1) can be re-written as,

$$\frac{\partial f_b}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla f_b + \mathbf{a}_b \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} f_b - \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot [(\mathbf{d}_e + \mathbf{d}_i) f_b] = H_b. \quad (2.121)$$

One final approximation will now be considered. Assume that $|\mathbf{d}_i| \ll |\mathbf{d}_e|$ for problems of interest. For beam particles with thermal velocities much larger than the target particle's thermal velocity, $\zeta_\alpha \gg 1$. In that limit, $\kappa(\zeta_\alpha) \sim 1/\zeta_\alpha^2$. Therefore, $|\mathbf{d}_i| \ll |\mathbf{d}_e|$ with the ratio being of the order of $\sqrt{\frac{m_e}{m_i}}$. However, for beam particles with velocities less than the target's thermal velocity, $\kappa(\zeta_\alpha) \sim \zeta_\alpha$, then $|\mathbf{d}_i| \gg |\mathbf{d}_e|$. This can be understood intuitively. For a single collision, a beam-ion will transfer much more momentum than a beam-electron collision. However, if the beam is traveling much faster than the thermal velocities, there will be many more electron collisions than ion collisions. This is a consequence of the fact that $v_{te} \gg v_{ti}$ and that the Coulomb cross-section decreases as the center of mass energy increases. That is, the beam will be most strongly affected by collisions with ions and electrons with velocities near the beam velocity. If the beam velocity is below the thermal velocities, then there is an abundance of ion scatters that will dominate the drag. If the beam velocity is much larger than the thermal velocities, then there will be many more electron scatterers than ion scatterers. This ration scales like an exponential of the square root of the mass ratio. This scaling becomes more important than the fact that each electron collision transfers a factor of m_e/m_i less momentum. That is, each electron impact transfers m_e/m_i less momentum than each ion impact, but there are $\exp(\sqrt{m_i/m_e})$ more electron impacts than ion impacts.

Therefore, the $|\mathbf{d}_i| \ll |\mathbf{d}_e|$ approximation is valid except for velocities at or below the thermal velocities, but in this region, the diffusion term is large

compared to the drag term. Therefore, the $|\mathbf{d}_i| \ll |\mathbf{d}_e|$ approximation is justified. That is if this approximation is invalid, then my previous neglect of the diffusion term is also invalid. These approximations will lead to unphysical motion for beams when they have slowed to near the electron thermal velocity. In the other cases, however, they are valid approximations. In short, a superthermal beam will decay primarily due to drag from electron collisions. This fact is well known.[62] Neglecting ion drag terms will also require a slight modification of the plasma dynamical equations. $\mathbf{R}_b$ becomes $\mathbf{R}_{be}$ in Eq. (2.108) since $\mathbf{R}_{bi}$ has been neglected.

It should also be noted that the kinetic equation can be placed either in a Hamiltonian form as shown in Eq. (2.1) or in a phase space conservative form since $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot \mathbf{a}_{\alpha} = 0$. The kinetic equation is stated in the flux conservative form. In this form, the term from drag collisions will appear simply as an additional acceleration,

$$\frac{\partial f_b}{\partial t} + \nabla(\mathbf{v}f_b) + \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot [(\mathbf{a}_b - \mathbf{d}_e)f_b] = H_b. \quad (2.122)$$

This equation, along with the definitions for $\mathbf{R}_{be}$, $\mathbf{J}_b$ will close the system. The form of Eq. (2.122) is now amenable to normal PIC simulation methods. The fact that finite sized particle methods simulate flux conservative equations of the form of Eq. (2.122) is somewhat subtle. An explanation is given in the Appendix. The individual particles move with the modified equations of motion,

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}}{dt} = \mathbf{v}, \quad (2.123)$$

and

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}}{dt} = \mathbf{a}_b - \mathbf{d}_e. \quad (2.124)$$

Particles are created or destroyed along their trajectories according to H_b , which must be additionally specified for each problem considered.

It is instructive to examine the final form of the drag coefficient and to recall the approximations used to arrive at it. Eq. (2.118) is

$$\mathbf{d}_e \equiv K_e \frac{\boldsymbol{\zeta}_e}{\zeta_e} \kappa(\zeta_e). \quad (2.125)$$

$\boldsymbol{\zeta}_e \equiv (\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_e)v_{te}$ is the dimensionless velocity vector. It is normalized by the electron thermal velocity and has been translated so that its origin coincides with the electron bulk motion. $K_e \equiv \gamma_{be} n_e / v_{te}^2 (1/m_b + 1/m_e)$ is the collision normalizing factor that gives the overall magnitude of the drag. $\boldsymbol{\zeta}_e / \zeta_e$ is a unit vector in the direction of the velocity difference and $\kappa(\zeta_e)$ is a shape function that gives the velocity dependence of the drag. For large ζ_e , $\kappa \sim 1/\zeta_e^2$, which is simply the “one over energy” factor in the cross sections.

In deriving this expression, collisional diffusion is neglected in favor of collisional drag and the ion-drag is neglected compared to electron drag. These approximations are appropriate when the beam velocity is much larger than the electron thermal velocity.[63] They are similar to previous classical transport drag analysis used to study current drive from injected beams.[62] The validity of these two approximations is only marginally satisfied for neutral beam injection schemes in an FRC.

2.8 Formulation Summary

For summary purposes let me list the components of this plasma plus beam model including that dynamical equations and constitutive relations. These equations, or further simplified equations are used as the basis of the sim-

ulations presented in the other chapters. The equations governing the fluid dynamical variables are,

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n\mathbf{V}) = 0, \quad (2.126)$$

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{-1}{c}\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B} + \eta\mathbf{J}_p + \frac{1}{en} \left[\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - f_{te}\nabla(nT) - \mathbf{R}_{be} \right], \quad (2.127)$$

$$m_i n \frac{d\mathbf{V}}{dt} = -\nabla P - \nabla \cdot \vec{\Pi} + \frac{1}{c}\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_{be}, \quad (2.128)$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (S\mathbf{V}) = (\gamma - 1)n^{1-\gamma} \left(\eta\mathbf{J}_p^2 - \vec{\Pi} : \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V} \right). \quad (2.129)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = -c\nabla \times \mathbf{E}, \quad (2.130)$$

and

$$\frac{4\pi}{c}\mathbf{J}_p = \nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{4\pi}{c}\mathbf{J}_b. \quad (2.131)$$

The beam terms are given by,

$$\frac{\partial f_b}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{v}f_b) + \nabla_{\mathbf{v}} \cdot [(\mathbf{a}_b - \mathbf{d}_e)f_b] = H_b, \quad (2.132)$$

where

$$\mathbf{a}_b \equiv \frac{e_b}{m_b} \left(\mathbf{E} + \frac{1}{c}\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B} \right), \quad (2.133)$$

and

$$\mathbf{d}_e \equiv K_e \frac{\zeta_e}{\zeta_e} \kappa(\zeta_e), \quad (2.134)$$

along with the definitions;

$$K_e \equiv \frac{\gamma_{be} n_e}{v_{te}^2} \left(\frac{1}{m_b} + \frac{1}{m_e} \right), \quad (2.135)$$

$$\kappa(\zeta_e) = \frac{1}{\zeta_e^2} \text{erf}(\zeta_e) - \frac{1}{\zeta_e} \text{erf}'(\zeta_e), \quad (2.136)$$

$$\gamma_{be} \equiv \frac{4\pi e_b^2 e}{m_b} \ln \Lambda, \quad (2.137)$$

$$\zeta_e \equiv \frac{\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{V}_e}{v_{te}}, \quad (2.138)$$

$$v_{te} \equiv \sqrt{2T_e(\mathbf{r})/m_e}, \quad (2.139)$$

$$\text{erf}(x) \equiv \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \int_0^x dy \exp -y^2, \quad (2.140)$$

and

$$\text{erf}'(x) \equiv \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \exp -x^2. \quad (2.141)$$

$\mathbf{R}_{be}$ and $\mathbf{J}_b$ are given by,

$$\mathbf{R}_{be} \equiv \langle m_b \mathbf{d}_e f_b \rangle, \quad (2.142)$$

and

$$\mathbf{J}_b \equiv \langle e_b \mathbf{v} f_b \rangle. \quad (2.143)$$

2.9 Beam Effects — Intuitive Analysis

The subsequent chapters will explore some features of a beam modified FRC. Ch. (3) includes a study the effect of a beam beam on the tilt mode by modifying the $\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ force. Ch. (5) examines an effect that can be created from the beam drag force in the momentum equation. Other researchers have looked at the possibility of using a beam to sustain the plasma current.[62, 18, 64] Additionally, the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term that was neglected in § (2.4) provides an additional coupling of injected beam to plasma momentum. Considerable research has been conducted concerning the effect of the introduction of energetic beams.[65, 66, 67] Several effects have been noted. The background plasma reacts to the injected beam current by reducing its own current.[62, 65] However, some net current drive can be recovered if $Z_b \neq Z_{eff}$, the effective Z of the plasma.[62] For beams injected perpendicular to the magnetic field (as is the case for FRC's) the plasma return current will completely cancel the injected current for times short compared to an Alfvén transit time. However, if the beam is injected

over a longer period the injected beam can be an effective source of current drive.[66] Additionally, the imposition of multi-pole fields can also inhibit the plasma return current.[67].

This section will examine the physical effects which remain in the formulation given in § (2.8). A heuristic analysis is presented whose aim is to highlight the various terms in the equations that represent these physical effects. For completeness, discussion of the the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term that was neglected in § (2.4) is also included. For purposes of this heuristic, consider Eq. (2.126)-Eq. (2.131) along with the following assumptions; the beam is given fixed in time with $\mathbf{J}_b = J_b \hat{\theta}$, the configuration is 1-dimensional ($\partial/\partial\theta = \partial/\partial z = 0$), viscosity and Hall terms are neglected, except for the beam drag terms in Ohm's law and the momentum equation, $\mathbf{V} = V_r \hat{r} + V_\theta \hat{\theta}$, and $\mathbf{B} = B \hat{z}$. Also approximate the electron-beam collision term as if the beam were Maxwellian, $-\mathbf{R}_{be} = \mathbf{R}_{eb} = n_e \eta_b \mathbf{J}_b$ where η_b is defined as $\eta_b = (Z_b/Z_{eff})\eta$. Eq. (2.126) and Eq. (2.129) reduce to simple forms that simply express the conservation of particles and the conservation of entropy (along with local resistive entropy generation) in the prescribed flow.

The z-component of the induction equation, Eq. (2.130), becomes,

$$\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} r \left[V_r B + \frac{\eta c}{4\pi} B' \right] + c\eta (1 - Z_b/Z_{eff}) \frac{1}{r} \frac{d}{dr} (r J_b), \quad (2.144)$$

where ' denotes $\frac{d}{dr}$. The effect of the beam is to offset the resistive flux loss if $1 - Z_b/Z_{eff} > 0$. This is the well known Ohkawa current.[62]

The r-component of Eq. (2.128) becomes,

$$m_i n \left(\frac{\partial V_r}{\partial t} + V_r V_r' - \frac{1}{r} V_\theta^2 \right) = -P' - \frac{1}{4\pi} B B' - \frac{1}{c} J_b B. \quad (2.145)$$

If the magnetic field remains fixed, the main correction to momentum balance across the flux surfaces is the $(-1/c)\mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B}$ term which due to part of the current which forms the magnetic field being carried by the beam. This effect is the focus of the studies in Ch. (3) where this beam force is used to affect the FRC's response to tilt perturbations.

The θ -component of Eq. (2.128) becomes,

$$m_i n \left(\frac{\partial V_\theta}{\partial t} + V_r V_\theta' + \frac{1}{r} V_r V_\theta \right) = n e \eta J_b (Z_b / Z_{eff}). \quad (2.146)$$

The right-hand-side is the angular momentum source. The left-hand-side is the radial convection of angular momentum and the generation of rotation (spin-up). In the time asymptotic limit, Eq. (2.146) will fix the radial profile of v_θ to be self-consistent. The existence of radial flow will also require that there be a source of density and entropy in order for n and S to have non-zero time asymptotic values.

Eq. (2.145) and Eq. (2.146) should also include $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ terms. The correction to Eq. (2.145) is minimal since E_r is simply $-V_\theta B/c$. This term will not be important, except for late time, very strong beam situations where the entire plasma is spinning supersonically. However, this term is an important correction to Eq. (2.146) since $E_\theta = V_r B/c - \eta c B' / 4\pi - (1 - Z_b / Z_{eff}) \eta J_b$. This will affect plasma spin up and final rotation states. This question is considered in Ch. (5). However, there, the whole of the beam effects are grouped together and considered as a given external force.

Finally, it should be noted that this section is only heuristic. It highlights the coupling of the dynamical variables. Any solution should be self-consistent. Therefore any analysis must provide a full explanation of the com-

plete feedback system to be complete. Of particular interest is the response of the beam to the changing electric and magnetic fields.

Chapter 3

Neutral Beam Capture and Tilt Mode Stabilization

3.1 Origin of Beam Stabilization Concepts

The simulational[6, 33, 32] and theoretical[28, 29, 30] prediction of a rapid and violent tilt mode (Fig. (1.2)) and its apparent experimental absence quickly gave rise to speculations to explain the discrepancy. Since the experimental FRC's were small, high beta devices, finite Larmor radius (FLR) and other kinetic effects were thought to be the cause of the observed non-fluid behavior. Later detailed analyses[41] and kinetic simulations [45, 43] confirmed this. This led to an accepted interpretation that kinetic effects could explain the observed stability of the then current experiments. However, next generation machines would be larger and would be expected to behave in a more fluid-like manner, as would scalings towards hypothetical reactor-sized devices. Therefore the tilt mode was considered a dangerous mode that was in need of some sort of stabilization mechanism for magnetic fusion based on the FRC concept to be viable. It was quickly recognized that the injection of a super-thermal beam offered the possibility of stabilizing the tilt mode.[1, 47] These ideas borrowed heavily from earlier alternative concept ideas for fusion such as Astron[68, 65] and energetic electron rings. The notion is that a small beam population of

very high energy could provide a large portion of the total current. This would reduce the unstable $\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ force while retaining the same overall magnetic structure since the considerable $\mathbf{J}_b$ could be relied upon to supply the additional current. Additionally, the response of the beam to tilt perturbations in the magnetic field would not necessarily be the same as the background fluid. Thus the beam could be used dynamically to add a restoring (stabilizing) force to the destabilizing fluid response.[46] Moreover, a detailed Vlasov-fluid dispersion functional approach indicated that the kinetic stabilization mechanism scales like a 4th order velocity moment of the plasma distribution function.[41] Therefore only a small super-thermal population may be required to stabilize the tilt mode if it is energetic enough.

The use of axis encircling beams for tilt stabilization offers the possibility of nicely dovetailing with other suggested use of beams in FRC's such as current drive,[62, 49] energy input[18], and rotational mode stabilization[69, 70]. However, these are different problems as was discussed in § (2.9). Current drive is connected with beam modification of the induction equation while tilt stabilization will arise principally from the $-\mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B}/c$ force term. Beam energy input will be manifested in the entropy equation and rotational analysis will come from the θ component of the momentum equation. Of course, all of these effects will be present simultaneously in an experiment. The point is that axis encircling beams may be a single answer for several problems. Of course it may present problems of its own that must be considered.

This chapter will further investigate the possibility of stabilizing the tilt mode by use of the force on the plasma from an injected beam. It will focus on proposed high current short pulse beam guns injecting into FRC's similar

to current generation experiments. The primary issues studied are the fraction of injected beam that is useful for stabilization and the effect of such a beam on the tilt mode.

3.2 Large Particle Orbits in FRC's

An energetic beam is a collection of charged particles which execute large, and sometimes exotic, orbits. The size of these orbits are on the same scale as the entire device. These orbits are very different from drift orbits where gyromotion is the dominant effect with higher order drifts superimposed on this motion. Consequently, the response of large orbit particles to perturbations can differ quantitatively and qualitatively from drift orbit particles. The basic notion is that a charged particle with a certain kinetic energy at a certain radius will execute a perfect Larmor orbit that will encircle the axis. The radius is somewhere between the radius of the O-point and the radius of the separatrix at the midplane. This can be seen by examining an "optimum orbit" for a particle of a given energy. An "optimum orbit" is defined as a particle trajectory that has no motion in the r or z directions. The particle simply moves in θ around the torus of the FRC. Elsewhere, these terms are more often referred to as "equilibrium betatron orbit".[59, 71] An optimum orbit is perfectly circular without any superimposed betatron oscillations. If the energy is low, then the orbit is near the O-point. Since the magnetic field is weak in that region, the size of the Larmor radius is on the scale of the entire device. As the particle energy increases, the radius of "optimum orbit" increases. This size of the increase is determined by two competing factors. First the simple increasing of the particle's energy will, in a uniform magnetic field, lead to an increase

in Larmor radius in proportion with the square root of the energy. However, in an FRC, the magnitude of the magnetic field is increasing in r from the O-point (field null) to the separatrix. This increase in magnetic field tends to decrease the Larmor radius. The net result is that the radius of the optimum orbit increases with increasing beam energy, but not as fast as the $\sqrt{E}$ scaling because of magnetic field inhomogeneities.

Since FRC's have toroidal symmetry, there exist two constants of particle motion (in a magnetic field fixed in time), H and P_θ , the energy and canonical angular momentum of the particles. In terms of the particles' velocities and masses they are defined as,

$$H \equiv \frac{1}{2}mv^2 = \frac{1}{2}m(v_r^2 + v_\theta^2 + v_z^2), \quad (3.1)$$

$$P_\theta \equiv mrv_\theta + \frac{e}{c}\Psi, \quad (3.2)$$

where, $\Psi \equiv rA_\theta$, is the poloidal magnetic flux defined by,

$$\Psi(r, z) \equiv \int_0^r dr' r' B_z(r', z). \quad (3.3)$$

The other canonical momenta of interest are P_r and P_z , the momenta in the r and z directions defined as,

$$P_z \equiv mv_z, \quad (3.4)$$

$$P_r \equiv mv_r. \quad (3.5)$$

They are not constants of the motion. In terms of the canonical momenta, the energy (Hamiltonian) can be expressed as,

$$H = \frac{1}{2m} \left[P_r^2 + P_z^2 + \frac{1}{r^2} \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c}\Psi \right)^2 \right] \quad (3.6)$$

The canonical equations of particle motion are,

$$\dot{P}_r = \frac{1}{mr^3} \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c} \Psi \right) \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c} \Psi + \frac{er}{c} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial r} \right), \quad (3.7)$$

$$\dot{P}_z = \frac{e}{mcr^2} \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c} \Psi \right) \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z}. \quad (3.8)$$

P_θ and H are constants of motion.

This knowledge allows the estimation or integration of particle orbits for particles which are not in an "optimum orbit". An orbit will be (partially) determined by its constants of motion, H and P_θ . If at a given point in space, (r, z) ,

$$\frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} = 0, \quad (3.9)$$

$$P_\theta = \frac{e}{c} \left(\Psi - r \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial r} \right), \quad (3.10)$$

$$2mH = \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c} \Psi(r, z) \right)^2, \quad (3.11)$$

then the orbit will be optimum. Eq. (3.9), Eq. (3.10), and Eq. (3.11), simply imply that $P_r = 0$, $P_z = 0$, $\dot{P}_r = 0$, and $\dot{P}_z = 0$. Therefore the orbit is executing simple rotation about the z -axis. Now If P_θ were slightly different, the orbit would acquire some slight motion in r and then z . The total orbit will be close to the previous rotation in θ with be small amplitude oscillations in r and z superimposed. These are the classic betatron oscillations.[43] The frequency and peak amplitude of these oscillations will depend both on the difference of H and P_θ from their optimum values and on the exact spatial dependence of Ψ in the neighborhood of (r, z) . In FRC's these large orbits are near a region in space of an absolute magnetic field null, the O-point. Therefore, analysis in terms of small departure from the optimum orbit is often invalid. Finite

amplitude corrections quickly become important. Nonlinear corrections to linear terms are often important. For instance, if the radial betatron excursions distance is as large as the distance to the O-point field null, then the orbit is not well approximated by a linear betatron orbit, but must be solved nonlinearly. In that situation the types of possible large orbits quickly multiply into a rich morphology spanning from optimum orbits to betatron orbits, then to figure eights with forward or retro-grade or even zero net drift. Finally at lower energies, the drift motion limit is recovered. There is also motion in the axial direction, and in the large amplitude limit, the (r, z) dependence of $\Psi(r, z)$ couples the radial and axial excursions. The general orbit characteristics depends on both the constants of motion, H and P_θ , and on the specific spatial dependence of Ψ . [43, 1].

Since there are more degrees of freedom than constants of motion, the motion may be non-integrable. Previous simulations have tended to confirm that hypothesis. [49] In that case, the orbit might be assumed to fill all regions of phase space that are dynamically allowed. This is a useful approximation that is commonly assumed in analytical calculations. [49] Given $\Psi(r, z)$ we can construct a spatial function using H and P_θ as parameters,

$$A(H, P_\theta, r, z) \equiv H - \frac{1}{mr^2} \left(P_\theta - \frac{e}{c} \Psi(r, z) \right)^2. \quad (3.12)$$

Then a particle with energy, H , and canonical angular momentum, P_θ , can exist in any region of real space where $A > 0$. However, no orbit with these values of H and P_θ exists in those regions where $A < 0$. The physical meaning of A is clear when one examines Eq. (3.6). [72] A is simply that portion of the Hamiltonian connected with the sum of the squares of the momentum in the r

and z motion. Since this sum must be positive, the particle's orbit cannot take it to regions of space where $A < 0$. For a given P_θ and $\Psi(r, z)$ increasing A will increase the real-space volume accessible to the particle. That is, if $V(H)$ is defined as the subset of R^3 that is the dynamically allowable volume for a particle orbit of energy H , canonical angular momentum, P_θ , in a magnetic field configuration given by Ψ , then $S(H_1) \subset S(H_2)$ if $H_1 < H_2$. For very low values of H , A will be < 0 everywhere, meaning no orbits with those values of H and P_θ exist for the configuration given by Ψ . For larger values of H the dynamically realizable volume begins as a point and expands to fill larger and larger portions of the FRC volume. The other feature to note is that the choice of P_θ serves to choose the value of Ψ to which the orbits remain close. If H is only slightly above its minimum value of $(P_\theta - e/c\Psi)^2/(2mr^2)$ the orbits will remain close to Ψ contour with a value of cP_θ/e . As H increases above this minimum, there is more freedom of motion in the r and z direction that allow the orbit to sample a larger spatial volume.

3.3 Possible Beam Sources

There are three widely discussed sources for high energy beams. The first is the FRC formation itself. Most formation schemes involve some early period of rapid pinch-like compression. If a beam is created some time before compression, it will be adiabatically compressed. During compression, the beam will gain energy. This can be understood by looking at the angular momentum of the beam. If radial compression conserves angular momentum, compression to a smaller radius implies an increase in beam kinetic energy which scales as the square of the compression ratio, $E_f/E_i = (r_i/r_f)^2$. Since beam energy is

multiplied under compression, the original beam can be of low energy. Thus the initial seed beam quite possibly could be the result of a portion of a thermal distribution that is selected for acceleration under compression. This possibility has been previously noted.[47]

A second beam source is the preferential trapping of fusion products in an ignited advanced fuel reactor.[49] With advanced D-³He fuel the fusion products are an alpha particle and a proton. Therefore all products are charged and have orbits dictated by the electric and magnetic fields. At the point of fusion, the energetic proton will be created with a kinetic energy near 14 MeV. However, since the fusion reaction is a sub-Coulomb barrier penetration reaction, the direction of the velocity is random. Therefore the direction of the product proton's velocity will be approximately random. However, the magnetic field will capture some protons in closed orbits that do not intersect the walls or end regions. Other protons will not be trapped. Given a direction of the magnetic field, it is found that the protons that are trapped will carry angular momentum of one sign, while the angular momentum of the lost protons will carry another sign. Thus D-³He fusion in an FRC will naturally create high energy beams from the fusion products. The available current and energy are of the same order of magnitude as that required to sustain fusion burning.[49]

Between formation and burning, there does not yet appear to exist a spontaneous beam generation mechanism. Therefore, a third source of beam particles is sought. These are externally supplied beams.[18] Since the tilt mode should grow to total disruption in a few Alfvén transit times. The external beams need to be injected very rapidly. This implies that a high current short pulse beam injector is needed,[73] at least initially, in order to inject

enough energetic beam quickly enough to prevent tilting. The required current out of the beams is well beyond present day neutral beam injection devices. However, for current generation sized FRC's, there appears to be a window of opportunity. Very fast ion diodes can be used.[73] The energy may still be low enough[48, 73] to allow moderate neutralizer efficiencies for positive ion neutral beam technologies.[74] At later times the energy of the beam may need to be quasi-statically increased, but this may be possible with higher energy neutral beams using negative ion technology since the required current will be lower.[18] The point is that injected neutral beam stabilization will require an initial very high short pulse to rapidly establish the beam. For current generation experiments, these initial pulse might consists of several modules, each of which could fired 50 mC (3×10^{17} particles) of neutral beam current is 5 μ sec.[73] The later beam current requirements are lower. At that point only enough beam is needed to replace the collision and fluctuation induced beam losses.

One should be careful when talking about beam current to clarify between two usages. One meaning is the current inside the torus which is due to beam motion, as stated in Eq. (2.45). The other meaning is common terminology used in the technology of neutral beam injection and ion plasma diodes. In that sense the beam current is a measure of the number of particles per second ejected from the gun. If singly charged particles were ejected at the same rate, the gun would emit a current of a specific amount. This amount is called the beam current in this context. This is a physically reasonable term since most neutral beam techniques began by generating directed flow of charged particles and then pass this charged beam through a neutralizing medium of some sort

where some fraction of the beam particles lose their net charge becoming a well collimated neutral beam. Where the context is not clear, I will distinguish between the two usages of the term "beam current" by using the term "beam current out of the gun" or "gun current" to describe the number of particles per second ejected from the gun and using the term "beam current in the plasma" to describe the trapped current encircling the symmetry axis. There is a direct relationship between these two beam currents. The amount of beam that is trapped in the plasma will be a function of the total amount of neutral beam that has been injected from the neutral beam guns. It is analogous to the relationship of a lake with its tributary. The description and numerical evaluation of this relationship will form a large part of the work described in § (3.5)-§ (3.8).

When a beam is generated from one of the three mentioned methods, it can be characterized in many different ways. The description used will discuss the distribution of the beam in an (H, P_θ) phase space. Even if the total number of beam particles is identical, two different beam distribution functions can have very different effects on the dynamical behavior of an FRC. The most important effect is the beam current density inside the plasma, $\mathbf{J}_b$, since this is the major effect that enters into the plasma dynamical equations, Eq. (2.126)-Eq. (2.131). The magnitude and spatial shape of $\mathbf{J}_b$ will depend on the details of the beam distribution function in phase space. For instance, given that $f_b(H, P_\theta)$ is non-zero in a finite region of (H, P_θ) space then $\mathbf{J}_b(r, z)$ will be zero outside of a given region in (r, z) that corresponds to the forbidden regions of all possible orbits. That is $\mathbf{J}_b(r, z) = 0$ for the set of (r, z) which is the intersection of all of the complements of the dynamical accessible regions of space for all values

of (H, P_θ) for which $f_b(H, P_\theta) \neq 0$. This is simply one example. Of course the exact nature of $J_b(r, z)$ is computable from f_b from its definition, Eq. (2.45). However, the velocity space integration must now be transformed into the new velocity space variables.[75]

Finally, the particular form of $f_b(H, P_\theta)$ is a consequence of the origin of the beam. If it arises from preferential trapping of fusion products, it will have a given dependence.[49] If it is of spontaneous origin during formation it may have quite a different distribution. If the beam is injected from the exterior during formation, compression, heating of burning phases, the form of $f_b(H, P_\theta)$ will be determined by the instantaneous (or recent historical) values of Ψ and the parameters that describe the energy and trajectory of the injected particles. This is true whether the injection scheme consists of neutralized output of an ion diode,[73] or a higher energy negative ion type neutral beam.[18] One could even consider an ionized, charge neutral dense beam penetration.[76, 77, 78]

In this chapter the dependence of $f_b(H, P_\theta)$ and $J_b(r, z)$ upon parameters of a ion-diode type neutral beam gun is studied. I will also investigate the stabilizing features of beams of such origin.

3.4 Previous Beam Stabilization Studies

Before describing specific modelling details of neutral beam injector, it is appropriate to explore the physical mechanism that allows an axis encircling beam to stabilize tilt mode activity. There are a couple of intuitive mechanisms which work together to provide stability. First it is useful to discuss the mechanism for tilt instability. The best intuition is provided when looking at the external tilt mode. Given a particular plasma configuration, and magnetic field in equi-

librium consider the effect of a perturbation of the type where the plasma is rigidly rotated about an axis perpendicular to the symmetry axis. By a simple change of coordinates, this is the same as the external field being slightly rotated in the opposite direction. In this case the perturbation analysis shows that the interaction of the perturbed field with the unperturbed current leads to a $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force that acts to accentuate the perturbation.[46] For the internal mode however, the perturbation is restricted to lie completely within the separatrix. In this case the destabilizing $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force still exists. However now it must compete with stabilizing magnetic compression terms.[30] Beyond some critical separatrix elongation the destabilizing term dominates. Therefore highly elongated FRC's will be unstable (in an ideal MHD analysis).

This suggests a first mechanism for beam stabilization. The beam current in the torus acts as a substitute for the plasma current. Thus it modifies the destabilizing $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ force. This can be made apparent by substituting Eq. (2.131) into Eq. (2.128) to obtain,

$$m_i n \frac{dV}{dt} = -\nabla P - \nabla \cdot \vec{\Pi} + \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_{tot} \times \mathbf{B} - \frac{1}{c} \mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B} - \mathbf{R}_{be}, \quad (3.13)$$

where $\mathbf{J}_{tot}$ is the total current defined as,

$$\mathbf{J}_{tot} \equiv \frac{4\pi}{c} \nabla \times \mathbf{B}. \quad (3.14)$$

Eq. (3.13) then implies that if the structure of the magnetic field is held constant then the addition of beam current in the torus gives an effective force that acts in the direction opposite the $\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}$ destabilizing force that would be present without the beam. Another way to state this is that $\mathbf{J}_p \times \tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ drives the instability where $\tilde{\mathbf{B}}$ is the perturbed magnetic field. If the shape of the

equilibrium magnetic field is held constant, then the magnitude of J_p will be decreased as J_b is increased. However, this mechanism alone will not stabilize the tilt mode unless J_b is so large as to reverse the sign of J_p .

However, there are other responses that also affect the tilt mode. The most prominent is that J_b itself will respond to perturbations in the magnetic field. Since the beam particles are very energetic, they may completely encircle the symmetry axis on a time scale consistent with a fluid perturbation. For rigid external tilting it has been shown that the response of the beam particle may give a perturbed force that acts to stabilize tilt-like perturbations.[46] However this result depends on a resonance effect between the period of axial betatron oscillation and the period of the axis encircling motion. When this ratio is slightly higher than unity the beam gives a large stabilizing force. If the ratio is less than unity then the beam acts to reinforce the instability. If the ratio is much greater than 1 then the beam gives a stabilizing force but of smaller magnitude. A variational fluid analysis that treats the beam as a second fluid gives a similar result.[79] The beam can stabilize the mode only for a narrow slice in parameter space. The width of the slice enlarges as the total beam current increases.

This effect has also previously been explored in a test particle simulations that are direct antecedents of the work presented here.[47] In that case a particular equilibrium was chosen. The beam characteristics were designed so that the axis encircling orbits were contained within the separatrix and outside of the field null. These conditions served to determined the ratio of the axial betatron period and the axis encircling period to a value larger than unity, on the order of 2 to 3. They then calculated the minimum total beam

inventory required for the perturbed $\mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B}$ force to exceed the destabilizing perturbed $\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ term. In this instance, the total beam inventory is a measure of the total beam located inside the plasma since the beam loading conditions specify the average current per beam particle. Later simulations in the same work[47] also allowed the plasma to evolve self-consistently in a manner similar to Eq. (2.126)-Eq. (2.133)

The above analyses have assumed that the introduction of a beam into the system will not perturb the magnetic field structure. Another way to look at the introduction of a beam into an FRC is that the plasma current remains unperturbed and the magnetic field structure adjusts in response to the beam. In this view the beam becomes a interpenetrating current carrier inside the FRC. If the beam is strong enough it may change the field line curvature as seen by the rest of the plasma. This would help stabilization of the tilt mode as well as other plasma modes such as interchange modes.[80] Additionally, the introduction of a beam will also change the shape of the plasma separatrix. A great deal of theoretical work has used the plasma separatrix shape as the identifiable stability parameter. It is not that the shape itself governs stability. Rather, the separatrix shape may be a consequence of underlying equilibrium and dynamical forces required for a FRC to be successfully formed and quiescent. The beam has the potential to change unstable configurations into stable ones. A previous simulation[47] has noted that the introduction of a beam into a background plasma that is allowed to evolve does lead to a change in the shape of the flux surfaces. The beam tends to concentrate in a ring in the midplane between the field null and the separatrix. The flux contours evolve to accommodate a large localized current in that area. The separatrix shape

then bulges outward at the midplane in a fashion that is reminiscent of the “problimak” shape.[29] The previous self-consistent simulations[47] could not distinguish between the effects of the modification of the magnetic field structure or the perturbed forces from the beam current. However, they could make crude estimates by noticing how the magnetic field structure changed with the introduction of the beam and by comparing the stability limits with previous non-self-consistent calculations.[47] Whether the principal effect of the beam is to replace plasma current or to modify the magnetic field structure depends crucially on the particular form of $f_b(H, P_\theta)$. The details of this relationship are only just beginning to be explored. The rest of the chapter will discuss some of the issues involved, but a comprehensive picture is lacking since there are so many diverse effects that come together to specify the beam distribution.

The focus of this chapter is on the interaction of the beam current, the magnetic field structure and the background plasma motion through the beam force term. To that extent, the friction force effects arising from the $\mathbf{R}_{be}$ term are ignored in this chapter. In terms of the discussion in § (2.9), this means that there will be no Ohkawa current, and no toroidal spin-up in this formulation.

It should be noted that this modelling assumes that there is no high frequency, direct, beam-field interaction. The electromagnetic fields are only considered to have variations on MHD time scales and not on the faster particle times scales. This assumption may not be valid for many of the cases described below.[81] The extension of the numerical model to include such effects would require a very large increase in computational requirements and is not considered in this work.

3.5 Realistic Neutral Beam Parameterization

3.5.1 Orbit Characterization

Two issues together imply that there is a need for more detailed modelling of injected neutral beams in an FRC. The first is that current generation or larger machines are very likely to have observable tilt activity[34] which will limit stability of confinement in FRC's. The second is that injected neutral beam can stabilize this mode.[47] Previous beam stabilization analyses have been rather limited by special assumptions such as single particle response[46] or a fluid characterization of the beam.[79] Previous hybrid fluid-particle simulations provide the most detailed modelling.[47]

However, previous studies an assumed beam generation scheme was used. The choice seems to be guided by a desire to consider energetic particles which, will intuitively contribute the greatest toward tilt stabilization, even though the assumed orbits are not ideal in the sense that they are perfect circular orbits. Orbits can be characterized by their values of H and P_θ . Equivalently, the orbit can be characterized by the value of all components of the velocity, v_r, v_θ, v_z , at a particular instant in time and at a particular point in space. The orbits of interest will be confined to within a finite distance of the midplane (axial confinement) and less than a certain radius (radial confinement).[72] Another orbit characteristic is "axis encircling" meaning that the winding number about the z -axis (symmetry axis) increases secularly in time. A sufficient (but not necessary) condition for an orbit to be axis encircling is that the sign of v_θ doesn't change. Most confined, axis-encircling particles will be confined to lie between the field null and the separatrix, although there will exist some particles with portions of their orbits inside the

field null or outside of the separatrix. A critical velocity in the theta direction can be derived[47]. $v_{\theta c}$ is defined by requiring an orbit to have a minimum radius of r_N , the field null, and a maximum radius of r_s , the separatrix radius at the midplane. Additionally, require that the orbit have no energy contained in axial motion. $v_{\theta}(r_N) = v_{\theta}(r_s)$ since $v_r = 0$ at the turning points and $v_z = 0$ by assumption and the fact that the motion conserves H . The equating the value of $P_{\theta} = mrv_{\theta} - e\Psi/c$ at these two points allows a unique solution for v_{θ} , of

$$v_{\theta c} \equiv \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}-1} \frac{e\Psi_0}{mcr_N}, \quad (3.15)$$

where Ψ_0 is the trapped flux, $\Psi(r_N, 0)$. This relation has made use of the general relation that $r_s = r_N\sqrt{2}$. [1] Therefore, $v_{\theta c}$ is a condition that determines whether an orbit is radially confined to be within the separatrix.

The previous calculation assumed there was no axial motion. However, the derivation is still valid even when axial motion is superimposed because FRC equilibria of experimental interest are convex. That is, for a given contour of constant $\Psi(r, z)$ a function, $r(z)$ can be defined. On the open field lines, there is a single branch of $r(z)$. For closed field lines there are two branches, one for small radius, $r < r_N$ and one for large radius, $r > r_N$. since the equilibria are convex, then $r(z)$ is a maximum at $z = 0$ for the open field line contours and the large r contours.

Axial confinement can be approximately determined by defining a critical axial velocity of[47, 72]

$$v_{zc} \equiv \sqrt{-P_{\theta} (2eB_0/m^2c) - v_{\theta t}^2}, \quad (3.16)$$

where B_0 is the maximum field strength in the throat of the mirror field. Note

that v_{zc} depends on $v_{\theta t}$, the velocity in the theta direction at the radial turning point. For a critical orbit, $v_{\theta t} = v_{\theta c}$. For an orbit that is more deeply confined, $v_{\theta t}$ may be less.

The particular beam loading scheme used in previous hybrid fluid-beam simulations was to have beam particles born at a point of space inside the separatrix within a certain range of r and z values. The initial velocities are specified as $v_{r_i} = 0$. v_{θ_i} and v_{z_i} are chosen as a given fractions of $v_{\theta c}$ and v_{zc} respectively. This choice tended to create beam particles whose orbits were precisely those that could test the previous speculations about beam stabilization. The choice was by no means capricious, but neither did it relate the simulated beam to a physical beam generation mechanism such as a neutral beam gun or spontaneous beam generation from inductive acceleration of the high energy ion tail during compression. These simulations allowed some exploration of different beam characteristics by varying the spatial region of beam origin or the initial azimuthal and axial velocities. However, this is only a small subset of possible beam configurations.

3.5.2 Beam Dynamical Behavior

Quite interestingly, these simulations found that the energetic beam could suppress tilt activity for certain beam parameters. Also interesting were the cases where energetic beams were not capable of stabilization. As was expected, if the beam were too small in the sense that there was not enough beam current, then stabilization was not possible. However, for some situations it appeared that enough bulk beam existed stability was still not found.[47] A few tentative explanations were given. One was that for beams with large axial motion, the

axial turning points were actually beyond the end of the separatrix. Therefore the beam current restoring force was concentrated on the field lines outside of the separatrix and therefore not as effective. For beams with very small axial motion, the beam tended to concentrate in the midplane. This high concentration of beam acted as an effective pressure and evacuated the plasma locally. This led to a local plasma pressure minimum and reversal of J_p . This had a couple of curious effects. First the induced plasma motion set up an electric field from $\mathbf{V}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ motion that acts to extract energy from the beam. This loss of beam energy then reduces the beam's ability to stabilize tilt perturbations. Secondly, the reversal of plasma current led to resistive flux generation. Since the current was reversed, the effect of resistivity was to create magnetic flux instead of annihilate it. The physical relevance of this mechanism for the simulations presented were suspect since the resistivity was artificially increased in order to semi-empirically model observed anomalous resistivity effects. Thus the flux generation was anomalously large. Additionally, the assumption that $\delta = n_b/n_i \ll 1$ is violated locally. Nevertheless the idea that a large local beam current near the field null may act as a current drive not only through normal energetic beam effects[62] but also by virtue of reversing the plasma current is a novel idea that is worthy of exploration.

The fact that the beam could stabilize the tilt activity, but that there exist regimes where the beam effect was qualitatively different emphasizes that it is important to model the beam realistically. The previous simulations demonstrated it is possible to stabilize tilt activity with energetic beams, but it did not address the question whether such beams can be deliberately produced in experimental devices. Another point of view is that the "beam in an FRC"

problem has a very rich behavior in terms of its natural control parameters. A study of the beam effect is very difficult analytically and computationally an exploration of a large dimensionality parameter-space is also computationally difficult.

3.5.3 Beam Parameterization

These issues then form the motivation for the study presented in this chapter. The goal is to continue the work of simulating energetic beam stabilization of tilt activity for differing types of beams. It is impossible to exhaustively examine parameter space. The question then becomes one of determining a rationale of which portions of parameter space will be simulated.

Here a very simple viewpoint is taken. Only beams that are a likely result of the physically relevant methods of beam generation are considered. Specifically, the previous beam simulation is modified to initialize the beam particles as neutral particles near the chamber walls. These particles will execute free motion. During this motion they will undergo a Monte-Carlo ionization process. If the particle is ionized then its charge is changed and it then propagates as an ordinary charged particle. As a result, the energetic beam will inherit its characteristics such a distribution function, total normalization, beam current, etc. from the characteristics of the beam gun that created it.

In this fashion the large parameter space of all possible beam distribution functions is reduced to a parameter space of variables associated with the placement and characterization of the one or more neutral beam guns that is the energetic beam source. This work will use two different but complementary numerical simulation techniques. The first is a simple integration tool

that will determine the point of ionization of neutral particles from a given set of beam guns. This tool is named “NBC” as an acronym for “Neutral Beam Capture”. The second is a self-consistent simulation that model the dynamical equations derived in Ch. (2), Eq. (2.126)-Eq. (2.143) with the exception that drag collisions are ignored. This simulation code is an outgrowth of the “Modified FLX Algorithm” used in previous beam simulations.[47] In turn, the fluid portion of the simulation is derived from the FLX algorithm.[82, 32] Here the code is modified to include realistic beam injection from a neutral beam gun and Monte-Carlo ionization of the neutral. Therefore, the acronym, “NBF”, is used to describe this simulation technique. These algorithms will be discussed in more detail below.

Now let us characterize those parameters that will serve to determine the launching of the neutral particles, and therefore will also serve to govern the resulting profile of captured beam. The first set of parameters are simple geometrical factors describing the shape of the target plasma, the aim of the guns and the size and divergence of the beam particles. Fig. (3.1) shows an end view of the FRC. This is the $r - \theta$ plane. The axes are the x and y axis. The separatrix is shown as a circle. The beam is shown as entering from the upper left and proceeding toward the lower right. The parameter, A_{impact} is defined as the distance of closest approach of the beam to the symmetry axis ($r = 0$ axis).

Fig. (3.2) shows a side view of an FRC with parameters labeled. The vertical axis is radius, r . The horizontal axis is z . The separatrix is drawn as an elliptical shape. The beam enters from the upper right and moves to the lower left. The $z = 0$ plane is also called the midplane. B_{impact} is the

distance of the beam from the midplane at the point of closest approach. That is $z = B_{\text{impact}}$ when $r = A_{\text{impact}}$. The angle φ is the acute angle formed by the intersection of the $r - z$ projection of the beam and the midplane, as shown. The beam itself is modeled with a finite thickness and divergence angle. Fig. (3.3) illustrates this configuration. R_{beam} is the radius of the beam. The beam is modeled as a Gaussian intensity with R_{beam} being the distance from the center of beam where the intensity has dropped to $1/e$ of its maximum. ϵ is the half-angle of the beam divergence. These beam characteristics are specified at a specific radius in the FRC. This is explicitly marked in Fig. (3.2) as R_{bref} . Characterizing the beam as a given width and divergence is a slight idealization. For instance it implies that the beam converges to a point in a finite upstream distance. The actual beam will not behave as such. What this implies is that the simulation will assume a very structured relationship of the transverse beam momentum. Specifically, the transverse momentum is a linear function of the distance from the beam center. In a real system, there will be a distribution of transverse momentum at each point in beam radius. The exact characterization of this distribution is unknown at this time. It is heavily dependent on the particular beam source module. Since data from prototype modules are not yet measured, it seems justified to use this simplification. If it is required, more sophisticated modelling could easily be included in later studies.

Figure 3.1: Beam Trajectory, End View.

Figure 3.2: Beam Trajectory, Side View.

Finally, it should be noted that there exists another parameter which has not been mentioned. It is the angle between the y -axis and $r - \theta$ projection of the beam path. Since the equilibrium is axi-symmetric, this angle is assumed to be 90° without loss of generality. There is an additional small point. Multiple independently targeted beam guns are used. Theoretically, these guns could inject beams at different θ angles in the plasma chamber. In fact experimental space considerations will probably require this. However, the energetic particles will orbit in θ . Thus any asymmetry of beam placement will be washed out by the particle orbits if the pulse time of the beam gun is longer than the time required for the captured beam to circulate about the axis. For the cases studied this was the case, and it would seem to hold for all cases that would seem to be of physical interest. Actually, this parameter could be included, but it does not appear to affect the results.

In Fig. (3.1) and Fig. (3.2) the beam has been shown as a single line. For the finite width beam, this line corresponds to the central bright spot of the beam, where it is understood that the entire beam is centered around this line. These parameters (A_{impact} , B_{impact} , φ , R_{bref} , R_{beam} , and ϵ) determine the geometrical characteristics of the beams. Now the parameters that characterize the beam itself need to be specified. There are two such parameters; E_{beam} , the energy of the particles in the beam and A_{beam} the atomic mass number of beam particles. In these simulations every particle of the beam has the same value for A_{beam} and E_{beam} . Again this is an idealization of the beam source, but it does not appear to lead to significant modelling errors.

The simulations will also allow for multiple beam guns that can be placed at different places axially and aimed independently. Therefore, the

Figure 3.3: Beam Shape.

above set of parameters are allowed to vary from gun to gun. Additionally, each gun is given a specified pulse time, t_{pulse} , and total particle emission inventory, N_{beam} . That is N_{beam} neutral particles of energy E_{beam} are fired from the gun in a time t_{pulse} . It is experimental traditional to state N_{beam} in Coulombs. This tradition will be continued here. If $N_{\text{beam}} = 1$ Coulomb it would imply that 6.24×10^{18} particles are fired from the gun.

3.6 Beam Ionization and Penetration

The specification of the beam parameters gives the initial state of the beam particles. Initially the particles are neutral (zero charge). The next issue is to accurately model the transformation of the of neutral particles to charged particles. Ionization occurs when the neutral particles collide with other particles in the chamber. The three most important reactions are; charge exchange, electron impact ionization, and ion impact ionization. The contribution from collisions with other neutrals or molecular species are negligible since the density of scatterers is slow low. The cross sections of the three principal reactions depend upon beam parameters, electron temperature (T_e), and electron density ($n_e = n$). The cross sections are semi-empirically given by,[74, 83]

$$\sigma_{ec} = \frac{0.6937 \times 10^{-14} \left[1 - 0.155 \log_{10} \left(E_{\text{beam}}/A_{\text{beam}} \right) \right]^2}{1 + 0.112 \times 10^{-14} \left(E_{\text{beam}}/A_{\text{beam}} \right)^{3.3}}, \quad (3.17)$$

for charge-exchange reactions and

$$\begin{aligned} \log_{10}(\sigma_{ii}) = & -0.8712 \left[\log_{10} \left(E_{\text{beam}}/A_{\text{beam}} \right) \right]^2 + \\ & 8.156 \log_{10} \left(E_{\text{beam}}/A_{\text{beam}} \right) - 34.833, \end{aligned} \quad (3.18)$$

for ion-impact reactions and

$$\sigma_{ie} = 2.0 \times 10^{-14} \sqrt{\frac{A_{\text{beam}} T_e}{E_{\text{beam}}}} \frac{u}{1+u} \left\{ \frac{1}{20+u} + \log_{10} \left[1.25 \left(1 + \frac{1}{u} \right) \right] \right\}, \quad (3.19)$$

for electron-impact reactions where,

$$u \equiv \frac{13.6}{T_e}, \quad (3.20)$$

and T_e , E_{beam} , and A_{beam} are expressed in electron volts, Ev, and the cross sections are in cm^2 . Strictly speaking, these expressions are only valid up to beam energies of ~ 100 KeV. The expression for σ_{ie} assumes that the electron thermal velocity is larger than the beam velocity. These limits of validity are only marginally obeyed, or even exceeded below. Nevertheless they are still used in the absence of more accurate expressions. While this limits the ultimate accuracy of the modelling, these expressions are a better approximation than approximating the cross-sections as independent of energy and electron temperature as is usually done.

The attenuation factor is defined as an inverse length that gives the probability per unit path length that a neutral particle will be ionized. The attenuation factor from each reaction is simply the cross-section for the reaction multiplied by the density of scatterers. The total attenuation factor is the sum of the attenuation factors from all processes,

$$\lambda_0^{-1} = n_e \sigma_{ie} + n_i \sigma_{ii} + n_i \sigma_{ec} = n_e (\sigma_{tot}), \quad (3.21)$$

where use is made of the fact that $n_e \approx n_i$ and defined the total equivalent cross-section as,

$$\sigma_{tot} \equiv \sigma_{ie} + \sigma_{ii} + \sigma_{ec}. \quad (3.22)$$

There is one final correction to add. The injected neutral particles have just passed through a gas neutralizer before they emerged out of the beam gun. This is a very short time after these particles have themselves captured an electron. Therefore there is a significant probability that the particles will not be in a ground state. If the electron is in a higher orbital, then the effective reaction cross sections will be larger due to the larger size of the electron wavefunction. The complete description of such an effect is quite complex.[74] Here use the common approximation that,

$$\lambda \equiv (1 + \gamma)\lambda_0. \quad (3.23)$$

γ is the penetration correction factor. For these simulations $\gamma = 1/5$.

Thus the local penetration depth along the neutral particle's path, $\lambda(s)$ can be calculated as a function of E_{beam} , A_{beam} , T_e and n (where s is the path length parameterization). The attenuation of the beam can then simply be expressed as,

$$\frac{dI(s)}{ds} = -\frac{I(s)}{\lambda(s)}, \quad (3.24)$$

where $I(s)$ is the local beam intensity. The NBC simulation tool integrates this beam intensity equation directly across the FRC geometry. The value of $\frac{\partial I(s)}{\partial s}$ is the local source of energetic beam.

In the NBF simulations, the particles are treated by the particle-in-cell algorithm.[84, 85] In that case the particles are initialized with zero charge. At each time step, the particle computes the ratio of the distance the particle traveled in the last time-step with the local (centered) value of $\lambda(s)$. It then compares that value with a randomly generated number between 0 and 1. If the value of the random number is less than the ratio, the particle is assumed

to have ionized. At that point the particle's charge is changed from 0 to 1. Subsequently, the particle will execute normal charged particle motion in the FRC.

Thus the history of a simulation particle is that it is born far away from the plasma as a neutral particle. It then propagates along the beam path. At some point it is ionized and then executes charged particle motion. The final destiny of the particle depends on the plasma density, beam energy and how the gun was aimed. The particle could pass from one side of the chamber to the other unionized. This particle is then said to "shine through" the plasma. The particle could ionize very early or very late in its path so that its point of ionization is outside of the separatrix. These particles are said to be "exterior ionized" particles. The third possibility is that the particle could be ionized within the separatrix. These particles are said to be "deposited". The term deposited, however, may be misleading. Particles which are ionized inside the separatrix are not guaranteed to remain confined in the FRC. Their orbits may intersect the radial wall or the end walls. Such particles are not confined, or sometimes said to be in "escape" orbits. As might be guessed, if the particle energy is too high or the trapping parameters are otherwise far off from the optimum values, escape orbits are much more likely.

3.7 Efficiency of Neutral Beam Injection

The principal question to address in this section is to characterize the energetic trapped beam in the FRC as a function of the neutral beam gun parameters. Of particular importance will be an estimate of the efficiency of the beam capture scheme. Previous simulations gave conclusions about what size and type of

embedded beam are required in order to stabilize the tilt mode. This allows a rough estimate of the total number of energetic particles N_b and the energy E_{beam} , that is required. Realistically, there are efficiency issues. Not all of the beam particles will be trapped. Also some that are trapped in orbits that contribute little to the current. Estimates of the required beam gun current should be multiplied by an efficiency factor between 0 and 1.

3.7.1 Simple Estimate of Required Beam Strength

Tilt mode stabilization will require a minimum amount of total beam current in the plasma, I_b . [47] Also estimates of current drive requirements are stated in terms of I_b . Of course there are other issues such as the distribution of the current for optimum tilt stabilization and return current issues for current drive. I_b can be related to N_b , the total inventory of particles ejected from all beams combined, $N_b = \sum_{\text{guns}} N_{\text{beam}}$. The total beam current is formally defined as,

$$I_b \equiv \int dA J_{\theta b}, \quad (3.25)$$

where dA indicates integration over the poloidal plane. A very simple estimate can be made of the relationship between I_b and N_b by simply multiplying N_b by an estimate of the total time for a typical orbit to circle the axis,

$$I_b = N_b f_{\Omega}, \quad (3.26)$$

where f_{Ω} is the cyclotron frequency of the beam measured in Hertz. For purposes of this estimate, the gyrofrequency of the large orbit particles is computed using the external magnetic field (field at the chamber wall). While it might be a better estimate to try to use some measure of the internal field, such estimates

are not simple and will change with differing equilibria, while the field at the wall is usually fixed. The purpose of Eq. (3.26) is not detailed accuracy, but it forms a first estimate connecting I_b with N_b . Simulation results described below are undertaken to estimate the necessary corrections. Eq. (3.26) simply assumes that every particle is trapped in an orbit that takes it around the torus in as short a time as possible. Thus Eq. (3.26) is an overestimate of the actual current. It is not possible for I_b to be larger, although non-ideal effects will make it smaller. Note this is another reason for using the magnetic field at the wall in the calculation of f_Ω . This insures that the actual f_Ω experienced by the beam is smaller since the magnetic field is usually a maximum at the chamber walls.

Several corrections to Eq. (3.26) can be guessed even before simulations begun. Five are listed here. Their effects are measured either alone and/or in combination by use of the simulations. The modest goal is to estimate these corrections to their first digit and exponent rather than 2 or 3 digit accuracy.

The first correction to consider is that Eq. (3.26) overestimates I_b because it assumes that all of the particles are ionized inside the plasma. In actuality some of the particles will shine through and some will ionize in the exterior. That is not all neutral particles will be deposited in the plasma

Secondly, even if the particle is deposited inside the plasma, it may be ionized with a value of P_θ that puts it on an escape orbit. This will also reduce I_b . The exact size of these corrections cannot be estimated beforehand. They will depend on the beam energy and the aiming direction of the beam gun.

A third correction is that the estimate for f_Ω is an overestimate. It should be revised downward by the average value of the magnetic field at the

particle's path as compared to the magnetic field at the wall. The optimum orbit could lie anywhere in the region for the field null to the separatrix. If the particle's orbit was circular and very near the field null, then f_{Ω} , in principal, could be as close to 0 as desired. In practice, this correction can be qualitatively estimated beforehand. The particles will need to be injected with a certain energy. If the energy is too low, the particle will not penetrate deep enough to reach the radius of its optimum orbit. Instead it will be ionized at a larger radius. If it is ionized at such a larger radius, then it will have a non-zero component of v_r at the ionization point. This will mean that the orbit will have some level of betatron motion. Moreover, if the low energy particle is ionized early, it will be ionized in a high magnetic field, since the magnitude of the magnetic field increases from field null to separatrix. Thus it will be impossible for a neutral beam gun to create a beam with lower energy that orbits in optimum orbits near the field null. Although it should be pointed out, that other beam creation mechanisms such as fusion product capture, and especially spontaneous beam generation may have a significant component that is deeply trapped near the field null since the physics of their origin has nothing to do with penetration issues. For the equilibrium used in this study (described below) it turns out that the particle energy is such that an optimum orbit for a particle with sufficient energy to penetrate to its optimum orbit radius implies that the actual field is about 2/3 to 3/4 of the value of the magnetic field at the wall. Of course this number is a rough number, since the particles ionize at different locations because of the Monte-Carlo ionization scheme. This average field seen by the energetic particles is actually higher than the volume averaged magnetic field.

A fourth correction to Eq. (3.26) is the realization that due to the random nature of the ionization not all particles will be in optimum orbits. In fact for poor beam gun aiming, none of the particles may be in optimum orbits. This will cause a decrease in I_b . This fact may be illustrated by considering two identical particles that are ionized at the same point in space with the same kinetic energy but the particles differ in their velocity directions at the point of ionization. Moreover, suppose that the point of ionization is at the radius that will give an optimum orbit for a particle of that kinetic energy when all of the kinetic energy is in θ directed motion. If the first particle is ionized with all of its kinetic energy in θ motion, then its integrated path length around the torus will be $2\pi r$. If the second particle is ionized with the same kinetic energy but at the point of ionization some of the energy is contained in radial motion, then this particle will exhibit radial betatron oscillations along its orbit. Therefore the total path length of the second particle around the torus will be longer than the first particle's path length. Since both particles have the same kinetic energy, and it is conserved during the motion, the second particle will take longer to complete its orbit (or strictly speaking to increase θ by 2π since the orbit may not be closed). I call this the "bumpy orbit" phenomenon. Particles with bumpy orbits take longer to circle the axis. It is not easy to estimate the impact of this effect beforehand. One must calculate how averages of orbits and how bumpy those orbits are.

There is a small note here. For some particles with very large radial betatron excursions, the total path length may be shorter because oscillations to small r can increase the angular rotation rate, $\omega \equiv v_\theta/r$. However these orbits are a small portion of the total orbits for the cases studied and in general

these orbits are not desirable because in addition to near axis motion, they will also extend into regions far beyond the separatrix. although for other fusion concepts, such as Migma[86] orbits of this variety are precisely the ones which are desired.

The fifth extension to the approximation of Eq. (3.26) is the fact that the fluid response to the beam's introduction may have a back reaction which modifies the characteristics of the beams. Such an effect was noted on previous simulations.[47] It seemed to have an important effect that could turn beams that would otherwise be sufficient for stabilization into insufficient beams.

The goal in this section is to get a more accurate estimate of the effects of the first 4 corrections. The next section, § (3.8), will discuss the 5th correction.

3.7.2 Equilibrium Characteristics

Simulations were conducted on a specific FRC equilibrium that has been used in previous tilt mode[32] and beam stabilization[47] studies. It is the output of a numerical equilibrium solver.[75] It is characterized as an approximately elliptical FRC with separatrix radius of 21.6 cm. The radius of the field null is 15.2 cm. The half-length is 79.8 cm. Fig. (3.4) shows the electron temperature at the ($z = 0$) midplane. The temperature is constant inside the separatrix. Fig. (3.5) shows the midplane plasma number density. It peaks at a value of $1.55 \times 10^{15}/\text{cm}^3$ at the O-point. It falls off both toward the separatrix and towards the symmetry axis. Since the temperature is constant inside the separatrix, the shape of the pressure profile is identical to the density profile inside the separatrix. Fig. (3.6) shows the magnitude of the midplane magnetic field as a function of radius. It has a peak value of 4.1 KGauss at the chamber

Figure 3.4: Equilibrium Electron Temperature Profile.

Figure 3.5: Equilibrium Density Profile.

Figure 3.6: Equilibrium Magnetic Field Profile.

walls. Inside the separatrix it decreases with decreasing r and finally crosses 0 at $r = r_{null}$. At $r = 0$ it has almost fully reversed to a value of -3.5 KGauss. Fig. (3.7) shows contours of constant flux, Ψ for a portion of the poloidal (r, z) plane. The region $z < 0$ is obtained by a mirror reflection at the midplane. The values of n and T_e are constant on the flux surface and can therefore be extrapolated from their midplane values (the (r, z) dependence of the magnetic field strength is more complex). It should be noted that the contours in Fig. (3.7) are not evenly spaced in Ψ . Since this is a numerical equilibrium, it is also important to note that the equilibrium is calculated from a finite difference formulation in z and cubic splines in r . This solution is then interpolated to a 40×100 grid in r and z for use in the penetration and dynamical simulation studies.

This particular equilibrium was computed in order to compare with conditions in the FRX-C/LSM experiment.[87, 34] This particular magnetic

Figure 3.7: Equilibrium Poloidal Flux Contours.

field implies that $f_{\Omega} \approx 6$ MHz in Eq. (3.26). The density of the FRC is quite large as compared to some other magnetic fusion energy concepts such as a tokamak. This is a consequence of the large β of FRC's. It implies that the neutral beam may have difficulty penetrating into the plasma. As seen below, this is indeed the case. Much of the beam will be ionized in the first few cm past the separatrix.

These parameters also allow a rough estimate of the required beam energy range for optimum orbits. Using the $B = 4.1$ KGauss value and the radii of the null and separatrix, the required beam energy is estimated to lie between, 187 KeV and 374 Kev. This is computed by finding the kinetic energy that will give a Larmor radius equal to the field-null and separatrix radius respectively. I have also assumed that the neutral beam is composed of atomic hydrogen. Since the actual magnetic field is somewhat lower, the actual beam energy will lie in the low end of this range. This discussion has now narrowed the set of parameters enough to begin simulational studies.

3.7.3 NBC Simulation Tool

The NBC code simulates the injection of one or more neutral beams into this equilibrium. Each beam is represented as a series of 64 beamlets. Each beamlet is actually just a geometrical line. The beamlets are arranged in 8 groups of 8 beamlets. Each group is at a different divergence angle in such a fashion that the total beam distribution is distributed according to a Gaussian profile that falls off with increasing distance from the central beamline. This divergence angle is selected according to a cumulant distribution method.[88] Within each group the 8 beamlets are equally spaced in the angular direction around the central beamline. The number 64 is chosen in order that the discrete beamlet representation of the beam is packed closely enough to accurately model a continuous beam. For these simulations I have taken a divergence angle of 5° and a radius of 2 cm at a beam reference radius of 35 cm. These parameters were chosen based on projected characteristics of beam guns that have been proposed.[73] Whether these are realistic parameters has not been fully explored. Since the beam is fairly tightly focused, it is found that 64 beamlets reduces the graininess of the beam modelling sufficiently.

The NBC algorithm then first determines all of the beamlet paths through the FRC chamber. Each beamlet is parameterized by its path length, s , along the direction of travel. Each beamlet is given a total initial intensity of $N_{\text{beam}}/64$. The intensity at every point along the path length is then computed by numerically integrating the beam intensity equation, Eq. (3.24), which becomes a simple ordinary differential equation with the path length as the independent variable. $\lambda(s)$ is computed according to Eq. (3.23) along the path using the beamlet geometry to determine the spatial coordinate parame-

terizations, $r(s)$ and $z(s)$. This gives $I(s)$ the beamlet intensity as a function path length. It also gives $dI(s)/ds$ which is the source of charged beam inside the chamber. These quantities can then be converted into spatial deposition profiles by utilizing the coordinate parameterizations for each beamlet and summing over all beamlets.

Intensity in this usage stands for the total number of particles. Since NBC is a non-interacting simulation, the intensity could be changed to number of particles/sec by simply dividing the results by the beam gun pulse time, t_{pulse} . Likewise the deposition would become the number of charged particles per second. The dimensional normalization is actually not important since the results from NBC will be compared to the total possible deposition. The ratio of two identically dimensioned quantities is simply a pure number.

The NBC algorithm forms a step in a ladder of analysis and simulation. It bridges the gap between analytic results and later NBF simulations. To that extent, NBC can be calibrated against analytically known results. Once confidence in NBC as a modelling tool is established, it can then be used as a yardstick to verify the accuracy of NBF. To this end, NBC was first applied to a series of test problems where analytic deposition profiles were calculable. Such cases included at first pencil beams, and later mildly diffuse beams which impacted on very special profiles such as a sharp plasma cylinder, or a plasma with linear or parabolic density profile. In all cases NBC performed within expected error limits. Actually, the sharp profile boundary formed a good test of the accuracy of the different differential integrators used since it contained a discontinuity in the density. While the error was larger for this case, it was still within the *a priori* error estimates from standard numerical analysis.

An additional post-processing feature was added to simulate the noise that should be expected from modelling the beams as discrete particles instead of beamlets. After the intensity equations had been integrated along each beamlet, a set of particles was then considered. The particles were divided among the beamlets in ratios that were equivalent to the ratios of the beamlets' intensities. The particle's ionization position was determined by picking a random number, g , between 0 and 1 and considering the particle to have ionized at the point, s , along the beamlet's path where its intensity had decreased such that $I(s)/I(0) = g$. If no such s exists, then the particle is assumed to have shone through to the other side of the chamber. After the particle's ionization position is determined, it is accumulated onto an interpolated grid. This allows a mock-up of the PIC algorithm that will be used later. Therefore, NBC can estimate the amount of error that is introduced from discrete particle shot noise. This noise should scale as $\sqrt{1/N}$ where N is the number of particles per grid cell. This relationship is shown to hold. For the tightly focused beams considered here, fluctuations from discrete particle ionization could be kept in the 5% range for a few thousand to ten thousand particles. It should be noted that reducing fluctuations on ionization positions and reducing fluctuations during subsequent particle motion are different since the subsequent orbit will take the particle to different parts of the FRC and different grid cells. So the natural statistical limiting factor that should determine the number of particles that are required for accurate modelling would be assumed to be the requirement to reduce noise during the subsequent motion. However, as will be discussed later, the use of subcycling will have an added side effect of improving the statistics during particle motion. Therefore, uniformity and

faithful reproduction of ionization profiles actually becomes the limiting factor that determines the minimum number of particles required in the simulation. Other issues such as uniformity and adequacy of velocity space information is avoided in this scheme. Since the particles are fired with a specific kinetic energy and in a specific direction, the particles position in velocity space is completely determined at ionization. Moreover, this corresponds to the physical situation for beam injection. NBC only gives the position of ionization. It cannot follow the orbit after that point. NBF will be used later to investigate the quality of the subsequent orbits. However, NBC results coupled with results from analytic orbit theory can give some guidance. This possibility is not considered further in this work. In hindsight, however, it maybe should have been. This point will be discussed some more below.

3.7.4 Ionization Profiles

For the equilibrium under consideration, NBC was used as a preliminary tool to try to optimize the targeting of the beam guns and the energy of the neutral beams. At this point there remains a 4-dimensional space of parameters to search for the optimum configuration. the 4 parameters are E_{beam} , A_{impact} , B_{impact} , and φ . The space has not been completely explored yet. This lack of complete exploration is not due to any inherent limitation. An intuitive guess for 2 of the parameters, B_{impact} and φ , are used and the beam placement is optimized for the other 2 parameters, A_{impact} and E_{beam} .

The effect of changing the value of φ can be estimated beforehand. If $\varphi = 0$ then the particle will have $v_z = 0$ when it is ionized. If $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$ also then the particle will remain in the midplane without any axial motion.

If $\varphi \neq 0$ but we still have $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$ then when the particle is ionized, it will have a non-zero axial velocity, $v_z = \sqrt{2E_{\text{beam}}/m} \sin(\varphi)$. The azimuthal velocity will be reduced since some the beam kinetic energy will be tied up in axial kinetic energy, $v_\theta = \sqrt{2E_{\text{beam}}/m} \cos(\varphi)$. Therefore the effect of a non-zero φ value is to initialize the beam particles with axial motion. Additionally, if the circulation time is to remain constant the beam energy will need to be increased in order to maintain a constant v_θ .

The effect of change B_{impact} can be similarly estimated. If we assume that $\varphi = 0$ then changing B_{impact} will also excite axial motion. Suppose a particle is ionized in the FRC with an initial $v_z = 0$ but away from the midplane. Inspection of Eq. (3.8) shows that unless the particle has a perfectly matched value of $P_\theta = e\Psi/c$ the $\dot{P}_z \sim \partial\Psi/\partial z$ will act to excite an axial velocity which moves the particle toward the midplane. In this sense an axial betatron oscillation is excited. Therefore a trade-off exists between the values for φ and B_{impact} . A particle ionized and finite B_{impact} and $\varphi = 0$ will have the same orbit as a particle ionized at finite φ and $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$. The only difference is that the phase of the axial betatron oscillation. There are limits to this relationship. φ can be used to give arbitrarily large axial velocity while B_{impact} cannot give axial motion that extends far beyond the separatrix. However, this is not an issue since interest is focused on particles that remain inside the separatrix in order to be most effective at stabilizing tilt activity.

The effective beam penetration distance before ionization is another consideration. For the equilibrium under study, and a beam energy, E_{beam} of 225 KeV, the total cross section is $\approx 6.4 \times 10^{-17} \text{cm}^2$. The peak plasma density (at the O-point) is $1.6 \times 10^{15} / \text{cm}^3$. This implies that the beam penetration

distance is about 15 cm. While we can expect a portion of the beam to penetrate further, most of the neutral beam will actually be ionized before the beam has penetrated that far into the FRC. It is actually a bit of a problem to get the neutral beam to penetrate sufficiently deep into the FRC. In this sense the FRC is very close to being over-dense for effective beam penetration, in the sense that a neutral particle with enough kinetic energy to penetrate a significant distance will be so energetic that when it is ionized, its orbit will not be confined. This is in contrast to neutral beam injection on other magnetic fusion experiments. There the plasma β is much lower. Lower β implies that the density is lower and the magnetic field larger. The FRX-C/LSM sized devices allow beam penetration. However, there is no reason to believe that such a relationship will be maintained in larger devices, or reactor designs. For the parameters of the Artemis design,[18] the beam penetration distance is ~ 270 cm but the separatrix radius is only 112 cm. This means that only 1/2 of the neutral beam power will be ionized inside the plasma, and even less will be ionized on usable orbits. This is an important issue to bear in mind during design decisions for new experiments.

The geometry of the beam path implies that increasing φ will also increase the path length required to penetrate in order to reach a given radius. This allows a distinction to be drawn between exciting axial motion by use of the B_{impact} parameter of the φ parameter. Use of φ will lead to ionization profiles that are closer to the separatrix than if the same motion was excited by use of the B_{impact} parameter. Since the optimum orbit beam energies are already marginal or too low for effective penetration, axial particle motion will be introduced by aiming the neutral beam guns at different axial distances

along the FRC instead of changing their angle of approach.

Previous simulations[47] showed that beam stabilization was most effective when the beam was spread over the entire volume inside the separatrix, I will attempt to place the beam guns to create such a distribution. I will use a configuration with several beam guns. Each gun is located at a different z value. Each gun will inject with $\varphi = 0$ in order to get the deepest penetration possible.

This leaves the determination of A_{impact} and E_{beam} for optimum beam capture. I will choose A_{impact} and E_{beam} to minimize the first correction to Eq. (3.26), the number of particles ionized outside of the separatrix. Simulations with the NBC algorithm were used. Several regions of this 2-dimensional parameter-space were explored for a single beam gun aimed in the midplane ($B_{\text{impact}} = 0$). Extrapolations to other values of B_{impact} are not difficult. Two separate 1-dimensional scans are presented in Fig. (3.8) and Fig. (3.9). Fig. (3.8) is a scan of the particle deposition percentage as a function of energy when the beam is aimed with $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm, just inside the field null. The beam is taken to have a profile radius of 2 cm and a divergence angle of 5° . This aim ensures that almost all of the beam passes inside the separatrix. NBC simulations are performed for energies from 50 KeV to 500 KeV. Deposition is defined to occur if the particle is ionized within the separatrix. The deposition percentage is over 80% for a very broad range of energies from 100 KeV to 400 KeV. The exterior ionized percentage is as large as 20% for low energy, but decreases as the E_{beam} increases. The percentage of the of shine through particles that are not ionized inside the the chamber is low for lower energies and increases to 10% at 500 KeV. These relationships are as expected

Figure 3.8: Ionization Percentages as a Function of Energy.

Figure 3.9: Ionization Percentages as a Function of A_{impact} .

since the electron impact (Eq. (3.19)) and charge exchange (Eq. (3.17)) cross sections decrease with increasing beam energy. While the ion-impact cross section (Eq. (3.18)) increases for this range of energies, its absolute magnitude is dwarfed by the other two processes and does not affect the trend that the total cross section decreases with increasing beam energy. Since most exterior ionization is a result of interactions with the lower coronal density just outside of the separatrix, shorter penetration lengths associated with lower energies should lead to larger exterior ionized percentages, as is seen. On the other hand, higher energy increases the probability that a neutral particle will completely penetrate the chamber unionized. Again this is seen in the simulations. A majority of the shine through and exterior ionized protons of the beam come from that part of the beam that had a grazing incidence on the FRC.

The actual peak in deposition occurs at 250 KeV with 92 %. The *a priori* error estimate in the numerical integrator is 5%. The highest beam efficiency would seem to be at this energy. However such items as orbit quality that might revised these considerations have not yet been discussed. In such a case it might be beneficial to pick a different energy for those reasons. If such a need arises, the efficiency penalty will not be severe over a large energy range.

One other consideration that has not been included here (or anywhere else in this work) is the optimization issues associated with beam energy and neutralizer efficiency. The dependence of the neutralizer efficiency on the beam energy falls off quickly above critical energies on the order of 100 KeV. In actual experiments this factor should also be considered when designs are developed. If the neutralizer efficiency can be doubled, then a 10 to 20% decrease in deposition percentage will be more than offset by the extra current available from

the beam gun.

Fig. (3.9) shows a scan in the A_{impact} parameter for a 2 cm , 5° divergence beam with energy of 225 KeV. The scan goes from 0 to 25 cm. For reference, the field null is at $r = 15$ cm and the separatrix is at 21 cm. The deposition profile is maximum for $A_{\text{impact}} = 5$ cm with a value of 94%. It is fairly constant at this value with only a slight decrease with increase A_{impact} until $A_{\text{impact}} \sim 17$ cm when the deposition begins to drop rapidly until by the time that $A_{\text{impact}} = 25$ cm the deposition has become nil. This is easily understood as the simple result of aiming the gun. If we aim into the FRC most of the beam will be deposited. Since the FRC is dense enough to ionize the entire beam, if it is a direct hit. If we aim so that the beam doesn't intersect the separatrix, little deposition is expected. The width of the region about the separatrix where the deposition drops to zero is related to the beam width. For other cases with pencil-like beams, the cutoff is much sharper. For more diffuse beams it is broader still. The values for the shine through and exterior ionization is also shown. The shine through goes from 0 at $A_{\text{impact}} = 0$ to 89% at $A_{\text{impact}} = 25$ cm as would be expected from the "hit or miss" notion. The exterior ionization is greatest where $A_{\text{impact}} \approx r_{\text{sep}}$. This can be understood as a result of the fact that exterior ionized particles have a maximum path length in the FRC corona (the region of significant density just beyond the separatrix) for grazing trajectories. For this equilibrium, the density at the separatrix is 60% of the peak density, but falls off rapidly to 0 in 1 or 2 cm. It is encouraging that exterior ionization is not a large problem for even such a large density.

The naive conclusion is that any value of A_{impact} less than the sep-

aratrix radius would be a good choice. However, one needs to also consider the characteristics of the resulting charged particle orbit for such parameters. Clearly a choice of $A_{\text{impact}} = 0$ will lead to an orbit with a maximum amount of radial excursion. If such a particle is ionized at $r = r_i, z = 0$ it will have $P_\theta = \frac{e}{c}\Psi(r_i, 0) = \frac{e}{c}\Psi_i$. At the radial turning points of the orbit, $v_r = 0$. Therefore the turning points of the orbits will be at flux values of

$$\Psi = \Psi_i \pm \frac{rc}{e}\sqrt{2mE_{\text{beam}}}. \quad (3.27)$$

For the equilibrium under consideration, the maximum trapped flux is 1.92×10^5 Maxwell = 1.9 mWb but $(rc/e)\sqrt{2mE_{\text{beam}}} = r0.7\text{mWb/cm}$ for a 225 KeV proton beam. Therefore, almost all particles will be on an escape orbit if they are aimed at the origin. The implication is that the beam should be aimed near, but inside, the separatrix and not at the symmetry axis. To determine exactly how far inside the separatrix requires consideration of the beam width and the beam penetration characteristics. Specifically, the beam should be aimed in such a fashion that most of the particle will ionize when v_r is small and v_θ is maximum. This means A_{impact} should be chosen according to,

$$A_{\text{impact}} = \sqrt{r_{\text{sep}}^2 - l^2}, \quad (3.28)$$

where l is an averaged penetration depth for the beam. The relationship is illustrated in Fig. (3.10).

Figure 3.10: Beam Trajectory, Penetration Geometry.

Most of the beam will ionize near the point P and will be in near optimum orbits. Of course the nature of the ionization process is such that some particles will be ionized before or after this point. In actuality, there is a bias in the ionization. More particles are ionized on the beam path before the point P than are ionized afterward. This is simply because the neutral beam intensity decreases monotonically along its path. Thus there is more beam to ionize on the inbound path than there is to ionize on the outbound path. This will be discussed in more detail below.

The conclusion is that the NBC algorithm allows the calculation of the first correction outlined above. It also shows that that correction can be adjusted such that the vast majority (80 – 90%) of the beam is deposited in the FRC. However, the NBC algorithm, by itself, is not able to estimate the other corrections. Some method is needed to trace the orbits after ionization and to characterize their radial and axial variation in time and the resultant beam currents in the plasma.

3.7.5 Description of NBF Algorithm

The NBF algorithm is an extension of the Modified FLX algorithm[47] which in turn was an extension of the fluid FLX algorithm.[82, 32] Each of these algorithms has an explicit analytic form that is related to the summary model presented in § (2.8). However, the primary motivation for deriving all of these models is to implement computational technique for simulation. The FLX algorithm solves the fluid dynamical equations, Eq. (2.126)-Eq. (2.131), assuming that the beam quantities are absent. The Modified FLX algorithm retains the J_b terms in these equations and determines J_b self-consistently with the beam

dynamical equation and relations (Eq. (2.132), Eq. (2.133), and Eq. (2.143)) while neglecting electron drag effects and friction force effects ($\mathbf{d}_e$ and $\mathbf{R}_{be}$). The modified FLX algorithm leaves the specification of H_b in Eq. (2.132) to the user. The NBF algorithm extends the modified FLX algorithm to explicitly specify that H_b corresponds to source of ionized particles from a realistic energetic neutral beam gun as described above.

It should be noted that neglecting the drag terms in this chapter will prevent modelling of current drive effects. However, such effects are not the object of study here. The focus is the beam's ability to stabilize the tilt mode. However, if current drive were investigated, some of the efficiency analysis presented here would apply there also. However, the discussion of fluid-beam interaction given below is not relevant for current drive studies because of the neglect of drag effects.

The simulation techniques involved are a novel combination of three distinct, but oft used computational physics algorithms, gridded discretization, particle-in-cell (PIC), and Monte-Carlo methods. FLX discretizes the fluid variables onto a mesh in r and z and mode expands in θ . [82, 32] The dynamical equations are advanced in time with a semi-implicit scheme. The modified FLX scheme adds a PIC simulation. The electric and magnetic fields from the fluid simulation are used to push the PIC particles. The current from the particles is then fed back into the fluid equations. Since the time scales are often widely separated, two time steps are used. One for the particles and one for the fluid simulation. The particles are then pushed in a subcycling fashion and the currents are accumulated by means of an orbit-averaging scheme. NBF adds a Monte-Carlo ionization scheme that reproduces the effect of specific collision

cross-sections and neutral beam gun parameters.

Run-time switches allow various interactions to be selectively turned on and off. This feature is useful to test physical mechanisms for observed behavior and to check the simulation integrity with other simulations and analytic results. Specifically, the plasma can be held fixed in time and the motion of the beam particles studied. The beam current can be held fixed in time and the plasma response calculated. Also, the term in square brackets in Eq. (2.127), the Hall terms, can be eliminated.

NBF models the neutral beam gun by loading particles at the initial beam position during the beam pulse time. Initially the particles are given a charge of 0. The particles proceed in straight-line motion. At each step they are tested for the possibility of ionization. When ionized, they are given a charge of $+e$ and then move in the computed electric and magnetic field. In the limit of a large number of particles, the NBF particle source term will recover the actual characteristics of a physical beam gun. It should be noted that this algorithm for modelling beam ionization collisions is very different from intensity integration along path length approach of the NBC scheme. If NBF is run in a mode where the plasma response is turned off, then the aggregate ionization profiles from NBF should match the results from NBC. The differences will be a reflection of the errors from using a finite number of particles or a finite integration step-size. The results presented in Fig. (3.8) and Fig. (3.9) are reproduced to within 2% for NBF runs with 400 particles. Since the actual NBF code is an outgrowth of simulations that used the modified FLX algorithm[47] there is confidence of its ability to reproduce previously simulated fluid and particle responses. This check verifies that the ionization characteristics are

also accurately calculated. the conclusion is that the NBF algorithm is adequate to model realistic beam injection, deposition, and interaction with the bulk FRC plasma.

NBF also allows calculation of orbits of the deposited beam particles. Which was beyond the scope of NBC. When NBF was run with the plasma interaction turned off, the second correction discussed in § (3.7.1) can be calculated. Fig. (3.11) and Fig. (3.12) show the fraction of the beam that is ionized on escape orbits. A particle is said to be on an escape orbit if its orbit intersects the chamber wall radially or axially. These graphs present the same optimization as shown in Fig. (3.8) and Fig. (3.9) The number of particles was 400 giving a $\sqrt{N}$ error bar estimate of 5%. The energy scan shows that the particles are fairly well confined for energies of 225 KeV and below. As the beam energy increases beyond this level more and more beam is lost. Most of the lost orbits are lost because the orbit intersects with the radial wall. A rough estimate says that the energetic particle gyroradius is less than R_{wall} for energies less than 1 MeV. In fact particles with energies of 360 KeV and below will have gyro-radii smaller than R_{sep} . Naively, this would lead one to expect that the escaping beam fraction as a function of energy would not slope upward until much higher energies than is seen for the results in Fig. (3.11). The explanation for this is that the beam was aimed with $A_{impact} = 14$ cm. Therefore the larger beam energies are trapped in orbits that are far from optimum. They will have large radial excursions. Therefore the particle loss threshold will be lower than would naively be expected, as is observed.

Fig. (3.12) shows the escaping beam fraction as a function of A_{impact} as was discussed above in § (3.7.4) when the beam was aimed at the symmetry

Figure 3.11: Escaping Beam Fraction as a function of Energy.

Figure 3.12: Escaping Beam Fraction as a function of A_{impact} .

axis, the orbits are escape orbits. The reason is simply that P_θ at the point of ionization does not allow radial trapping. The escaping beam fraction decreases linearly from near 100% at 5 cm to less than 10% at 12 cm. The result of these two figures is that the escaping orbit fraction correction is less than 10% if the beam steers clear of extremely high energies and small values of A_{impact} . Thus the combined effects of the first 2 corrections listed in § (3.7.1) is on the order of 10%

3.7.6 Depressed Field and Bumpy Orbit Corrections

The combined effect of the first four corrections can be calculated by accumulating the toroidal beam current in an NBF simulation while holding the plasma fixed. This eliminates the fifth correction, the fluid interaction. The total beam current for the same two 1-dimensional parameter scans are shown in Fig. (3.13) and Fig. (3.14). These simulations modeled a 50 milli-Coulomb beam current out of a simple gun ($N_b = 3.125 \times 10^{17}$). Eq. (3.26) gives 300 KAmps for the estimated total beam current in the plasma. Fig. (3.13) show that the total current peaks at a value of just over 200 KAmps at a beam energy of 225 KeV. This means that the cumulative effect of the first four effects listed in § (3.7.1) reduce the total beam current in the plasma to about 2/3 of the estimated value. The efficiency drops for lower energy because the particles are moving slower. Also they tend to be ionized at radii larger than in optimal orbit radius. At energies > 225 KeV, the current is decreased because more of the particles are lost in collisions with the wall. If one is willing to accept a sub-optimal value total beam current in the plasma, a large energy range is available. For instance, 50% of the estimate can be obtained for energies

Figure 3.13: Total Beam Current as a Function of Beam Energy.

Figure 3.14: Total Beam Current as a Function of A_{impact} .

between 150 KeV and 300 KeV.

Fig. (3.14) shows a scan of A_{impact} (given $E_{\text{beam}} = 225$ KeV) The peak is at 15 cm with a total current of 209 KAmps. This parameter pair ($E_{\text{beam}} = 225$ KeV, $A_{\text{impact}} = 15$ cm) was the highest current found for all simulations, although the $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm case was almost as high at 205 KAmps. Again these are near the 2/3 of the crude estimate. The current falls off for lower radii, principally due to radial wall collision from bad P_{θ} values at the point of ionization. At large radii the current decreases due to the beam simply not intersecting enough plasma to ionize a significant amount of the beam.

Additionally, in the 12 cm to 20 cm range, the current is also affected by the fourth correction listed in § (3.7.1). Ideally, a 225 KeV beam would have an optimum orbit near $r = 18$ cm. However, the beam penetration problem is an attenuation problem. In fact, for all parameters studied the beam source (number of particles ionized) is largest when the beam crosses the separatrix. The choice of A_{impact} should be smaller than the optimum radius in order to quickly traverse the outer portion of the plasma. For instance, suppose the beam energy is chosen such that the radius of the optimum orbit is 18 cm and the separatrix is at 21 cm. Particles that ionize at $r = 21$ cm will have large amplitude radial betatron motion which will decrease that particle's contribution to the total beam current in the plasma. However, particles that ionize near $r = 18$ cm will be in an almost optimum orbit. For this example, define a "green zone" from $r = 17$ cm to $r = 19$ cm. Also for the sake of this example, assume ionization points in the "green zone" give good particle orbits while orbits outside the "green zone" are of such poor quality to not

be of use. If the beam were aimed with $A_{\text{impact}} = 18$ cm, the path length between passage of the separatrix until $r = 19$ cm is 50% longer than if it is aimed at $A_{\text{impact}} = 15$ cm (4.73 cm vs 3.03 cm path lengths). This is shown in Fig. (3.15).

Figure 3.15: Comparative Beam Penetration Path Length.

This is simply a geometric effect. However, the path length inside the "green zone" ($17\text{cm} < r < 19\text{cm}$) is longer (12.2 cm) for the $A_{\text{impact}} = 18$ cm beam than for the $A_{\text{impact}} = 15$ beam (7.3 cm path length). Which aim point is preferable will depend on the beam penetration length, λ . If λ is small, then it is more important to shorten the path length from the separatrix to the green zone. Otherwise too much of the beam is ionized into bad orbits. If λ is large, then it is more important to aim the beam to graze the inside edge of the green zone to maximize the path length in the green zone. Of course this example is a simplification in that there is no sharp demarcation between good and bad orbits, rather it is a gradual degradation of the orbit by the excitation of radial betatron oscillations. Moreover, one needs to also consider the fact that the aiming will also effect v_r of the particle at ionization. These effects are too complex to analytically describe. However, they help to explain the behavior that governs the position of the current peak in the A_{impact} scan in Fig. (3.14). Particularly, it shows why the optimum value of A_{impact} is less than the radius of optimum orbit. Fig. (3.16) illustrates this feature for two runs. One has $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm and the other has $A_{\text{impact}} = 20$ cm. The average ionization radius is smaller for $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm. It is also broader.

The radial beam density and current profiles are shown in Fig. (3.17) and Fig. (3.18). Both of these figures are for 225 KeV beams. Fig. (3.17) has $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm while Fig. (3.18) has $A_{\text{impact}} = 20$ cm. The most important feature to note in Fig. (3.17) is that both the density and current have twin peaks in radius. The peaks point down since the current is negative for this equilibrium field direction. This is a consequence of the fact that A_{impact} is considerably less than the radius of the optimal orbit. When the particles are

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.16: Radial Ionization Positions for Beams aimed with $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm (a) and 20 cm (b).

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.17: Beam Density and Current Deposition Profiles, $A_{\text{impact}} = 14$ cm.

Figure 3.18: Beam Density and Current Deposition Profiles, $A_{\text{impact}} = 20$ cm.

ionized, they have significant v_r , which gives them large radial oscillations. On a time averaged basis, the particles tend to linger at the radial turning points, since a classical oscillator spends most of its time at the turning points. This explains why the density has twin peaks located at the radial turning points. Additionally, at the turning points all of the kinetic energy is contained in azimuthal motion while for intervening values of r some fraction of the kinetic energy is contained radial motion. This explains why the beam current is even more peaked than the density. The fact that the current density peaks at lower radius are larger than the peaks at larger radius is a $1/r$ cylindrical geometry effect. For some particles, the maximum kinetic energy contained in radial motion is equal to the total kinetic energy, the typical particle is ionized into an orbit with a maximum kinetic energy in radial motion that is $1/3$ to $1/2$ of the total kinetic energy. This means that v_θ is maximum at the turning points and smaller at other values of r . This explains why the radial current profile

is even more peaked than the beam density profile.

It should also be noted that the outer peak is actually located well outside the separatrix. Nevertheless, these particles are confined both radially and axially. Actually axial confinement is not realistic here since these beams were fired with $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$). However, other simulations presented in the next chapter with non-zero values of B_{θ} show that axial confinement is not an issue, until times long enough for the plasma response to have a back-reaction on the beam dynamics. The point is that the particles are confined even though a large part of their orbit is outside of the separatrix. This is in contrast to common solubility assumptions made in analytic treatments.[49]

Fig. (3.18) shows radial beam density and current profiles when $A_{\text{impact}} = 20$ cm. In this case, when the particles are ionized, much less energy is locked in radial motion. These profiles exhibit a single peak that is located near $r = 20$ cm. One might think of this as the limiting case where the separation of the two peaks is less than their natural widths. However, in this case the beam particles still spend a great part of their orbit beyond the separatrix, although in this case, the maximum distance beyond the separatrix is less.

It seems that the characteristic of spending a large part of the orbit near or beyond the separatrix is a universal feature of beams that originate in a neutral gun. It appears to be that penetration far into the plasma requires a large portion of the beam to be ionized at or just inside the separatrix with enough energy in radial betatron oscillations to reach beyond the separatrix. The fact that the orbits extend beyond the separatrix may or may not affect the beam in other ways. For instance rapid loss from collisions with cold particles may be an issue.

This result, although understandable in hindsight, is still somewhat surprising and interesting. The implication is that the beam radial profile can be selected (to some extent) by altering the placement of the beam guns. Moreover, the cost in terms of optimum performance may not be too severe. The total current from the $A_{\text{impact}} = 20$ cm case was 50% of the crude estimate, while the most optimized case was 67%. Since this will change the spatial dependence of J_b , which is thought to be the factor affecting tilt stability, it means that there may be additional physically relevant parameters besides the beam strength and the plasma equilibrium. The particular beam profile will also affect other beam studies such as rotational mode stabilization[69, 70] and FRC transport analysis.[64]

The conclusion that is drawn for the non-interacting cases is that the crude relation between neutral beam current out of the neutral beam guns and the ionized beam current in the plasma, Eq. (3.26), needs to be multiplied by a factor of the order of 1/2 to 2/3 when realistic descriptions are given. Secondly, the beam will inevitably exist both inside and outside the plasma. Finally, there are physical control parameters that can be used to tailor the beam current profiles inside the FRC, to some extent. It seems warranted to repeat these computational studies with a net that is cast larger to explore this issue more completely.

3.8 Fluid Interaction and Influence on Tilt Mode Activity

3.8.1 Fluid Interaction Correction

The fifth correction listed in § (3.7.1), the effect of fluid back-reaction, has not yet been explored. To do so, one must allow dynamical evolution of the fluid variables. This is done in the NBF scheme with the toggling of an input parameter to allow evolution of the warm plasma.

Fig. (3.19) shows a measure of this effect. It is a graph of the total efficiency for a set of runs. It plots the total beam current in the plasma as a percentage of the estimate from Eq. (3.26) as a function of time. All of the cases are for a beam of width 2 cm and a divergence angle of 1.5° . The pulse time is $3 \mu\text{sec}$. The beam is fired with $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$ and $A_{\text{impact}} = 14 \text{ cm}$. The beam energy was 225 KeV. Each run contained 1000 particles, but the statistics of the simulation was much greater because the particles are pushed and accumulated over 300 times in each fluid time step by means of the sub-cycling algorithm. This allows a simulation of 1000 particles to give statistics that are usually seen from simulation runs with 300,000 particles! What is varied in these traces is the total beam amount and whether the fluid interaction is turned on. The first trace is with the fluid interaction absent. It shows a linear rise to the plateau maximum of 70% at a time of $3 \mu\text{sec}$.

Figure 3.19: Normalized Interacting Total Beam Current.

The other traces are interacting cases of varying beam strength. If the interaction was turned off, all traces would overlay the first trace since the non-interacting case is simply a single particle response to a fixed field structure. The difference between the interacting cases and this non-interacting case then becomes a measure of the effect of the fluid interaction on the energetic beam quality. The general trend is that with increasing beam gun current, the efficiency ratio decreases. Physically this implies that as the beam becomes stronger and stronger, it perturbs the fluid more and more violently. Since the estimated current changes with changes in the beam gun current, the data is presented as a normalized percentage of this theoretical maximum, Eq. (3.26). As this perturbation grows, the fluid reaction is such that the total beam current is reduced. This back-reaction effect reduces even the small 5 mC beam efficiency from 67% to about 55%. The 50 mC beam has an efficiency of 30% and the 150 mC beam peaks at 20%. The 500mC beam is such a large disruption that it terminates the simulation in a few μsec . This large disruption also leads to a field configuration that eliminates almost all trapping possibilities. These numbers were given normalized to the theoretical maximum efficiency. It is also useful to analyze the total beam current delivered to the system in relation to the equilibrium plasma current inside the separatrix, which was ~ 580 KAmps. This implies that a perfectly efficient (100% current with beam current for a value of N_b of 145 mC. When the efficiencies are considered, one finds that 2%, 12%, 25%, and 18% of the total equilibrium current was supplied by the beams for the 5 mC, 50 mC, 150 mC, and 500 mC interacting cases, respectively.

There are several possible fluid interactions that can affect the beam

motion. The resistive flux decay will lead to an azimuthal electric field that can accelerate (or decelerate) the particle in the low field regions and cause drifts in the high field regions. The plasma tilting motion can also cause changes in the beam motion, and also lead to deconfinement of the orbits. However, the initial tilt perturbation was not applied, so tilt activity should be reduced. In practice this means that the tilt mode will have to grow from noise instead of an initial value. This should delay noticeable tilt activity to later than $10 \mu\text{sec}$. However, this was not independently verified on these runs. Since the equilibrium has no energetic beam, the introduction of such a beam will necessitate adjustment of the plasma configuration to a different equilibrium state. This adjustment can affect the ability to trap beams and the fluid motion can induce electric fields that can extract energy from the beam. These effects have characteristic time scales. The physical mechanism may be similar to previously described return current effects[66] or resonant energy extraction scheme.[65] Although conclusions about the exact identification of which of these effects is important in each of these cases, some tentative conjectures can be guessed.

The 5 mC case seems to oscillate on a 2-3 μsec time scale. The 5 mC does not seem to be strong enough to cause a great change in the plasma behavior. Thus the difference between the 5 mC interacting case and the non-interacting case then becomes a measure of the inductive electric field and temporal variation of the magnetic field upon particle orbits. Under those conditions neither H or P_θ are constants of the motion. Separate diagnostics showed that both H and P_θ varied greatly during the simulation. Although only a few particles were examined, two classes of behavior were observed. The injected particles had an initial energy of 3.6×10^{-7} erg (225 KeV). Two

examples of the first type of behavior as shown in Fig. (3.20) and The initial value of P_θ depended on the point of ionization, but was typically around $1.5 - 1.8 \times 10^{-14}$ gm m² / sec. These orbits tended to have a large range of radial motion. As time progressed, they lost energy, down to $1-2 \times 10^{-7}$ erg and gained canonical angular momentum. Some particles gained enough angular momentum for P_θ to become positive and the particle escaped. This is a "non-prompt escape" in the sense that the orbit path at ionization was confined but that the fluid interaction changed the values of H and P_θ until the particle moved to an escape orbit. A "prompt escape" particle would leave the system in less than $1/2$ μ sec after ionization.

The second type of orbit is illustrated in Fig. (3.22) and Fig. (3.23). They had the same initial energy, but, on average, slightly lower initial P_θ . They do not have the secular trend of decreasing H and increasing P_θ although their values did vary greatly. The deeper values of P_θ implied that the turning points of radial betatron motion were less extreme. This may explain the different type of behavior, but the conclusion is not yet clear. A manner to classify the orbits in a time-varying field is lacking.

Figure 3.20: Particle Orbit, Example 1. Plots of z vs. t (a), x vs. y (b), P_θ vs. t (c), and E vs. t (d)

However, there is one generality that can be stated about the nature of the changes in H and P_θ . They appear to be piecewise constant with step function like changes. That is $\dot{P}_\theta$ and $\dot{H}$ are the sum delta functions. Plots of P_θ vs. r and H vs r show that these jumps tend to correlate with r , with the largest radii having the biggest effect (Fig. (3.24)). This suggests a mechanism for the interaction. Each flux surface may have a different electrostatic potential. As particles cross back and forth they increase and decrease their electrostatic potential. However, the electrostatic potential changes in time. So the potential drop from the inner to the outer radial turning points changes with time. This forms an energy extraction mechanism. For the non-interacting case there are similar jumps, but of much smaller magnitude and they have some memory in that successive errors cancel and the long term secular trend averages to no effect. While the reason this particular point in the orbit is so important is not clear at this time. However the configuration is remarkably similar to the problem of configuration and particle motion in the earth magnetotail and neutral current sheet.[53, 89]

The 50 mC case in Fig. (3.19) shows a further reduction in the total beam current deposited in the plasma to about 30% of the estimate. In the 5 mC case there were two effects at play. The first was that the electric fields and the motion of the plasma caused changes in the beam's orbits that led to reduced current. This effect was not a back-reaction effect. Rather it only expressed the fact that beam was not hitting a stationary target. This first effect assumed that the plasma's motion was not a result of the 5 mC beam. The second effect is that the beam motion may have been affected by bulk plasma motions that were themselves caused by the presence of the beam. It

Figure 3.21: Particle Orbit, Example 2. Plots of z vs. t (a), x vs. y (b), P_θ vs. t (c), and E vs. t (d)

Figure 3.22: Particle Orbit, Example 3. Plots of z vs. t (a), x vs. y (b), P_θ vs. t (c), and E vs. t (d)

Figure 3.23: Particle Orbit, Example 4. Plots of z vs. t (a), x vs. y (b), P_θ vs. t (c), and E vs. t (d)

Figure 3.24: Variation of H vs. τ for interacting case(a) and non-interacting case(b).

is argued in the 5 mC case that this should not have been a big effect since 5 mC is a small beam, but this assertion was not proven. However, the difference in efficiency between the 5 mC and the 50 mC beam is entirely attributable to this second back-reaction effect. That is, if the 50 mC beam's efficiency was reduced only because of simple plasma motions without any back-reaction effects, then it would overlay the 5mC result. Since it doesn't, the difference must be due to back-reaction effects. Observations of a few of the orbits in the 50 mC case showed a marked increase in the number of orbits in the class that lost energy and increased their value of P_θ to near 0.

The 150 mC case in Fig. (3.19) continues the trend in reduced beam efficiency with increasing beam strength. It obtains only 20% of the estimated total beam current in the plasma. A new feature also emerges. For the 5 mC and 50 mC cases, the currents reached their maxima within 2 μsec after the beam pulse and remained close to that value of the remaining 5 μsec . However, the 150 mC case shows a current peak at the end of the beam pulse and a decay after that, to the point that at 8 μsec , the current is about 1/2 of its original value. This is because of a loss of axial confinement. As was noted in previous simulations[47] if the local beam current in the plasma became too large, the beam lost axial confinement. This arose because the beam current became large enough to modify the magnetic field curvature at the midplane. That is, normally constant flux contours, $r(z; \Psi)$ where $r(z; \Psi)$ is defined as the locus of point with a value of poloidal flux of Ψ . Normally the outer branch of $r(z; \Psi)$ is a maximum at $z = 0$. This means a particle with $v_z = 0$ at $z \neq 0$ will acquire motion in the z -direction and move toward the midplane ($z = 0$) and set up axial betatron motion. However, when the beam becomes strong enough, it

will modify the magnetic field as if there was a diffuse coil located *inside* the plasma. When it is strong enough, then for some values of Ψ , the outer branch of $r(z; \Psi)$ will no longer be a maximum at $z = 0$. This is also often stated in terms of the convexity of surfaces of constant Ψ . If the current is large enough it may cause the flux surfaces to be non-convex. In that case, if a particle is orbiting in the midplane with v_z it is unstable to axial betatron motion and will begin to move in z . This is in contrast to the case when the flux surfaces are convex. Then motion in the midplane remains in the midplane.

From the beam width and divergence angle, one expects that the particle motion would remain within 10 cm of the midplane. This is indeed the case for the 5 mC and 50 mC cases. However, the 150 mC case shows a large fraction of the beam that is executing very large amplitude axial motion. In this sense the beam has become strong enough to axially destabilize itself. Axial destabilization is defined as when motion in the midplane does not remain in the midplane. However, axial destabilization does not imply loss of axial confinement, because at large z convexity is restored and there the change in P_z of the particle will try to force it back toward the midplane.

Even though the efficiency of the 150 mC case is smaller, the absolute beam current in the plasma is larger than that for the 50 mC and 5 mC cases because the efficiency is a ratio of theoretical maximum current, I_b , from Eq. (3.26), but the estimate, I_b is three times larger for 150 mC than for 50 mC.

Axial destabilization in and of itself does not imply a loss of beam current in the plasma. It only implies that the current will be spread out axially. However, when the axial betatron motion becomes large, the variation

of Ψ with z has to be included. In that case the field line curvatures that drive axial and radial betatron motion change in the frame of reference of the particle. Thus one is forced to consider coupled nonlinear axial and radial betatron motion. This may allow for decay of the beam current. Plots of selected particle orbits show that a common orbit will begin to wander in z . For given values of H and P_θ the particles appear to be able to escape radially or axially when they are at large values of z near the axial separatrix (spindle point) than when they are near $z = 0$.

An alternate explanation for the axial deconfinement may be found in studies of the buildup of Astron layers.[65] There resonant interactions of energetic, encircling particles with the fields can cause axial motion to arise from Landau damping. This is interesting because it would provide a mechanism both for axial destabilization and energy extraction. Plots of the total beam current as a function of time shown below in § (3.8.2) do show a rather short time scale, low amplitude modulation that is on the scale of the axis encircling time for the energetic particles. Which, if either, of these two possibilities are actually the case has not been conclusively identified at this time.

The 500 mC simulation in Fig. (3.19) terminates due to the plasma density locally being driven to 0. This is because the beam is so strong that it drives almost all of the plasma out of its region. Thus it tends to recreate a vacuum where the beam current is strongest. It peaks at about 5% efficiency. In absolute terms, this current is still less than the maximum current in the 150 mC case at 3 μ sec. However, by 3 μ sec, some portion of the 150 mC beam has already become axially deconfined and therefore the localized peak of beam current density is not as large as the 500 mC case. Another way to look at it,

is that the 500 mC case, for the first μsec is like firing 167 mC with a 1 μsec pulse time. It hits just as hard, but much faster.

There is one final feature about Fig. (3.19). One can ask is the source of the reduced efficiency due to more particles being lost or is it due to each particle contributing less current on a per particle basis. The answer is that it is both. By the end of the simulation, the non-interacting case has 93.3% of the particles fired from the gun still confined; the 5 mC case, 91.5%; the 50 mC case, 60.1%; the 150 mC case, 23.5%; and the 500 mC case, 0.0%. The fraction of lost particles can explain a majority of the efficiency drop from the 5 mC case, but not all. This means that other effects such as a reduction of average beam particle energy are causing a significant effect. Moreover, the difference between the non-interacting case and the 5 mC case is due almost entirely to this energy reduction effect. This energy reduction is not due to drag, since no drag is modelled here. Instead, it is the extraction of beam kinetic energy non-collisionally. It appears to be a result of an induced E_θ that acts to decelerate the beam and spin up the FRC.

These set of runs were all conducted with a single beam aimed at the midplane. Therefore, an estimate can be formed about the maximum strength of a neutral beam gun. The conclusion is that if the beam gun emits much more than 50 mC, most of it will be wasted in reduced efficiency. It may be possible to increase this maximum by increasing the pulse time, but this has not been explored.

However, this does not imply that the total beam current in the plasma is limited to 50 mC. Multiple beams can be used and aimed with different values of B_{impact} . For the 50 mC case the majority of the beam remains

within 5 cm of the midplane. that is the average axial betatron turning point is $z = \pm 5$ cm. The radial betatron turning points are at $r = 15$ cm and $r = 29$ cm. This gives a rough estimate of the plasma volume that can support 50 mA of beam current. Of course this estimate is very rough in the sense that orbits are connected globally in real space and also in phase space. Nevertheless, the path to higher total beam current in the plasma seems to require multiple beam guns.

3.8.2 Tilt Mode Suppression

The next simulation study was to attempt to use the information from the beam optimization studies to simulate beam stabilization of tilt activity. The same equilibrium as used above was again used. However, the initial velocity was given a perturbation with peak amplitude of 1% of the Alfvén velocity and an eigenfunction similar to [30] or identical [32, 47] to previous studies. Since the goal was to simulate a physically realizable situation, the beam energy was reduced to 100 KeV in order to have acceptable neutralizer efficiency. The point being that at higher energies, it is impossible to develop a high current, fast pulse, neutral beam. Several similar simulations were conducted. The fluid was simulated in 3-dimensions. However, the azimuthal mode expansion was truncated after the $n = 1$ mode. This meant that only the $n = 0$ and $n = 1$ modes were retained. While inclusion of the higher modes is possible it was not done here for three reasons. First, other modes are not needed to determine the linear stability of the tilt mode. Second, the $n = 2$ rotational mode will be zeroed out which might otherwise act as noise affecting the tilt results. Third, the required computer time increases rapidly with increasing mode number.

The fewer the modes, the faster the computations.

Five beams are modeled. All had energies of 100 KeV, radii of 2 cm, and divergence angles of 1.5° . The beams had values of B_{impact} from -40 cm to $+40$ cm in 20 cm increments. The values for A_{impact} were 15.5, 18.0, 18.0, 18.0, and 15.5 cm. The values for B_{impact} were -40 , -20 , 0 , $+20$, and $+40$ cm, respectively. Each beam carried the same number of particles, but that number varied from run to run. The background plasma is modeled using the FLX algorithm. The resistive, viscous, and Hall terms are retained. The electron-beam collisional drag force is neglected. For each run, the number of simulation particles was 5000

Five runs were conducted. The nominal total beam strength was 250 mC, 50 mC in each beam. Some of the runs had less however. RUN-I has no beams present. It should (and does) reproduce previously observed the fluid tilt instability.[32]. It is a standard to which the beam effects can be measured. RUN-II is a 2-dimensional case. That is, it only retains the $n = 0$ mode. This prevents the evolution of the tilt mode. It will serve as a test of the ability of the beam to affect the equilibrium of the FRC. RUN-III is the base case run with 250 mC of beam with the $n = 1$ mode allowed. This is the nominal configuration. RUN-IV is identical to RUN-III except the total beam strength has been reduced to 100 mC. Finally, RUN-V has a tiny beam of strength $1 \mu\text{C}$. This beam is so small that it should not affect the fluid dynamics. Thus RUN-V is essentially a non-interacting test particle run. It will serve two purposes. First fluid quantities should evolve almost exactly as in RUN-I. Second, the evolution of the beam can be compared to the interacting 5mC run in the previous section. Most of the differences should be attributable to the fact

that the FRC is tilting underneath the beam in RUN-V but is not in the 5 mC run of the previous section.

The general results of these 5 runs are described here. RUN-I exhibited pure fluid tilt motion as expected. RUN-II was pathological. The beam stayed highly localized in z . The local beam current density was much larger than the total current density. $\mathbf{J}_p$ was in the opposite direction to $\mathbf{J}_b$. That is the plasma current was reversed. Since flux decay is a consequence of resistivity from the plasma current, as seen in § (2.9), resistivity actually led to an increase in flux instead of flux loss. The peak trapped flux increased by a factor of 2.5 by the end of the simulation. The total energy in the beam was reduced, while the fluid plasma was spun up to large (super-Alfvénic) speeds. It should be noted that this occurred without including drag effects or the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ terms. This means that there was an indirect beam-plasma coupling that was mediated by the electric and magnetic fields. This run leads to two conclusions. First, the perturbations that led to axial deconfinement are very important to the combined dynamics of the plasma plus beam system. That is, the mechanism that limits the size of the local beam current density involves 3-dimensional effects. We are also led to the conclusion that at least some part of the energy extraction mechanism that transfer beam kinetic energy to plasma motion is retained in the 2-dimensional limit. However, many of the other conclusions about this run in terms of the magnitude of quantities are not physical because: one, the local beam density is a large fraction of the plasma number density invalidating the $\delta = 0$ approximation and the neglect of the $\sigma_b \mathbf{E}$ term, and two, the physical beam would not stay in such a small region of the FRC due to axial motion induced from 3-dimensional effects.

RUN-III showed a large perturbation of the plasma motion both for $n = 0$ and $n = 1$ motion. At early times the beam had a large peak at the midplane and a significant but smaller value over the rest of the region inside the separatrix. Fig. (3.26) shows contours of the beam current at $5 \mu\text{sec}$. During this period, the peaking of the beam at the midplane digs a deep density and pressure well in the fluid plasma as shown in Fig. (3.25). At later times, the beam current has dispersed along the entire interior of the FRC. The peak value of the current density has been reduced by a factor of 3 but the total integrated current has remained almost unchanged as shown in Fig. (3.27). Also on this time scale, the fluid has also started to tilt as seen by a plot of the flux contours in Fig. (3.28).

DENSITY CONTOURS IN R-Z PLANE
AT T = 0.00 AT TIME = 5.000E-06
(MIN = 9.000E+03 MAX = 1.229E+15)
total system mass = 5.914e-04

5.12E+13	2.56E+14	4.61E+14	6.65E+14	8.70E+14	1.08E+15
1.54E+14	3.58E+14	5.63E+14	7.68E+14	9.73E+14	1.18E+15

Figure 3.25: Density Contours at $t = 5 \mu\text{sec}$.

It is not clear which is the cause and which is the effect. That is, did the axial deconfinement of the beam allow the plasma to tilt, or did the plasma tilting cause the beam to become axially deconfined. Which is the case, or whether such a distinction can even be made is not clear. It also should be noted that the injection of this large current has also changed the shape of the plasma equilibrium. Comparison of the flux contours in Fig. (3.28) with the initial contours shown in Fig. (3.7) reveals that the separatrix has moved outward in r . The separatrix has not lengthened in the sense the z_{sep} has not changed. However, the radius of the separatrix for z values in the range of 30 cm to 60 cm is much larger. This implies that the plasma volume has also increased significantly. Also, the magnetic field structure has changed. The $\mathbf{J}_p \times \mathbf{B}$ force may have a radically different shape at this point in the simulation than it did initially. This raises a question as to whether it is meaningful to compare the tilt perturbations in this run with those in runs without beams. One suggestion is that 250 mC may be simply too large of a beam.

RUN-IV is run with a smaller total beam of 100 mC. The beam is better confined. It also does not modify the equilibrium flux surface shapes as dramatically. This case also seems to suppress tilt mode activity initially, but at later times, a weaker, but definitely identifiable tilt mode is seen. This suggests that 100 mC is small enough to avoid drastic equilibrium perturbations and beam degradation from fluid feedback mechanisms. However, it also appears to be too small to completely stabilize tilting motions. RUN-V reproduces all of the features of RUN-I. It also provides some diagnostics of particle characteristics that will be described below.

Fig. (3.29) shows the total plasma current contained inside of the sepa-

IONIZED BEAM DENSITY IN R-Z PLANE
AT T = 0.00 AT TIME = 5.000E-06
(MIN = 0. MAX = 2.133E+14)
total beam ion number = 1.487e+18

8.89E+12	4.44E+13	8.00E+13	1.16E+14	1.51E+14	1.87E+14
2.67E+13	6.22E+13	9.77E+13	1.33E+14	1.69E+14	2.04E+14

Figure 3.26: Beam Current Contours at $t = 5 \mu\text{sec}$.

IONIZED BEAM DENSITY IN R-Z PLANE
AT T = 0.00 AT TIME = 1.000E-05
(MIN = 0. - MAX = 7.974E+13);
total beam-ion number = 1.481e+18

3.32E+12	1.66E+13	2.99E+13	4.32E+13	5.65E+13	6.98E+13
9.97E+12	2.33E+13	3.65E+13	4.98E+13	6.31E+13	7.64E+13

Figure 3.27: Beam current Contours at $t = 10 \mu\text{sec}$.

PSI COUTOURS IN R-Z PLANE
AT T = 0.00 AT TIME = 1.000E-05
(MIN = -4.786E+05 MAX = 1.600E+06)

-4.31E+05	-1.91E+05	-4.79E+04	0.	2.30E+05	9.22E+05
-2.99E+05	-1.08E+05	-1.20E+04	5.76E+04	5.18E+05	1.44E+06

Figure 3.28: Flux Contours at $t = 10 \mu\text{sec}$.

matrix.

Figure 3.29: Total Plasma Current Inside of Separatrix.

Fig. (3.30) shows the total beam current inside the separatrix.

Figure 3.30: Total Beam Current Inside of Separatrix.

These traces help to understand the behavior of these runs. RUN-I and RUN-V show the behavior without the injection of beams. Fig. (3.29) shows that the initial plasma current is large (and negative) with a value of ~ 600 KAmps. The value remains fairly constant until about $t = 15 \mu\text{sec}$ where it is rapidly disrupted from tilt activity. The tilt mode steadily grows from its small initial amplitude. It is only large enough to be noticed in Fig. (3.29) after the mode has grown a few e-fold. The traces for RUN-I and RUN-V in Fig. (3.30) are indistinguishable from the $I_b = 0$ axis. By comparison, RUN-II starts out with a plasma current of 600 KAmps but it is quickly depressed to below 100 KAmps as the 250 mC beam is injected. The plasma current has been replaced by beam current as is seen in Fig. (3.30). This is a very large beam case. For instance, Eq. (3.26) estimates $I_b = 1.5$ MAmps. In fact this beam is so strong that it almost reverses the total of the plasma current.

When 3-dimensional variation is added in RUN-III, this large beam is not maintained. Initially the beam does depress the plasma current, but the beam current decays in time. This allows tilt activity to begin.

RUN-IV shows the most promise for achieving tilt stability without wreaking excessive havoc on the plasma integrity. This 100 mC beam set gives rise to about 200 KAmps of beam current within the separatrix (as in all of these cases, there is also a considerable amount of beam current outside of the separatrix). This is about a 30% efficiency as compared to Eq. (3.26). Moreover the beam current in RUN-IV remains constant through the simulation as seen in Fig. (3.30). It does not appear to be subject to the beam degradation seen in RUN-III. However, the strength of this beam appears to be too weak to stabilize the tilt activity. As seen in Fig. (3.29) the plasma current slowly

decays from near 350 KAmperes to around 275 KAmperes.

Fig. (3.31) shows the time dependence of the plasma kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ mode.

Figure 3.31: Kinetic Energy in $n = 1$ tilt mode (a) for the entire run and (b) for early times.

This is a measure of the tilt activity. Fig. (3.31)a shows the entire runs from 0 to 35 μsec . Fig. (3.31)b expands to show the early behavior. The tilt growth time (e-folding time) is estimated to be 6 μsec for this equilibrium. RUN-I and RUN-V show the classical tilt behavior. They peak at $t \approx 25 \mu\text{sec}$ where independent diagnostics show that the field lines have opened and the entire FRC is disrupted. The RUN-III amplitude is at a lower level and doesn't show obvious exponential growth. RUN-IV appears to be stable, but for times $> 20 \mu\text{sec}$, it begins to exhibit exponential growth. The trace for RUN-II is not shown since it is a 2-dimensional limit.

The key to understanding this behavior is in the early time dependence. For RUN-III the perturbation of the fluid from beam injection is larger than the initial perturbation that is designed to trigger the tilt mode. This may explain why RUN-III does not show exponential kinetic energy growth. Most of the $n = 1$ plasma motion is simply response to the brute force of the invading kinetic beam. At any rate, RUN-III gives a fairly large perturbation to the $n = 1$ plasma motion. This, along with $n = 0$ motion, may be a cause for the behavior of RUN-III. This run terminates early when the plasma density goes to 0. For RUN-IV this perturbation is smaller and apparently, the plasma recovers since the amplitude decreases after beam injection is complete. For $t > 10 \mu\text{sec}$, the $n = 1$ kinetic energy in RUN-IV is actually less than that for RUN-I. This is evidence of the beam stabilization effect. However, at later times this effect is lost. This may be a consequence of the slow decay of the plasma current (Fig. (3.29)).

Fig. (3.32) shows corresponding plots for the $n = 0$ plasma kinetic energy.

Figure 3.32: Kinetic Energy in $n = 0$ mode (a) for the entire run and (b) for early times.

In Fig. (3.32)a the outstanding feature is that RUN-II has a huge kinetic energy. By comparison, this energy peaks at a value that is over 10 times as large as the kinetic energy in tilt mode activity in a non-beam situation. This energy is primarily contained rotational motion. It is questionable whether this result is physical, since the artificial restriction to 2-dimensional motion is very suspect. For instance, such large rotation rates would surely excite 3-dimensional rotational modes.

The behavior of RUN-I and RUN-V is characteristic of classical tilt mode activity. The $n = 0$ motion shows exponential growth. It is slaved to the $n = 1$ activity. As the $n = 1$ perturbation acts to open up the field lines, significant $n = 0$ motion is induced as plasma rapidly streams out the end of the FRC.

RUN-III shows initial behavior that is similar to RUN-II, it begins to diverge after $t = 5 \mu\text{sec}$. This is an indication of 3-dimensional effects leading to beam degradation. RUN-IV shows behavior that is similar to RUN-III but is of smaller amplitude. Nevertheless, the $n = 0$ motion in RUN-III and RUN-IV are both larger than the intrinsic tilt-induced motion as seen in RUN-I.

This feature also helps to explain the large early time $n = 1$ amplitudes for RUN-III and RUN-IV. The beam current in the plasma is mainly in the $n = 0$ mode. The magnitude of $|\mathbf{j}_{b\theta}|$ for the $n = 1$ mode is only 1% of the magnitude of the $n = 0$ mode. This can be understood by the fact that the beam particles will encircle the symmetry axis on a time scale of the order of $0.2 \mu\text{sec}$. This is short compared to the pulse time of $3 \mu\text{sec}$. After pulse completion the beam is loaded rather uniformly in θ . Moreover subcycling over the fluid time-step also reduces the contribution from $n \neq 0$ modes to $\mathbf{J}_{b\theta}$ since

the fluid time-step is $0.5 \mu\text{sec}$. It is understandable that the introduction of a beam would affect the kinetic energy in the $n = 0$ mode, but the fact that it also affects the $n = 1$ energy is a new feature that was not anticipated. However, the scale between Fig. (3.32)b and Fig. (3.31)b is a factor of 20. So that even though the $n = 1$ components are much smaller than the $n = 0$ components, they are still large when compared to the small initial tilt perturbation amplitude. That is, the motion the beam induces in the plasma seems to be as important, or perhaps even more important than the initial tilt mode perturbation.

This suggests that one should stop and revisit the question of tilt stability in different equilibria. The beam stabilization may be due either to dynamical effects of the beam, or it may simply be a consequence of changing the equilibrium of the FRC. From an experimental perspective, this distinction is not important. Both imply that the introduction of the beam leads to tilt stability, but for the sake of theory and to predict and design future experiments, it is desirable to understand which of these mechanisms is responsible. This issue is the genesis of the investigations in Ch. (4).

The difference between RUN-III and RUN-IV is more important than it appears at first glance. It is more than just a factor of 2.5, the ratio of their total beam strength. The relevant parameter is the ratio of total beam current to total plasma current. for RUN-III this ratio is ~ 5 but for RUN-IV it is closer to 0.7. This suggests that the FRC will be sensitive to small changes in the total beam current within this range. That is, the parameter window between 100 mC and 250 mC may seem to be only 2.5, but in terms of the relevant physical parameter, it is closer to 10.

There are also other parameters that may affect the tilt stability char-

acteristics. One of these features is the location of the beam guns. For this study, 5 beams were used in order to spread the beam across all axial positions. However, in hindsight, this may not be the best choice. Fig. (3.33) shows the beam distribution function, $f(z)$, as a function of z , for the different values of B_{impact} , where the dependence on other variables has been suppressed (integrated).

Figure 3.33: Beam Distribution Function as a Function of z for Different Axial Aim Points; (a) $B_{\text{impact}} = \pm 40$ cm, (b) $B_{\text{impact}} = \pm 20$ cm, (c) $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$ cm.

Fig. (3.33)a show $f(z)$ for the two guns at $B_{\text{impact}} = \pm 40$ cm. Fig. (3.33)b shows $f(z)$ for the two guns at $B_{\text{impact}} = \pm 20$ cm. Fig. (3.33)c shows $f(z)$ for the gun at $B_{\text{impact}} = 0$ cm. The beams fired at ± 40 cm actually covered the region from -40 to $+40$ fairly uniformly while the beams aimed with $B_{\text{impact}} = \pm 20$ cm did not reach much beyond $|z| = 20$ cm, and the beam fired in the midplane ($z = 0$) never got beyond $|z| = 5$ cm. Thus the total beam distribution, $f(z)$ for all guns combined is not optimal. It is larger for smaller values of z , and has a very sharp peak near $z = 0$ since the entire current from the middle beam is concentrated there. If the simulation were repeated, it seems preferable to use only 2 guns placed at $z = \pm 3L_z/4$. This would give beams that extended over almost all values of z inside the separatrix. Moreover, there would be moderate peaks located near the ends of the plasma where the beams will have the most stabilizing effect[47].

Analysis of the beam distribution function at the end of the simulation also allows the documentation of the fact that energy has indeed been extracted from the beam through a fluid interaction feedback mechanism. Fig. (3.34) shows plots of $f(E)$, the beam distribution function as a function of energy.

Figure 3.34: Beam Distribution as a Function of Energy, $f(E)$ for; (a) 250 mC 2-D case at $t = 40 \mu\text{sec}$, (b) 250 mC 3-D case at $t = 16 \mu\text{sec}$, (c) 1000 mC 3-D case at $t = 36 \mu\text{sec}$, (d) $1 \mu\text{C}$ 3-D case at $t = 27 \mu\text{sec}$.

In each of the panels, the scales change to accommodate the entire distribution function. In RUN-II (Fig. (3.34)a) the entire beam has lost a great deal of energy. The average value for the energy has dropped to ~ 65 KeV. This is consistent with the statements above about the large energy extraction to drive super-Alfvénic plasma rotation. RUN-III, (Fig. (3.34)b), also shows a loss in energy to an average of ~ 65 KeV. However, RUN-IV, (Fig. (3.34)c), lost much less energy. Its final average energy was much higher at around 85 KeV. Finally, RUN-V, (Fig. (3.34)d), lost almost no energy at all. The fact that smaller beams lost less energy is proof that the energy extraction mechanism is a finite beam effect. The beam affects the fluid which then affects the beam in a feedback fashion. If the beam is minuscule (RUN-V) or if the interaction is turned off, this effect is not seen. There is actually an explanation for this phenomena. When the beam is injected, it sets up its own current inside the plasma. These currents are strong enough to move the magnetic field lines aside. Since the plasma is frozen to the field lines, the plasma is partially evacuated from regions of high beam density. Thus plasma motion is induced by the beam. The violence of this motion will be in proportion to the strength of the beam. Larger beams will evacuate a larger area faster. When this plasma motion is initiated, an electric field is induced from the $\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B}$ term in Ohm's law. The sign of the electric field is set up in the θ direction that decelerates the beam. This may be the mechanism that is responsible for the beam deceleration. An interesting question[59] which has not been explored is whether longer pulse times will reduce this back-reaction effect.

Two principal conclusions are drawn from the studies of the effects of realistic beams upon tilt stability in FRC's. First, effective efficiencies of about

$1/3$ of the estimated maximum beam current in the plasma, Eq. (3.26) are possible. Secondly, there appears to be a maximum possible beam strength, beyond which the beam wreaks too much havoc on the FRC structure to maintain its own integrity. There is also a minimum beam strength, below which, the FRC will not be tilt stable. These effects were also seen in previous, non-realistic beam simulations.[47] In that study they found a window of opportunity where the mode can be stabilized without the beam being too strong to cause its own degradation. In these studies, we have not definitively identified such a situation. The exact maximum beam strength is a function of several parameters that if fully explored might increase this ceiling limit. Additionally, there is a good possibility that for beam strength between those studies here, that both conditions may be satisfied. However, there is also the possibility that in moving from idealized beams to realistic beams, these two constraints may overlap and there may not exist a window of beam strengths where the beam is strong enough to stabilize tilt activity but not too strong to cause its own degradation. The fact that much of the current is located outside of the separatrix and that many of the particles are trapped in orbits that are much less than optimal may contribute to this effect. There are many particles that carry current which affects the FRC equilibrium, but the current from these particle may not be localized in regions that are beneficial for reducing tilt activity. Even if no window exists, it is clear that the beam does decrease the violence of the tilt activity. Thus even an insufficient beam may be of use when coupled with other schemes that may also reduce tilt activity. The question of the existence of a parameter window is worthy of further investigation.

Chapter 4

Profile Stabilization

4.1 Motivation: Examination of Variation of Equilibrium Choice

The energetic beam stabilization studies suggested that the question of the variation of equilibrium configuration on tilt stability is worth revisiting, if for no other reason than to exclude it as a candidate for the mechanism responsible for tilt stabilization.

Previous theoretical work has concentrated on the shape of the separatrix as a determining factor of tilt stability.[28, 29, 30, 7, 31] The conclusions are that for FRC's which are more prolate than a critical value are unstable. The growth rate of the instability would be on the scale of the Alfvén transit time, Eq. (1.1),

$$\gamma_{\text{tilt}}^0 = \frac{C V_{\text{Alfvén}}}{b}, \quad (4.1)$$

where $V_{\text{Alfvén}}$ is an average Alfvén velocity, C is a constant, on the order of unity and b is the separatrix half-length. External stabilization is difficult since perturbations are confined largely within the separatrix, as has been verified in fluid simulations.[1, 6] Nonlinear simulations see no saturation mechanism before total disruption.[33, 32] Subsequent single fluid theory has been unable to find stability for equilibria of experimental interest. While toroidal rotation can

stabilize the mode,[7] the required rotation rate is much higher than observed in experiments. Effects from inclusion of the Hall term[38] and gyroviscous effects[39] indicate that stability can be achieved for high elongations. The several studies imply tilt instability is universal for equilibria of physical interest when kinetic effects are neglected. There was no theoretical reason to presume that other fluid equilibria would not also be unstable. Fluid simulations with numerical equilibria supported these conclusions.[6, 32]

More elaborate kinetic theoretical approaches show the possibility of stabilization by kinetic effects.[41] Many of the ion orbits in this regime are complex, resembling neither drifting Larmor orbits[42] nor betatron orbits.[43] Most experiments (with two recent exceptions[34, 44]) are of such a small size to allow large enough kinetic effects to increase the instability growth time to longer than the FRC lifetime.[41, 45, 43] A third exception is a cool FRC with high collisionality.[35] In that case the plasma may be so collisional ($\nu_{\text{coll}} > \Omega_{\text{cyc}}$) that fluid-like behavior is seen even in small devices.

It has recently been suggested that there may be another tilt mode stabilization mechanism — profile consistency.[50, 51] It is based on analysis of experimental data that suggests that many FRC's naturally self-regulate themselves into particular equilibrium configurations. It is conjectured that this is the result of the competition between a transport process and a marginally stable MHD mode. That is, transport will drive the equilibrium parameters in one direction until some fluid stability threshold is surpassed, at which point a fluid mode is excited which rearranges the plasma back away from the unstable set of parameters. The observed profiles have a nonlinear relationship between pressure P and poloidal flux Ψ . Previous studies have assumed that

the relationship was linear. The fluid displacement in variational theory can be expressed in terms of first and second derivatives of the pressure profile $P(\Psi)$ plus other terms independent of $P(\Psi)$, where Ψ is the poloidal flux. The $P'(\Psi)$ term is always destabilizing while the $P''(\Psi)$ term can be either stabilizing or destabilizing depending on the sign of $P''(\Psi)$. Alternatively this is stated in terms of comparisons between a normalized current, $j/r = P'(\Psi)$, at the O-point and at the separatrix.

This observation then re-opens the issue of tilt stability as a function of the choice of equilibrium. It also meshes very well with the issues raised in the Ch. (3) about whether tilt dynamics can be affected by the presence of an energetic beam.

The purpose of this chapter is to investigate the tilt stability of equilibria with special pressure profiles. The basic question can be stated as: Do MHD or Hall fluid equilibria exist which are stable against tilt perturbations? Our numerical simulations indicate yes, for a class of special, but perhaps realizable equilibria. The approach is to search for a small set of fluid equilibria using standard elliptic equilibrium solvers and then to use these as the initial data for initial value fluid simulations. The subsequent analysis neglects explicit kinetic effects (but does include extensions to fluid theory such as viscosity and Hall terms). Since kinetic effects are generally considered stabilizing, this analysis may be viewed as a conservative estimate of stability in this regard. Additionally, this investigation may serve as an indicator of the possible effects of different equilibria upon stability. This especially includes modification of the FRC due to energetic ion components.[47, 48, 49]

4.2 Hall Fluid Model and Numerical Formulation

FRC fluid theory has included various extensions to simple ideal MHD such as resistivity, equilibrium flow,[7, 38] non-diagonal pressure (ion gyroviscosity[39]), and Hall terms[38] in their analysis. These extensions arise from the inclusion of physical effects which are neglected in ideal MHD. This work continues these practices for comparison with previous computational results. It also allows for precise identification of the effects upon stability of the model extensions, independently and in combinations. The plasma is modeled by the following dynamical equations:

$$\frac{\partial n}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (n\mathbf{u}) = 0 , \quad (4.2)$$

$$Mn \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} \right] = \left(\frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} \right) - \nabla P - \nabla \cdot \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi} , \quad (4.3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{A}}{\partial t} = \mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} - \eta c^2 \frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} - H \frac{c}{en} \left[\frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla P_e \right] , \quad (4.4)$$

$$\frac{\partial S}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot S\mathbf{u} = \frac{\gamma - 1}{n^{\gamma-1}} \left[\eta \mathbf{J}^2 - \overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi} : \nabla \mathbf{u} \right] , \quad (4.5)$$

where n is the number density; $\mathbf{u}$, the flow velocity; M , the ion mass; $\mathbf{J}$, the current density; $\mathbf{B}$, the magnetic field; P , the total pressure; $\mathbf{A}$, the vector potential; η , the resistivity; S , an entropy density; P_e , the electron pressure; $\overset{\leftrightarrow}{\Pi}$, the viscous stress tensor; γ , the adiabatic constant; and H is an artificial variable used to include or exclude Hall effects. $H = 1$ utilizes the Hall terms while $H = 0$ ignores them. The derived quantities are defined by the following relations:

$$\mathbf{B} \equiv \nabla \times \mathbf{A} , \quad (4.6)$$

$$\frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \equiv \left(\frac{1}{4\pi} \right) \nabla \times \mathbf{B} , \quad (4.7)$$

$$P = nT , \quad (4.8)$$

$$P_e = f_{te} P , \quad (4.9)$$

$$\vec{\Pi} \equiv -(\nabla \mu \mathbf{u}) - (\nabla \mu \mathbf{u})^T + (\nabla \times \mu \mathbf{u}) , \quad (4.10)$$

$$S \equiv n^{2-\gamma} T \quad (4.11)$$

where f_{te} is a parameter determining the total pressure contained in electrons and μ is the viscosity coefficient. These are the same dynamical evolution equations as those presented in Ch. (2) with the beam terms neglected. Also $\mathbf{A}$ instead of $\mathbf{B}$ is used for the dynamical evolution of the magnetic field.

The ‘‘Hall’’ term, $c/en [\mathbf{J}/c \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla P_e]$, results from the massless electron approximation to the generalized Ohm’s law without the usual further assumption of wavelength small compared to spatial gradients.[90] Since FRC’s have large β and the tilt mode is a global mode, effects from the Hall term may be of dynamical importance. Another way to understand the physical importance of the Hall term is from a two fluid formalism.[38] In ideal MHD, $\mathbf{V}_e = \mathbf{V}_i$. Thus the Hall term measures the physical effects of the different responses of ions and electrons to equilibrium and perturbed fields. The value of the artificial parameter H is selected at run-time in order to include or exclude the Hall term effect.

The equilibrium problem is cast by taking the steady state limit of the dynamical equations with the extra assumptions of zero resistivity, zero viscosity, no Hall term, and no flow velocity. The geometry is specified as cylindrical (r, θ, z) coordinates with θ as the ignorable coordinate. It is further assumed that the toroidal field, B_θ , is zero, characteristic of FRC’s . If the

poloidal flux function is defined as:

$$\Psi(r, z) \equiv \int_0^r B_z(r', z) r' dr' . \quad (4.12)$$

The equilibrium equation,

$$\nabla P = \frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} , \quad (4.13)$$

reduces to the Grad-Shafranov relation:

$$\Delta^* \Psi \equiv r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial z} = -\frac{4\pi r^2}{c} \frac{dP}{d\Psi} . \quad (4.14)$$

Eq. (4.13) also implies that the pressure is entirely a function of the poloidal flux, $P = P(\Psi)$. This formulation can be extended to include the problem of an equilibrium which also contains an interpenetrating beam. However, the first purpose is to examine the effect of varying non-trivial equilibrium parameters on tilt activity. Therefore, in this chapter I will investigate with computational equilibria and dynamical simulation the effect of varying equilibria according to the profile consistency prescription.

Experimental data to determine the functional dependence of P upon Ψ is not available. Most work has used either a rigid rotor profile, a linear profile, or an approximately linear profile. Recent transport calculations[51] indicate that either pressure profiles or resistivity profiles must be of a more complex structure in order to explain observed flux loss and particle loss. In this chapter, profiles with more complex dependencies of P upon Ψ are examined.

These models are investigated using numerical equilibrium and initial value codes. The equilibrium solver[75] iteratively solves Eq. (4.14) for $\Psi(r, z)$. Its domain is the region $0 < r < r_{\text{wall}}$ and $0 < z < z_{\text{wall}}$, assuming $\Psi(r, -z) =$

$\Psi(r, z)$. Algorithmically, it is a descendant of previous 2-dimensional equilibrium studies.[4, 5, 6] The code set allows solution to both kinetic, rotating, or fluid plasmas. Only the fluid formulation is used in this investigation. The problem size was 45 cubic splines in the radial direction and 81 finite difference points in the positive z half-space.

The initial value simulation uses the FLX algorithm[82, 32] for 3-Dimensional spatial plus temporal plasma evolution. It numerically solves the dynamical model equations, Eq. (4.2)–Eq. (4.5). The evolution is solved using a semi-implicit time advance. The dynamic fields are represented in r and z on a finite difference, staggered grid. The toroidal direction (θ) is mode expanded. This is the same numerical approach used to compare predicted and measured probe signals in recent experimental tilt observations.[34] Simulations examining beam effects on tilt stability also used an extension of this algorithm.[47, 48] It is also the same algorithm that was used for the fluid portion of the interacting simulations in Ch. (3).

In these runs, 40 radial and 100 axial points were used. The axial points covered the region $-z_{\text{wall}} < z < +z_{\text{wall}}$, allowing for both even and odd axial dynamics. Since our goal is to study profile effects on tilt stability, only the modes with azimuthal index $n = 0$ and $n = 1$ are kept in these simulations. Nonlinear errors from neglecting higher mode couplings will not affect the conclusions about linear tilt stability.

The equilibria used in this investigation explore more fully different pressure (and hence current) profiles. Specifically, here equilibria are examined where the functional dependence of $P(\Psi)$ on Ψ is different from piece-wise linear, or approximately piece-wise linear.

The equilibria will be described in terms of conventional dimensionless FRC parameters. The first is a measure of the finite Larmor radius (FLR) corrections,

$$s \equiv \int_R^a \frac{r dr}{a \rho_i}, \quad (4.15)$$

where R is the radius of magnetic field null, a is the separatrix radius, and ρ_i is the local ion gyro-radius. A second measure is:

$$\bar{s} \equiv \frac{e}{c} \frac{|\Psi_0|}{\sqrt{MT(1-f_{te})}} \frac{1}{a}, \quad (4.16)$$

where $|\Psi_0|$ is the absolute value of the trapped flux. $\bar{s}$ is a quantity which can easily be calculated from numerically computed equilibria. Finally, S_* is defined by,[38]

$$S_* \equiv \sqrt{4\pi e^2 n_0 a^2 / M c^2} = \omega_{pi} a / c, \quad (4.17)$$

where n_0 is the plasma density maximum (density at O-point). The S_* is a measure of the importance of the Hall term in the plasma dynamics.

The relations among s , $\bar{s}$, and S_* can be derived by considering the case of highly elongated FRC equilibria where midplane field line curvature can be neglected. Pressure balance relates the peak pressure at the O-point to the external magnetic field, $P_0 = n_0 T_0 = B_{\text{ext}}^2 / 8\pi$. Thus in such high beta systems, the plasma and cyclotron frequencies are not independent, but are related by,

$$\omega_{pi} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{2} v_{ti}} \omega_{ci}^{\text{ext}} = \frac{c}{\sqrt{2}} \rho_i^{\text{ext}}, \quad (4.18)$$

where it is understood that the density at the O-point is used in the calculation of ω_{pi} and the external field is used in ω_{ci} and ρ_i .

s and S_* are related by:

$$S_* = \frac{\sqrt{2}}{\lambda} s, \quad (4.19)$$

where

$$\lambda \equiv \rho_i^{\text{ext}} \left\langle \frac{1}{\rho_i} \right\rangle \quad (4.20)$$

and

$$\langle A \rangle \equiv \frac{\int_R^{r_{\text{sep}}} A r \, dr}{\int_R^{r_{\text{sep}}} r \, dr}, \quad (4.21)$$

with the additional note that $R = r_{\text{sep}}/\sqrt{2}$. Note that $0 < \lambda < 1$. λ is a measure of the degree to which the average internal magnetic field is less than the magnetic field at the wall. λ will be small for small internal magnetic fields. s and $\bar{s}$ can be related through

$$\bar{s} = \frac{s}{\sqrt{1 - f_{te}}}, \quad (4.22)$$

when it is noted that Eq. (4.12) implies $\int_R^{r_{\text{sep}}} B r \, dr = \Psi_0$. Thus, $\bar{s}$ incorporates into s the partial cancellation of the Hall term effect arising from the ∇P_e term.

On the one hand, S_* is a measure of how the electron and ion fluids responses differ while s measures the importance of FLR and/or finite ω/ω_{ci} effects. For small FLR, the ion and electron response are identical. Therefore it is reasonable for s and S_* to scale similarly. The Hall term effect and other non-ideal MHD effects will be most pronounced for low s (and hence S_*). Practically, $\bar{s}$ is a better measure of these effects since it takes into account the details of whether the internal field is depressed (i.e. the factor of λ). The question of a depressed internal field is important since it is one of the principal features of hollow equilibria.

4.3 Profile Choice

In addition to the choice of physical model, the unique equilibrium solution depends on the specification of additional parameters. The boundary choice is a perfect conducting flux conserver at a fixed radius $r = r_w$ and a free boundary at $z = \pm z_w$. The flux at the wall is fixed as Ψ_w . The functional relationship $P(\Psi)$ must also be specified. Since the Grad-Shafranov equation is in general nonlinear, additional parameters may be necessary to uniquely specify the solution.[4, 5] The growth rate of the tilt perturbations, γ_{tilt} , may depend upon a multitude of parameters.

These may include geometrical factors (such as separatrix radius a ; $X_s \equiv a/R_w$; separatrix length, b ; separatrix elongation, $E \equiv b/a$), physical quantities (such as total trapped flux Ψ_0 ; midplane averaged beta, $\langle\beta\rangle$; temperature profile; pressure profile), experimental parameters (such as bias field; fill pressure; formation method; etc.), or model determining parameters (such as s ; velocity; and transport coefficients),

$$\gamma_{\text{tilt}} = \gamma_{\text{tilt}}(\Psi_w, \Psi_0, r_w, z_w, a, b, E, X_s, P(\Psi), \langle\beta\rangle, B_{\text{bias}}, P_{\text{fill}}, s, \eta, \mu, \dots) . \quad (4.23)$$

Many of these quantities are not independent. The elongation is just the ratio of separatrix length to separatrix width. The quantity $\langle\beta\rangle$ depends strongly on P_{fill} ; $\langle\beta\rangle$ is given in terms of X_s from axial force balance.[1] Experimental evidence relates $P(\Psi)$, η , and X_s . [51] Only small portions of parameter space may be tractably examined at once. An ansatz must be invoked to limit the parameters to survey. In this work possible profile functions are investigated. Specifying $P(\Psi)$ will almost uniquely specify the equilibrium. Since the equilibrium problem is nonlinear (for a general $P(\Psi)$ profile), there may be more

than one solution. In addition if the length of the separatrix, b , is specified, then in practice the equilibrium is uniquely specified.[4, 5] Other parameters that determine γ_{tilt} that have not been explicitly specified are thus implicitly determined from the above conditions. The choice of $P(\Psi)$ serves to specify most of these implicit relationships. Equilibrium characteristics such as race-track or elliptic separatrix shape and elongation will fall out from the profile choice as opposed to being specified parametrically.

Most previous theory has assumed that $P(\Psi)$ was linear in Ψ while exploring other (mostly geometric) effects of varying other parameters.[30, 1] There is an analytic solution with a nonlinear $P(\Psi)$ which has been used in some FRC tilt studies.[31, 91] However, this particular profile has a $P(\Psi)$ form that does not allow independent specification of $P'(\Psi)$ and $P''(\Psi)$. It is not clear whether such a restriction can allow enough flexibility to explore the competing effects from the $P'(\Psi)$ and $P''(\Psi)$ terms. To the best knowledge, all known numerical studies, except one[92], of FRC tilt stability assumed pressure profiles that were linear, piecewise linear, or an approximation thereof.[6, 4] Even though these equilibrium solvers have the ability to find numerical solutions for nonlinear pressure profiles, stability studies have not looked at such profiles. A separate numerical approach[93, 8] to numerical equilibria chooses the entropy function instead of a $P(\Psi)$ profile. The implied $P(\Psi)$ profile is not linear, but again, it does not appear to have been used in stability studies.

The one exception is an early numerical simulation.[92] The current profile chosen in that study varied sinusoidally with a polynomial of the flux. The profile concentrated normalized current, j_{θ}/r , of the same magnitude at both the separatrix and the O-point. Depending on the choice of a profile index,

the normalized current between the O-point and separatrix and between the O-point and axis was higher or lower. That study did not report any large scale instability consistent with tilting for tens of Alfvén transit times.

Our choice of pressure profile is designed to investigate the possibility of hollow profiles having a stabilizing effect.[50, 51] The pressure profile is allowed to be a nonlinear function of the flux function. This may perhaps be regarded as an allowance for the possibility of a self-organizing tendency of FRC plasmas.[94, 50] A parameterized profile is chosen that allows the concentration of current at either the O-point or near the separatrix:

$$P(\Psi) = P_0 \mu(\chi) = \begin{cases} P_0(K_0 - \chi - \frac{1}{2} D\chi^2) & \chi \leq 0 \\ P_0 \left(\frac{1}{F} e^{-F\chi} \right) & \chi > 0 \end{cases}, \quad (4.24)$$

where P_0 is a normalizing constant for the pressure. Varying P_0 during the iterative solution process will serve to fix the separatrix length. $\mu(\chi)$ is the profile shape function. χ is the normalized poloidal flux, $\chi \equiv \frac{\Psi}{|\Psi_0|}$, and $\Psi_0 < 0$ is the trapped flux, the flux at the O-point. K_0 , D , and F are profile parameters. They are specified by four conditions: continuity of $\mu(0)$ and $\mu'(0)$ at the separatrix; $\beta_{\text{sep}} \equiv \frac{P(\Psi=0)}{P(\Psi_0)}$ given; and D given. Solving for F and K_0 , one obtains,

$$K_0 = \frac{\beta_{\text{sep}}(1 - D/2)}{1 - \beta_{\text{sep}}}, \quad (4.25)$$

$$F = \frac{1}{K_0}. \quad (4.26)$$

Hollowness and peakedness of the profile are defined as parameters that describe the current (or equivalently pressure) distribution within the separatrix.[51] The local values of $P'(\Psi) = j_\theta/r$ are compared. A "peaked"

profile has its current concentrated at or near the O-point. A “hollow” profile has the current concentrated near the separatrix (away from the O-point). In terms of the pressure profile, a peaked profile will be very peaked around the O-point and fall rapidly, even for regions still inside the separatrix. A hollow pressure profile will remain large and flat until very near the separatrix where it will then decrease. A flat profile has $P(\Psi)$ linear in Ψ inside of the separatrix. This corresponds to a current density which depends linearly on radius. In this case $P''(\Psi) = 0$. It should be noted that the discussion of “hollowness,” “peakedness,” and “flatness” are defined in terms of the variation of P with Ψ . Reconstruction of the spatial dependence of P will require further knowledge about the spatial solution for Ψ .

For this profile choice, the parameter D specifies the hollow or peaked equilibrium character. $D = 0$ gives a flat profile; $D > 0$, hollow; and $D < 0$ peaked. Note D is not identical to h , a previously defined hollowness parameter,[51] however, the qualitative notions of “hollowness” and “peakedness” are the same. This choice of profile function gives $P''(\Psi) \propto -D$ inside the separatrix. Thus D is a control parameter to increase or decrease the relative importance of the effect of the $P''(\Psi)$ term. The destabilizing $P'(\Psi)$ term is also modified by D : $P'(\Psi) \propto -1 - D\chi$. Since $-1 < \chi < 0$, D acts to decrease the tilt mode driven by $P'(\Psi)$ for $0 < D < 1$. On the exterior flux surfaces, $P''(\Psi) > 0$. This does not cause instability since the field lines have good curvature in this region.

This profile possesses adequate generality to probe possible profile stabilization effects while only requiring exploration of a small 2-dimensional parameter space. All equilibrium parameters are specified by the choices of bound-

β_s	D	$\hat{\gamma}$	$\sigma_{\hat{\gamma}}$	h	X_S	$\langle\beta\rangle_{vol}$	E	Ψ_0 (mwb)	$\bar{s}$
0.1	-1.00	1.41	0.17	1.21	0.83	0.43	2.80	9.05	12.49
0.1	-0.50	1.28	0.17	1.13	0.81	0.48	2.88	7.55	10.69
0.1	0.00	1.26	0.17	1.00	0.77	0.56	3.01	5.58	8.26
0.1	0.50	1.32	0.17	0.76	0.69	0.67	3.34	3.12	5.12
0.1	0.75	1.32	0.26	0.53	0.63	0.74	3.70	1.83	3.33
0.1	0.80	1.29	0.26	0.46	0.59	0.77	3.91	1.48	2.85
0.6	-1.00	1.44	0.13	1.21	0.53	0.72	4.99	1.20	2.60
0.6	-0.50	1.18	0.11	1.13	0.51	0.73	4.86	1.05	2.33
0.6	0.00	0.83	0.07	1.00	0.50	0.77	4.74	0.91	2.07
0.6	0.50	0.18	0.17	0.75	0.46	0.83	5.00	0.63	1.54
0.6	0.75	0.07	0.26	0.53	0.41	0.88	5.63	0.40	1.09
0.6	0.80	0.01	0.26	0.46	0.39	0.89	5.88	0.33	0.97
0.6	0.85	-0.04	0.26	0.38	0.38	0.90	6.16	0.28	0.85

Table 4.1: Characteristics of equilibrium solutions, including: Separatrix Beta, β_{sep} ; Hollowness Parameter, D ; Normalized Growth Rate, $\hat{\gamma}$; Normalized Growth Rate Error, $\sigma_{\hat{\gamma}}$; Hollowness Parameter, h ; Ratio of Separatrix to Wall Radius, X_S ; Volume Averaged Beta, $\langle\beta\rangle_{vol}$; Elongation, E ; Trapped Flux, Ψ_0 ; Kinetic Effect Parameter, $\bar{s}$

ary conditions, model formulation, profile functional form, imposed separatrix length, and by the point chosen in the (β_{sep}, D) parameter space.

4.4 Equilibrium Solutions

In this section, a series of equilibrium solutions are reported. They are broken into two sets, $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$ and $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$. These two sets are then scanned in D from peaked to flat to hollow values of D . The dimensional characteristics of these equilibria approximately correspond to previous numerical simulations.[47, 32] The dimensionless characteristics of some of these profiles are summarized in Table (4.1). As can be seen, varying β_{sep} and D with this profile choice also entailed changes in other physically meaningful variables. In

this sense, what was varied and what was fixed is not a division of parameter space into an orthogonal set of physically meaningful quantities. Contour plots of Ψ for some of these equilibria are shown in Fig. (4.1).

Figure 4.1: Poloidal flux contours of FRC equilibria.

Several features are observed for this parameter scan. Ratio of plasma radius to wall radius, X_s , is smaller for higher β_{sep} and for more hollow profiles.

The separatrix half-length b is a fixed input parameter. Therefore the elongation varies proportionally to X_s . However, a local pseudo-elongation can be defined in terms of the length versus the width of internal flux surfaces. This may be more physically meaningful since the actual $\Psi = 0$ contour, being a separatrix, is susceptible to small perturbations. This is especially pronounced for peaked profiles. This local pseudo-elongation may also be viewed as a closer approximation to the local field line curvature. In the literature, this is often referred to as the question of a racetrack vs. elliptical shaped flux surface.[6] Elliptical profiles tend to have a their field line curvature distributed all along z , while racetrack equilibria have almost all of their field line curvature concentrated into a small endcap near $z = b$. Peaked profiles ($D < 0$) lead to elliptical, low pseudo-elongation profiles, while hollow ($D > 0$) profiles cause racetrack, or high pseudo-elongation profiles.

The volume averaged β , $\langle\beta\rangle_{\text{vol}}$, is larger for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ equilibria (note that volume averaged β , $\langle\beta\rangle_{\text{vol}}$, is different from midplane averaged β used in the relation $\langle\beta\rangle_{\text{mid}} = 1 - X_s^2/2$). For fixed β_{sep} , $\langle\beta\rangle_{\text{vol}}$ increases for hollow profiles, as expected. Also note that for the given profile choice, high β_{sep} and hollow profiles tend toward decreased plasma volume, peak plasma pressure and actual trapped flux (Ψ_0). Low Ψ_0 can be partially explained in terms of the boundary condition fixing Ψ_w . A smaller X_s implies a smaller external field, which is one of the natural normalization parameters of the equilibrium. However, for Ψ_0 there is an additional effect. Two equilibria with identical X_s will have differing values of Ψ_0 depending on their degree of hollowness.

The trapped flux Ψ_0 is usually not directly measured in experiments, but rather is inferred from the measured excluded flux radius and an assumption about the $P(\Psi)$ profile.[37, 1] Experiments would report identical inferred values for Ψ_0 , while their actual values may vary. Direct experimental observation of hollowness of profile (and hence also Ψ_0) requires direct knowledge of P as a function of radius, $P(r)$. It is necessary to perform interferometry at many different radii in order to differentiate hollow, flat, and peaked profiles experimentally, since this distinction relies on the second derivative of the pressure. Fig. (4.2) shows normalized current, $|j_\theta(r)|/rB_{\text{wall}}$, and pressure profiles $P(r)$ at the midplane for some of the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ equilibria. While the distribution of current density varies greatly as D is varied from highly peaked to highly hollow, the pressure profile is only mildly modified. It is not clear that previous experiments could have distinguished hollow and peaked profiles from previous interferometry data that had only modest numbers of radial data points and shot to shot variation.[1, 95]

Figure 4.2: Normalized pressure and current radial profiles for $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$.

4.5 Dynamical Simulation Results

These equilibrium solutions were then used to initialize the dynamical simulation. An initial perturbation velocity of peak amplitude equal to 1% of $V_{\text{Alfvén}}$ was added. The functional form of this perturbation resembles other compressionless, internal trial functions.[30, 6, 47] The objective was to determine γ_{tilt} for each equilibrium and compare it to γ_{tilt}^0 . The simulation parameters were nominally similar to the FRX-C/LSM experiment.[87] They ran for 25 μsec , which is about 5 growth periods. The *a priori* hypothesis was that γ_{tilt} would be considered independent of pressure profile in this parameter search if the normalized growth rate, $\hat{\gamma} \equiv \gamma_{\text{tilt}}/\gamma_{\text{tilt}}^0$, is within a factor 2 of unity. Geometric manipulation of the equilibrium separatrix shape for flat profiles can change the growth rate by as much as a factor of 2.[30, 29, 6] Any profile modification effect is required to lie outside of this noise range. The γ_{tilt} was measured from fits to the kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ mode.

The measured growth rates are summarized in Table (4.1). Fig. (4.3) shows the time histories of $n = 1$ kinetic energy.

Figure 4.3: Kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ tilt mode for $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$ in (a) linear and (b) logarithmic scales and for $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$ also in (c) linear and (d) logarithmic scales

Figure 4.4: Tilt growth rates as a function of hollowness.

For the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$ cases the saturation amplitude decreased as the profile changed from peaked to hollow but the growth rate (as measured by the slope on the logarithmic plot) is essentially unchanged. Separate diagnostics show that all magnetic field lines are open after the peak amplitude in all cases. This allows parallel motion from inside the separatrix to the end walls. Separate diagnostics also show a depletion of the central pressure peak on an Alfvén transit time scale. Similar traces are shown for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ cases. Again the peak tilt amplitude was lower and the time of tilt peak was longer for the more hollow cases, but the effect was more pronounced. The scale for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$ case is about 60 times larger than the scale for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ case. A more surprising feature emerges in the logarithmic traces, where the actual growth rates (determined from the slope of the traces) show a decreasing trend with increasing hollowness. Fig. (4.4) plots $\hat{\gamma}_{\text{tilt}}$ as a function of hollowness.

The hollow, high β_{sep} profiles show a clear trend toward lower growth rates. These features are reinforced when traces of field lines are examined.

Fig. (4.5) shows a sample of integrated magnetic field lines. The field lines open up not only for the flat profile cases (Fig. (4.5)a and Fig. (4.5)c) but also for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$ hollow cases (Fig. (4.5)b). However, the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ $D = 0.8$ and $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ $D = 0.85$ cases (Fig. (4.5)d–Fig. (4.5)g) maintain closed field lines for up to $50 \mu\text{sec}$, further indicating tilt stability. $50 \mu\text{sec}$ is about 10 growth times and is a significant fraction of τ_{Ψ} , the flux confinement time. At this late time, the configuration has changed considerably owing to simple transport effects.

Finally, Fig. (4.6) shows the perturbation mode structure well into the simulation for selected profiles. These are snapshots of the $n = 1$ poloidal components of the velocity after development of the natural mode structure from the initial perturbation and noise. The flat profile cases (Fig. (4.6)a and Fig. (4.6)c) show the usual tilt mode displacement as an almost rigid rotation perpendicular to the symmetry axis. The hollow profiles Fig. (4.6)b, Fig. (4.6)d, and Fig. (4.6)e show a mode structure much more localized to the end regions as previously observed.[6] This is explained by the concentration of instability inducing field line curvature in the end regions. However, the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$, $D = 0.8$ case Fig. (4.6)b shows an interesting new feature. The instantaneous velocity streamlines are localized into 3 cells of length $2b/3$ instead of the normal single cell of size $2b$ as would be the case for rigid tilting. Similar effects have previously been noted in Hall fluid simulations.[32] At later times, this mode structure evolves decreasing the central cell and enlarging the outer cells until they all finally merge late in the simulation into a normal tilt type

mode structure. The $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6, D = 0.8$ and $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6, D = 0.85$ cases (Fig. (4.6)d and Fig. (4.6)e) had less well defined mode structures. The mode was very localized to the endcaps with no other discernible structure.

Figure 4.5: Magnetic field lines (a) $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$, $D = 0.00$, $t = 20 \mu\text{sec}$ (b) $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$, $D = 0.80$, $t = 20 \mu\text{sec}$ (c) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.00$, $t = 25 \mu\text{sec}$ (d) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.80$, $t = 25 \mu\text{sec}$ (e) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.80$, $t = 50 \mu\text{sec}$ (f) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.85$, $t = 25 \mu\text{sec}$ (g) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.85$, $t = 50 \mu\text{sec}$.

Next I consider whether the apparent tilt stability of the hollow high β_{sep} profiles is robust to minor numerical or physical modifications of parameters. Is the behavior due to coarseness of numerical grid? Is the behavior due to a short simulation time? Is the behavior due to viscous effects? Is the behavior due to the Hall term? Five additional dynamical simulations were conducted to address these questions. They extended the simulation to 50 μsec (approximately 10 growth times). Two of the cases were repetitions of the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$, $D = 0.8$ and $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$, $D = 0.85$ runs above. They served as the baseline cases to measure the effect of these model and algorithmic variations. The purpose is to determine whether questions about simulation integrity and physical model can cause a simulation to vary more than the variation caused by changing the D parameter from a value of 0.80 to 0.85. The other three simulations were repetitions of the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$, $D = 0.85$ case with modifications. One modification was to run the simulation with a grid doubled in both the r and z directions. Another was to halve the viscosity coefficient, and the final case was run with the Hall term absent ($H = 0$ in Eq. (4.4)). The time history of the $n = 1$ mode kinetic energy is shown in Fig. (4.7).

Figure 4.6: Perturbation mode structure (a) $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$, $D = 0.00$, $t = 5 \mu\text{sec}$ (b) $\beta_{sep} = 0.1$, $D = 0.80$, $t = 15 \mu\text{sec}$ (c) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.00$, $t = 15 \mu\text{sec}$ (d) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.80$, $t = 15 \mu\text{sec}$ (e) $\beta_{sep} = 0.6$, $D = 0.85$, $t = 15 \mu\text{sec}$.

Figure 4.7: Kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ tilt mode-integrity runs.

The vertical scales on the linear plots are about a factor of 1000 smaller than for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$ cases in Fig. (4.3), and a factor of 20 smaller than the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ cases in Fig. (4.3). The effect of doubling the grid or halving the viscosity was less than the effect of changing D from 0.85 to 0.80.

The effect of neglecting the Hall term changed the trace significantly. Moreover, separate diagnostics showed that this $H = 0$ case could not be classified as absolutely tilt stable, if for no other reason than that the field lines were opening up by the end of the simulation as shown in Fig. (4.8).

Figure 4.8: Field lines for the $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$ $D = 0.85$ $H = 0$ case at time $t = 50$ μsec .

However, the level of tilt activity for the $H = 0$ case was still much less than either the hollow $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.1$ or the flat profile cases.

Nevertheless, Fig. (4.7) shows that except for the $H = 0$ case, the level of $n = 1$ kinetic energy differs little from its initial perturbation value and is characterized by slow evolution or oscillation rather than exponential growth. The $H = 0$ case can be seen as a long 40 μsec oscillation or an unstable mode with a saturation 2 to 3 e -foldings from onset. The initial value numerical simulation technique has trouble distinguishing between these possibilities.

The effect of the Hall term appears important to tilt stability. A final series of runs was conducted to focus on this issue. Simulations were conducted in pairs for various values of D (with $\beta_{\text{sep}} = 0.6$). One member of the pair included the Hall term while the other neglected it. The results are shown in Fig. (4.9).

Figure 4.9: Kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ tilt mode, comparison of Hall term effect for different values of D .

In all instances, the kinetic energy in the $n = 1$ tilt mode is less when the Hall term is included. For the flat profile case, the two traces are almost identical. For the hollow profiles (large values of D) the traces diverge. Beyond a value for D of about 0.5, increasing hollowness does not decrease tilt activity if the Hall term is neglected. The $D = 0.85$ run without the Hall term more closely resembles a value of $D = 0.50$ than $D = 0.85$ when compared with runs that included the Hall effect.

4.6 Discussion and Implications

We set out to investigate profile effects upon tilt stability. The conjecture that hollow profiles will have a tendency toward reduced tilt activity is borne out by simulation. However, hollowness alone is not sufficient to eliminate unstable growth. We have found that the effect is only sufficient for high values of β_{sep} . It should be noted that an initial value simulation cannot give reliable information on contours of marginal stability. Typically at marginal stability the growth rates approaches zero and the modes become oscillatory. A half period of oscillation is difficult to distinguish from growth and saturation when kinetic energy histories are the only diagnostic. Future numerical variational modelling and variational theory may give more concrete statements about marginal stability contours.

Further, if the Hall effect is neglected, there appears to be a lower bound on the effectiveness of hollowness. Equilibrium profiles with hollowness parameters below this bound experience “diminishing returns” with respect to the ability of additional hollowness to suppress instability. Moreover, the values of hollowness required to achieve stability are below this bound. Increasing

the hollowness of an equilibrium reduces the strength, and to some point the growth rate of the tilt instability. However, only when hollowness is combined with high β_{sep} and the inclusion of the Hall effect are simulations seen that appear stable. It should be noted that these relationships were observed for only a particular class of equilibria. These results may not generalize to different equilibria with differing sets of fixed and varying equilibrium parameters.

In these simulations I chose $f_{te} = 0$. This cold electron assumption is in accord with previous kinetic calculations[41] and is a fair approximation of low fill pressure experimental conditions soon after formation.[96, 87] The Hall term is proportional to

$$\frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla P_e = \frac{\mathbf{J}}{c} \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla P + (1 - f_{te})\nabla P = (1 - f_{te})\nabla P, \quad (4.27)$$

when one makes use of the non-rotating equilibrium condition, Eq. (4.13). Thus the effect of errors in choice of f_{te} in non-rotating equilibria is equivalent to varying the ad hoc Hall Parameter H . The physical value is $H = 1$. Using a value of f_{te} less than its physical value thus overestimates the effect of the Hall term, but by no more than a factor of 2. Additionally, the simulation run with $H = 0$ has no dependence on the choice of f_{te} . Since even this run showed marked departure from usual tilt behavior, I conclude that there is a significant reduction in tilt activity independent of the Hall term for hollow profiles. The inclusion of the Hall term leads to the further conclusion that a point of tilt stability has been reached in (β_{sep}, D) parameter space.

That hollow profiles with high β_{sep} can stabilize the tilt mode is at first surprising. This is emphasized when it is realized that this simulation neglected many aspects of physical FRC behavior that might act as a stabilization mechanism such as large orbit ions.[43] It is known that kinetic stabilization for

small s is possible,[41] By neglecting kinetic effects, these simulations appear to apply to the $s \rightarrow \infty$ limit. However, selected kinetic effects are explicitly re-introduced in the form of viscosity and Hall terms. The question then becomes one of whether the observed stability is ascribable to previous extensions of MHD theory. Variational theory has indicated that if the parameter, $S_* \equiv a\omega_{pi}/c$, is small enough, large elongations may be stabilized. Stability is found for $S_* < C E$, where C is a model depend factor of order unity and E is the plasma elongation. For Hall fluids, $C_{\text{hall}} \approx 1$. [38] For gyroviscous theory $C_{\text{gyro}} \approx 1.6$. [39] However, S_* is not a good figure of merit for assessing hollow profile effects. Two equilibria that have identical external fields, but differing levels of hollowness in their pressure profiles will nevertheless have the same value for S_* , even though $\bar{s}$ may differ radically for the equilibria, since hollowness can drastically alter the value of $|\Psi_0|$. Thus $\bar{s}$ is more appropriate for characterizing equilibria, when pressure profiles have different hollowness values. Equivalently, it can be stated that $\bar{s}$ is preferable to S_* since it considers the effect of midplane averaging in the factor of λ . Table (4.1) lists values of $\bar{s}$ for these runs and Fig. (4.10) graphs $\hat{\gamma}$ versus $\bar{s}$. The trend to stability correlates well with $\bar{s}$. One conclusion it that the effect of hollow profiles is to provide additional stabilization apart from previously considered effects. The fact that the exclusion of the Hall term causes the stable cases to become marginal or even unstable supports this notion.

However, the $H = 0$ runs also show decreased growth rates. This is very interesting, because $H = 0$ implies that all finite Larmor radius effects have been eliminated. $H = 0$ means that the simulation models a pure MHD fluid. Therefore there is a purely fluid effect which reduces tilt mode growth! This

Figure 4.10: Normalized tilt growth rate as a function of $\bar{s}$.

possibility has been noted previously.[51, 97] Moreover, this purely fluid effect seems to scale with macroscopic variables such as trapped flux and separatrix radius in a manner similar to the s scalings associated with beam particle effects and S_* associated with Hall effects. As a small note, viscosity which technically is a finite Larmor radius effect, was still included, varying the viscosity did not affect the results significantly.

The addition of hollowness to this analysis may come in many forms. First, the proportionality constant C may depend on the value of a hollowness parameter. Second, the left side of the relation may be S_*^{eff} , an effective S_* that is corrected for the low internal magnetic field. However, the relationship may be a more complex synergistic relation with various threshold requirements. This study is unable to distinguish between these possibilities. Comparison of

analytic results with computational results is difficult for two additional reasons. First, analytic equilibria and simulation equilibria differ. Second, an initial value simulation will naturally pick the most unstable mode while variational calculations often have limited trial functions. Previous simulation [32] has indicated that for small values of S_* a new, more complex unstable mode emerges. They found that the instability growth rate could not be reduced below about 50% of γ_{tilt} . Such resistance to further reduction in γ may indicate that a new mode is dominating the dynamics. Such may be the case for the hollow, no Hall, simulations presented here.

Experimental comparisons require close examination of equilibrium conditions in order to determine whether comparisons of nominally similar shots are actually comparable. Diagnosis, let alone control, of parameters such as β_{sep} and hollowness is not evident for many experiments. It may depend on details of formation and device specificity. This may explain discrepancies regarding effects of tilt perturbations in current generation, larger s experiments.[34, 44]

While this work suggests that the effect of hollowness is to improve the marginally stable s/E ratio toward shorter elongations and higher s , it cannot be ruled out that its effect on tilt stability may be more complex. This effect is important in FRC reactor analyses.[98] A stable path from formation through compression and heating until ignition must be maintained quasi-statically at all times. During these stages both s and E can vary by factors as much as 3 to 5. Additional stabilization due to hollowness can relax reactor design criteria, allowing easier or more confident paths to ignition.

The implication for beam stabilization is also worth noting. Traditionally, it has been considered that FRC's with large values of s could be stabilized

using energetic ions.[47, 98] Profile stabilization is most effective for moderate to long elongations (as are previous Hall fluid and gyroviscous results). Beam stabilization depends on a resonant condition between the axis encircling frequency and the axial betatron oscillation.[46] Tuning to this resonance requires an increase in betatron frequency by decreasing elongation. When the equilibrium is not tuned to resonance, the critical beam current needed for stabilization increases. Thus profile stabilization and beam stabilization are more effective for different equilibrium characteristics. Whether these conditions are compatible or exclusive must be addressed. That is, do equilibria exist where both effects are strong enough to insure stability or must equilibria be designed for either extremely large or small elongations to take advantage of only one effect in isolation?

Finally, these results for profile stabilization may have consequences in transport analyses. It is often assumed that as experimental devices became larger that β_{sep} would naturally decrease to almost negligible levels. Larger experiments have not observed this trend in β_{sep} . These simulations found the possibility for stability only when hollowness was coupled to high β_{sep} . High β_{sep} may be an inherent co-requisite for stability, or high β_{sep} may simply serve to decrease the $\bar{s}$ of the equilibrium. High β_{sep} implies a need for some form of plasma confinement on the open field lines beyond the separatrix. Moreover, the necessity of maintaining high β_{sep} may dominate the determination of global FRC confinement characteristics. This will necessitate consideration of plasma in the region just beyond the separatrix. It should be noted that hollow current profiles may not be constant on resistive time scales. Current at the field null is small as is the total trapped flux. Therefore hollow profile effects upon τ_{Ψ} ,

the flux lifetime, are not clear. Yet the large currents near the separatrix in hollow profiles point to decreased particle confinement time, τ_n , and resistive evolution towards flatter profiles.

Chapter 5

Induced Spinning in an FRC From Preferentially Trapped Ignition Products

5.1 Motivation

The previous chapters started with an examination of the effects of an energetic beam on the tilt mode. The discussion then digressed to questions of profile modification leading to tilt stability. This chapter will logically refer back to general questions about the behavior of a beam in an FRC. As was noted in Ch. (3), the dynamical behavior will be different for different beam distributions. Ch. (3) discussed idealized beam[47] and realistic modelling of beams out of neutral beam guns. In an advanced fuel FRC reactor, the fusion products themselves may create a beam through preferential trapping.[49]

A fusion product beam will be important in FRC's for several reasons. It will be a source of current drive and plasma heating. It will also affect the plasma equilibrium, and may modify MHD instabilities such as the tilt or rotational modes. This chapter will give a preliminary consideration of one of these problems, beam induced plasma rotation.

At first glance, the plasma is expected to have a toroidal flow because this is the component of the drag force. However, for steady state to be achieved, there must also be some poloidal flow to convect angular momen-

tum from the beam source outward toward the open field lines, as was noted in § (2.9). Another possibility is the existence of an anomalously large viscosity that could transport the angular momentum outward without the need for poloidal flow.

It is interesting to note that while this is a study aimed primarily at FRC's, this issue is more universal. For instance, the question of toroidal rotation is important in the study of neutral beam heating in tokamaks. The beam injection can be strong enough to induce near sonic flows, both in the toroidal and poloidal directions. Spinning tokamak plasma with a divertor X-point may share some common features with a rotating FRC. It is speculated[71] that rapidly spinning, high β tokamaks which contain energetic charged fusion products and whose field contains an X-point may yet a jet flow similar to what is discussed below. If such is the case, then one may be able to use such flows for direct energy extraction in tokamak plasmas much the same as they are proposed for FRC's. Additionally, such flows will help in the efficient removal of ash and heat.

The characteristics of the fusion product beam will be different than the externally injected beam. $f(H, P_\theta)$ will differ in its spatial distribution and energy. The spatial distribution will be governed by the density of the plasma. Since plasma reactivity scales like n^2 , the majority of the beam particles will be born near the field null. Many particle will be born *inside* the field null. Very few externally injected particles penetrated this deep, and the ones that do are not on good orbits. Thus particles will have orbits very different from those observed in the beam gun studies. For instance, for a given H and P_θ , it is possible for a particle to be trapped in an orbit that is rotating in a

direction opposite $\mathbf{j}_p$, the plasma current. Also more likely are orbits that cross the field null, including the so-called "figure eight" orbits.[43] The figure eight orbits can drift in either direction. They also have very large radial extent and other odd features. For example, in one fundamental quasi-period (the orbits are usually not closed), v_θ will change sign 4 times. This is contrasted with v_θ never changing sign for betatron orbits or changing sign twice for drifting orbits. This odd behavior is because figure eight orbits traverse the field null and therefore sample regions where the axial magnetic field has different signs.

The beam will also be more diffuse in (H, P_θ) space. Since the source is a thermonuclear fusion reaction the energy of the particles at birth will vary greatly.[99] This feature is often overlooked. In the center of mass frame of the two colliding particles, the fusion reaction releases a precise amount of energy. Since there are only two products, conservation of momentum along with the equation for total energy release (18.3 MeV for D- ^3He reactions) will determine the center of mass trajectories except for the angle of recoil. However, since almost all fusion reactions are sub-barrier penetration reactions, this angle will be random (in the center of mass frame) One might then be tempted to say that the fusion products will be born with a definite well defined energies and random velocity directions. However, one must convert back to the lab frame. The D- ^3He reaction rate peaks at a temperature of 200 KeV[100]. The common mistake is to assume that this means that the width in energy distribution is 200 KeV. In fact one has to convert the center of mass velocities into lab velocities using a Galilean transformation. This implies that the width in energy distributions scales like twice the geometric mean of the temperature

and the reaction energy yield,

$$\Delta E \approx 2\sqrt{E_y/T}. \quad (5.1)$$

For D-³He reactions at a temperature of 200 KeV, this implies a fractional width in energy, $E/\Delta E, \approx 20\%$. Thus the beam energy is much more diffuse than the output of a beam gun where the potential across the grids is well controlled. Additionally, P_θ of the beam will be determined mainly from the magnetic configuration. That is the fusion process will create particles with random velocity directions. Some will be trapped and some will not. Thus the dependence of f on P_θ will be determined by the point the reaction occurs and the random choice of initial v_θ that determines P_θ . There is a small correction here. If for some reason, the plasma is rotating at large speeds approaching the sound speed, the initial value of P_θ will not be random. This is because the transformation from lab frame to center of mass frame will be highly anisotropic due to large average v_θ . If the rotation rate is near the sound speed, this bias will be of the same order as the width of the Maxwellian. Thus the distribution of the birth values of P_θ will be different for FRC's that are rotating rapidly.

In many ways, making definitive statements about the effects of fusion product beams upon ignited FRC's is very difficult and somewhat speculative, especially because the source of the beam and the determining factor in its capture is given self-consistently from the FRC itself. Since there are no experimental conditions that can mimic this delicate interaction, investigations in this area must be particularly careful to be physically relevant or risk expending effort investigating regimes that are not physically interesting.

This chapter will explore one of the many aspects of ignited beam interaction with the FRC. That aspect is the collisional spin-up of the bulk FRC. To be relevant, the duration of the burn phase in an ignited FRC should be longer than the beam slow-down time. The beam will transfer angular momentum to the bulk FRC plasma. The FRC will adjust to this angular momentum source, and ultimately find a mechanism to shed it. The simulation method will focus on three effects. First, angular momentum source in the plasma from beam deceleration from slowing down collisions. Second, the redistribution of this angular momentum from viscous effects. Third, the re-adjustment of the pressure balance equation to accommodate Bernoulli effects from large scale, large amplitude plasma rotation.

This issue has been explored analytically[67] where fluid ions and electrons were coupled to a kinetic beam. They also considered beam collisional relaxation, viscosity, and 3-dimensional effects such as the interaction with multi-pole magnetic fields. They concluded that the steady-state plasma rotation is determined by the balance of the angular momentum source from the beam and the various angular momentum loss mechanisms. This balance sets limits on FRC reactors, particularly when operated with D-T fuel.

The focus is again on simulation studies since they will not be restricted by mathematical tractability to a small set FRC equilibria. There are several simulational approaches that suggest themselves. The NBF simulation scheme described in Ch. (3)[82, 48] might be used to simulate both the beam and the fluid. However there are many issues that would have to be explored. First a MHD stable configuration must be found for fusion product type beams. Initial beam distributions could be guessed and the extended equilibrium problem

could be solved as was described in Ch. (4) with the addition of the $\mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B}$ term to the Grad-Shafranov formulation. Then these solutions would need to be tested first for orbit confinement and later MHD stability. Finally the time asymptotic beam distribution must be calculated. This asymptotic state will be a result of the combined effects of orbit confinement, MHD stability, and collisional drag and diffusion. Many initial guesses are required in order to test the time asymptotic behavior. Moreover, the collisional effects will act over much longer time scale. Therefore, this activity will either have to be modified to accelerate the computational scheme (for instance by choosing an artificially small collision time and constructing scaling argument to extrapolate to realistic collision times) or would require enormous computational resources. In fact, this problem should be approachable with the techniques presented here. There are also other effects that have been neglected that might be important. For instance the model developed in Ch. (2) neglected the velocity-space diffusion part of the collision operator. Also, anomalous transport effects will probably be required. In any case a simpler preliminary study is in order.

Here a completely fluid simulation method treats the beam quantities as given and fixed. This simplification comes at the expense of beam self-consistency. This is important since the response can potentially be so complex. The model presented in § (2.8) is further simplified by retaining only the beam drag term, $\mathbf{R}_{be}$, in Eq. (2.128). It is a bit curious to retain the $\mathbf{R}_{be}$ term while neglecting the $\mathbf{J}_b$ term which will probably be much larger. This means that the results presented below should not be regarded as experimentally accurate predictions. Rather it is an investigation of the consequences of a particular physical effect, examined in isolation from other physical effects in order to

understand general features about its influence on plasma behavior.

A new transport process is what is under study. In usual transport studies, things such as energy diffusion or particle diffusion are studied. Here the z component of the angular momentum, L_z , is studied. The source is the drag force exerted by the beam upon the plasma. L_z is then transported outward beyond the separatrix by means of viscosity where it can escape axially from divergence of the plasma stress tensor and shear Alfvén waves and is lost from the plasma out the ends.

For a reactor to operate in steady state, an equilibrium must be established. The source function is given by the fusion reactivity. The transport process via viscosity is a consequence of classical collisions and gyromotion. The sink is simply a boundary condition. Classical viscosity coefficients are quite small. If viscosity behaved classically, the interior of the FRC would spin up to very large speeds. This will lead to larger velocity shear that will enhance radial transport of angular momentum. The amplitude of the oscillation in steady state is proportional to the dissipation or loss mechanism.

The advent of large velocity shear brings with it the prospects of other micro-instabilities which will have as one of their effects the generation of anomalously large viscosity coefficients. In this manner the self-regulation mechanism is even more robust. However, it also adds the modelling difficulty that in this truncated description, the exact value for the viscosity coefficient must now be specified externally and is not simply the result of a normal Chapman-Enskog process.

This angular momentum transport process still exists even in the 2-dimensional limit where variation in θ is not allowed. Such an approximation

will eliminate tilt and rotational modes which are not the focus of this chapter.

Previous work on beam stabilization gives some idea about the general behavior of energetic beams. It examined the beam current's modification of the momentum equation. Here the effect of the beam frictional drag on the FRC's momentum is examined. The process begins by examining the effect of a given beam upon the bulk FRC plasma. The next step after this work would be to adjust the estimates of the beam's size and shape to accommodate for the changes in the FRC equilibrium shape.

Physically, this problem is similar to the problem of accretion disks in astrophysics.[101, 102] In astrophysics, the problem concerns a massive body which has a large gravitational attraction. The infall of matter is prevented by the conservation of angular momentum. The transport of angular momentum is the key to understanding the behavior. The physical problem is characterized by a fluid of high density (disk) surrounded by a fluid of lower density (corona). Because of the similarity, astrophysical terminology is used some places here in describing the FRC equilibrium. For instance, the low density plasma region outside the FRC separatrix is a corona, while the plasma inside the separatrix is the disk, etc.

However, there are important differences. The most important is that in the study of star formation or active galactic nuclei, the configuration integrity is supplied by the large gravitational force of the central object while in an FRC, this radial force balance is achieved principally by an external solenoidal coil that creates a magnetic field of enough strength to confine the plasma. This difference is important when it comes to detailed analysis of the behavior of end jets.

5.2 Generalized Grad-Shafranov Problem

One could start with an equilibrium without flow and apply an external driving force and look for a steady-state solution. However, when this was attempted the results were less than satisfactory. The time required to set up a steady flow was longer than some of the decay times (density especially) making it difficult to separate effects from viscosity in a spinning state from the noise of the perturbations. I turned instead to equilibrium formulations whose initial values were already spinning.[103, 104]

The model equations in § (2.8) are further specified for the equilibrium formulation. All beam effects are neglected. Finite resistivity, viscosity, and Hall terms are also neglected in this approximation. Also assume $\partial/\partial t = 0$ since this is the equilibrium (time independent problem). Also make the 2-dimensional approximation by requiring $\partial/\partial \theta = 0$. However, the θ components of vector quantities such as $\mathbf{B}$ and $\mathbf{V}$ are retained.

Since the concern is spinning caused by beam drag, it is expected that the important equilibrium velocity will be in the toroidal direction. While it is possible to include the effects of poloidal flows, it can become a numerically challenging problem because the equilibrium equations can change character from elliptic to hyperbolic if the poloidal Mach number or Alfvén-Mach number exceeds unity.[104] Assume that the equilibrium velocity is given by,

$$\mathbf{V} = v_\theta \hat{\theta} = \omega(r, z) r \hat{\theta}. \quad (5.2)$$

Represent $\mathbf{B}$ by its Clebsch decomposition,

$$\mathbf{B} = \frac{J}{2\pi r} \hat{\theta} - \frac{1}{2\pi r} \hat{\theta} \times \nabla \Psi, \quad (5.3)$$

where $\Psi(r, z)$ is the poloidal flux and J is an as of yet unspecified function that determines the azimuthal component of $\mathbf{B}$.

Then follow a Grad-Shafranov derivation keeping the $\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{v}$ term in the momentum equations. Faraday's law requires,

$$0 = \nabla \times (\mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) = \frac{1}{2\pi} \nabla \omega \times \nabla \Psi. \quad (5.4)$$

This means that ω is a function of Ψ alone, a flux-function; $\omega = \omega(\Psi)$. Similarly, the poloidal component of the momentum equations also requires that, $J = J(\Psi)$.

The toroidal component of the momentum equation becomes,

$$\frac{1}{16\pi^3 r^2} (JJ' + \Delta^* \Psi) \nabla \Psi + \nabla P + \rho \omega^2 r \hat{\mathbf{r}} = 0, \quad (5.5)$$

where $'$ denotes $d/d\Psi$ and $\Delta^* \Psi \equiv \frac{\partial^2 \Psi}{\partial z^2} + r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \frac{1}{r} \frac{\partial \Psi}{\partial r}$, the Grad-Shafranov operator. Define P_r by

$$P_r \equiv P \exp(-\omega^2 r^2 / 2T), \quad (5.6)$$

where $T = P/\rho$ is the plasma temperature. Additionally assume that $T = T(\Psi)$ is a flux function. Eq. (5.5) then reduces to terms of 2 types, terms that are parallel to $\nabla \Psi$ and terms that are parallel to ∇P_r . This implies that $P_r = P_r(\Psi)$ is also a flux function. At that point the equilibrium equation collapses to a nonlinear scalar partial differential equation,

$$JJ' + \Delta^* \Psi + 16\pi^3 r^2 \exp\left(\frac{\omega^2 r^2}{2T}\right) \left[P_r' + P_r r^2 \left(\frac{\omega^2}{2T}\right)' \right] = 0, \quad (5.7)$$

which is the appropriate generalized Grad-Shafranov equation for this study.[103, 104] While some analytic solutions are possible, I will describe numerical solutions of this problem.

5.3 Numerical Equilibrium Solver — FRCEQM

A numerical equilibrium code (completely different from the code used in Ch. (4)) was developed to solve Eq. (5.7). This code is named “FRCEQM”. Given the 4 flux functions, $T(\Psi)$, $P_r(\Psi)$, $J(\Psi)$, and $\omega(\Psi)$, the Grad-Shafranov operator was iteratively inverted using a SOR algorithm with conjugate gradient acceleration.[105, 106]. The solution domain was the upper portion of a cylinder, $0 < r < R_{\max}$, $0 < z < Z_{\max}$. The region with $z < 0$ is determined by requiring Ψ to be symmetric about the midplane, $\Psi(r, -z) = \Psi(r, z)$. This domain was broken into a non-uniform rectangular grid and the Grad-Shafranov differential operator, Δ^* was discretized on a five point stencil. The discretization was second order accurate. For the run presented below, 40 grids in r and 40 grids in z were used.

The boundary condition at $r = 0$ was specified as $\Psi = 0$. The symmetry condition naturally imposes the boundary condition at $z = 0$ of $d\Psi/dz = 0$. The boundaries at $r = R_{\max}$ and $z = Z_{\max}$ can be given by an external Dirichlet condition. However, another choice for these boundaries is the far-field condition. That is the values of $\Psi(R_{\max}, z)$ and $\Psi(r, Z_{\max})$ are given as the integration of all known currents in the system with the appropriate Green’s function kernel. The currents are of two types. The first is a set of externally specific coil currents that are outside the simulation domain. The second is simply a sum over grids in the simulation of the current present during a particular iteration. Since the problem is cylindrically symmetric the Green’s function can be explicitly calculated in terms of elliptic integrals.

The far-field boundary condition introduces a convergence issue. In a usual elliptic solver, the boundary conditions serve to fix the solution. However,

here the boundary conditions are (at least in part) themselves determined by the iterative interior solution. Thus it is possible for both the interior and boundary values to wander away from the desired solution. Of course the nature of this wandering, or whether it even occurs depends also on the choice of the profile functions. Experience with problems has shown that when this effect was present, its most usual course of action was to force the interior and boundary values to a vacuum state, i.e. a state where there is no interior current ($\Delta^*\Psi = 0$). The solution I adopted was to introduce a nested iteration scheme. In the inner iteration, the boundary conditions are held fixed. At the outer iteration loop, the boundary values are adjusted to reflect both the external current and the plasma current. Since the plasma diamagnetic ratio is less than 1, I presumed that this outer iteration would converge. Except for very high rotation rates (discussed below) convergence did occur. Usually the outer iteration loop was repeated only a few times. This is because the external coils were chosen to be near the simulation boundary, so they tended to dominate the values of Ψ at the boundary.

There was also another issue about convergence. Since Eq. (5.7) is a nonlinear equation, there is no guarantee that solutions are unique. In the numerical formulation, this meant that it was not clear beforehand which solution would be a stable attractor for initial guesses and which would be repellers. This is sometimes called the question of the bifurcation of equilibrium solutions.[107, 4] Moreover, often the equilibrium of interest is a repeller for common iteration schemes.[107] In these studies, I was usually looking for a solution with plasma inside the separatrix and little or no plasma outside the separatrix. This meant that I chose $P_r(\Psi)$ to be near 0 when $\Psi < 0$. [Note:

in this chapter, $\Psi > 0$ inside the separatrix while $\Psi < 0$ in the interior of the FRC in Ch. (3) and Ch. (4)] This choice of profile function usually admits at least two kinds of solutions, one (or more) are the solutions of interest while the other is the vacuum solution. The vacuum solution turns out to be a very strong attractor for this profile choice and numerical scheme. This can be seen by looking at a guess for $\Psi(r, z)$ that is close to a non-vacuum equilibrium solution but has a slightly smaller plasma volume. Since the volume is smaller, the total current of the plasma is also a bit too small. This means that in the next iteration, the guess for $\Psi(r, z)$ will be updated to reflect this lower current. That will mean that the plasma volume will decrease even further, leading to a yet smaller current estimate. This feedback proceeds until the solution becomes the vacuum solution. The solution to the convergence problem is to choose a normalizing factor as a prefix for $P_r(\Psi)$. The factor prefix is adjusted at each iteration in order to maintain a constant $\int P_r dv$. This condition then eliminates vacuum solutions and the iteration scheme converges to a solution. Of course there are still open questions about the uniqueness of this non-vacuum solution. Unfortunately, this updating of the normalizing coefficient reduced the convergence rate of the conjugate gradient acceleration.

One final issue was that the convergence of the equilibrium was also adversely affected by very high rotation rates. When the Mach number at the separatrix became much larger than 1, an iterative numerical instability developed. It is similar to a centrifugal force. Suppose the current guess for $\Psi(r, z)$ is very close to a solution, but has a slightly larger plasma volume than the solution. This will lead to more current being present which will tend to drive the total plasma current estimate upwards so that the next iteration will

have even greater size. The normalizing condition on P_r attempts to correct this error, but the physical pressure gradient scales like $P_r \exp(\omega^2 r^2 / 2T)$. As the rotation speeds increase, the exponential behavior becomes too erratic to be tamed by simply renormalizing P_r . This problem is the practical limit on the maximum Mach number obtainable for FRCEQM solutions. I was able to achieve speeds slightly in excess of Mach 1. It may be possible to eliminate this problem by using Dirichlet boundary conditions since the centrifugal expansion would be countered with magnetic compressibility between the separatrix and the flux conserver. Additionally, if the current normalization condition was applied to P instead of P_r it might also help this problem. These avenues have not yet been explored.

5.4 Equilibrium Solutions

In this chapter I will present one particular equilibrium and its evolution from a series of simulations. In some sense it is characteristic of most of the runs, but in other respects it is extreme. For example, all were rotating, but this solution had the fastest rotation. The general characteristic of these equilibria is that the simulation space is broken into three different regions. Region 1 is in the interior of the FRC. It corresponds to the disk in accretion problems. It is characterized by large density, high β , and significant magnetic field gradients. The second region is outside the separatrix. It corresponds to the corona. It is low density, low β . The magnetic gradient scale lengths are longer. The third region is a plasma anchor. It is a high density, low temperature region. It is essentially a "soft wall" simulation boundary. Since one of the effects under study is the generation of end jetting process, the simulation boundary will

need to allow outflows. However, I want those outflows to be directed axially and not radially. Instead of using boundary conditions that embody external forces, I instead choose this high density anchor with an inertial time constant that is fairly long compared to other simulation times-scales.

The profile functions are chosen with these goals in mind. The regions are defined as the interior is for values of $\Psi > 0$. The corona is in the range $\Psi_c < \Psi < 0$ and the anchor is located as Ψ values of $\Psi < \Psi_c$. The different values of the profile functions are quadratically interpolated at the boundary between the regions to give well behaved forces at the interfaces. The interpolation width is given in terms of Ψ since these are flux functions. However, some of the quantities are actually specified by their spatial scale. For instance $\Psi_c \equiv \Psi(r_a, z_a)$ where r_a and z_a are input coordinates for a point on the edge of the anchor. Thus in the iterative equilibrium solution, the input is the location of the anchor and not the value of Ψ_c . Likewise, the interpolating coefficients are determined by specifying the boundary thickness at the midplane in terms of r . This will then serve to define interpolation coefficients in terms of Ψ that can be used in the profile functions.

The particular choices of the profile functions for the run presented below are:

$$J(\Psi) = 0, \quad (5.8)$$

$$\omega(\Psi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \omega_0 \text{ interior} \\ 0 \text{ corona, anchor} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (5.9)$$

$$P_r(\Psi) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \alpha\Psi \text{ interior} \\ P_{\text{COR}} \text{ corona, anchor} \end{array} \right\}, \quad (5.10)$$

and

$$T(\Psi) = \begin{cases} T_{\text{int}} & \text{interior} \\ T_{\text{cor}} & \text{corona} \\ T_{\text{anc}} & \text{anchor} \end{cases}. \quad (5.11)$$

Pick $T_{\text{anc}} \ll T_{\text{int}} < T_{\text{cor}}$, $P_{\text{max}} \gg P_{\text{cor}}$ and $r_s \omega_0 / C_s \sim 1$. These profiles give an FRC that is spinning on the interior but not on the outside. The rotation rate at the separatrix is $\omega_0 r_s$, which is close to Mach 1 for the equilibrium shown below. The interior rotation is a rigid rotation. The pressure peaks at the O-point and falls off to a minimum value in the corona. The corona is hotter than the interior. The anchor is much colder than either.

Before giving actual numbers, let me define the normalization of units for all of the quantities that follow. The physical quantities are represented in the computer in (unitless) normalized units. Conversion to physical units requires multiplication by the physical units. Therefore,

$$f = \tilde{f} \hat{f}, \quad (5.12)$$

where f is some physical quantity (in cgs units, for instance), $\hat{f}$ is the dimensional normalization of f , and $\tilde{f}$ is the normalized value of f . The numbers in the computer correspond to $\tilde{f}$ and therefore must be multiplied by $\hat{f}$ to get physical values.

There are three fundamental dimensional units that define the length scales of the simulation, $\hat{L}$, $\hat{B}$, and $\hat{M}$. These normalization values are chosen such that $\hat{L} = r_w$, the radius of the radial wall, $\hat{B} = \max\{B\}$, and $\hat{M} = \max\{\rho\} \hat{L}^3$, where the maxima are taken over the entire simulation region. Other physical dimensions such as velocity or time can be derived from these fundamental units in accordance with the dynamical equations (detailed below

in Eq. (5.14)-Eq. (5.17)). It should be noted that factors of 2π are not absorbed into the normalizations, but remain in the normalized equations.

$\hat{M}$ and $\hat{B}$ are designed such that $\max\{\hat{\rho}\} = 1$ and $\max\{\hat{B}\} = 1$. However, the iterative solver will not automatically assure that these restrictions are observed. Therefore, after convergence has been achieved, the simulation variables have to be renormalized to obey these conditions. This renormalization procedure gives $\max\{\hat{\rho}\} = 1$ and $\max\{\hat{B}\} = 1$. At the same time, the other physical variables are also renormalized in order to ensure that the Grad-Shafranov equation, Eq. (5.7), remains invariant under renormalization. Therefore, the initial values for some of the profile parameters in Eq. (5.8)-Eq. (5.11) are re-adjusted at the end of the equilibrium solver. For the profile choices, the various parameters, after renormalization, are as follows; $\omega_0 = 1.28$, $\alpha = 0.312$, $P_{\text{COR}} = 0.00483$, $T_{\text{int}} = 0.291$, $T_{\text{COR}} = 0.00483$, and $T_{\text{anc}} = 0.581$. The last set of parameters of the edge width of the interpolation regions. I choose $r_{\text{edge}} = 0.1$ since there are 40 grid points in r and z , this means that there are 4 grid points in the interpolation region at each boundary. Finally, the position of the edge of the anchor is $r = 0.85$, $z = 0.75$. That is, $\Psi_c = \Psi(0.85, 0.75)$.

There are 6 external coils. Their positions and currents are shown in Table (5.1). The coils are modeled as point loops. That is the entire current is presumed to flow in an infinitely thin wire that is azimuthally symmetric. The coil currents are in code normalized units, which have been renormalized. For this run, the renormalization correction was $\approx 17\%$. The coils are placed outside of the simulation regions symmetrically in z .

While the dimensionalizations are important for comparison to experimental parameters, the dynamical behavior is governed by various non-dimen-

r	z	I
1.25	-0.4103	-0.0150
1.25	-0.3589	-0.0450
1.25	-0.3077	-0.0150
1.25	-0.3077	-0.0150
1.25	-0.3589	-0.0450
1.25	-0.4103	-0.0150

Table 5.1: External Coil Placement and Strength (in Code Normalized Units).

sional ratios, or figures of merit, such as Alfvén velocity in code normalized units compared to rotational velocity, etc. Below, in the discussion of the dynamical model, the values for these figures are given.

Fig. (5.1)-Fig. (5.4) are contour plots of this particular equilibrium. These plots show the region, $0 < r < r_w$, $0 < z < z_w$. In code normalized units $z_w = r_w = 1$. Fig. (5.5) show contours of the local Mach number. The maximum is 0.72 just inside the separatrix. Fig. (5.6) plots the local Alfvén velocity. The axes numbers go from 0 to 40. These are grid indices and not physical or code dimensions. The grid spacing is a length of 0.0025 in code normalized units. It can be seen that the Alfvén velocity is highest in the corona. This is because the magnetic field is strong and the density is small. V_A is smaller in the interior because the density is high and the magnetic field strength is smaller. V_A is very small in the anchor because the density is so high. This equilibrium differs from experimentally observed equilibria. First it has a short elongation. Second the rotation is very large. These two characteristics will combine to give the end jet a nozzle since the magnetic pressure varies in z . The external coils reinforce this effect because of a substantial mirror ratio. The short equilibria will also reduce the axial Alfvén transit time. The fast rotation

Figure 5.1: Equilibrium Poloidal Flux Contours.

Figure 5.2: Equilibrium Pressure Contours.

Figure 5.3: Equilibrium Toroidal Velocity (V_θ) Contours.

Figure 5.4: Equilibrium Density Contours.

Figure 5.5: Equilibrium Local Mach Number (V_{θ}/C_s).

Figure 5.6: equilibrium Local Alfvén Velocity, V_A .

will decrease the rotation time. This is important because it is desirable for the rotation time and axial transit time to be short compared to the viscous delay time. However, viscous decay time should be short compared to the total simulation time. Therefore there is some need to artificially compress these ratios. Naturally, care should be given when attempting to quantitatively extrapolate the results of this particular equilibrium to all classes of FRC's of interest.

5.5 Dynamical Formulation

The numerical equilibrium computed with FRCEQM is used for the initial values for a dynamical simulation. The physical model is similar to that presented in § (2.8) with a few modifications. All explicit beam terms are neglected. A beam-like term is re-introduced in the form of an external force. That the $\mathbf{R}_{be}$, the beam friction force in Eq. (2.128) is replaced by an externally specified external force, $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$. The $\mathbf{J}_b$ effects are completely neglected. Of course the $\mathbf{J}_b$ terms are very important and should not be neglected in a final accurate simulation, but the thrust here is to investigate the dynamical interplay between an external force, viscosity, and outflow in an FRC. While not physically realistic, it is instructional in building intuition about plasma behavior.

Additionally, a $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} \cdot \mathbf{V}$ term is added to the energy equation, Eq. (2.129). We had previously neglected this term since it was formally higher order in the perturbation analysis of Ch. (2). However, in this work, the external force and the viscosity are of primary importance. Therefore this term will need to be re-included in order to conserve energy and to explore how energy is transferred among the different energy forms (kinetic energy, internal energy, and electro-

magnetic energy) along the different transfer channels (Poynting flux, viscous heating, resistive heating, adiabatic compression, and external forcing).

Additionally, the equations of motion are written in a flux conservative form since the numerical procedure described below will use this feature as an integral part of its algorithm. "Flux conservative form" means that time derivatives are expressed as partial derivatives and that all of the other terms are absorbed into terms that are expressed as the divergence of a flux where possible. Each dynamical equation will have a canonical form of,

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} f^i = -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} H^i - \frac{\partial}{r \partial \theta} D^i - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} G^i - L^i, \quad (5.13)$$

where the i superscript runs from 1 to 8 for each of the dynamical equations for the 8 dynamical variables; $\mathbf{V}$, $\mathbf{B}$, P , and ρ . Actually, when the equations are placed in flux conservative form, the dynamical variables also change to momentum, magnetic field, energy, and density. $\mathbf{V}$ and P are recovered from the expressions for momentum and energy, respectively.

The resulting dynamical equations are:[108, 109]

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \rho = -\nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{V}), \quad (5.14)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \mathbf{V}) = & -\nabla \cdot \left(\rho \mathbf{V} \otimes \mathbf{V} - \frac{1}{4\pi} \mathbf{B} \otimes \mathbf{B} - \mu \nabla \otimes \mathbf{V} \right) - \\ & \nabla \cdot \left(P + \frac{1}{8\pi} B^2 - \frac{1}{3} \mu \nabla \cdot \mathbf{V} \right) + \mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}, \end{aligned} \quad (5.15)$$

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \mathbf{B} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{V} \times \mathbf{B}) - \nabla \times \left[\frac{c^2 \eta}{4\pi} (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \right], \quad (5.16)$$

and

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t} \left(\frac{1}{8\pi} B^2 + \frac{1}{\gamma-1} P + \frac{1}{2} \rho V^2 \right) = -\nabla \cdot \left\{ \left(\frac{\gamma}{\gamma-1} P + \frac{1}{2} \rho v^2 \right) \mathbf{V} - \right.$$

$$\frac{1}{4\pi}\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{B}\cdot\mathbf{V}) + \frac{c^2\eta}{4\pi}\left[-\nabla\left(\frac{1}{8\pi}B^2\right) + \nabla\cdot\left(\frac{1}{4\pi}\mathbf{B}\otimes\mathbf{B}\right)\right]\} + \mathbf{V}\cdot\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}, \quad (5.17)$$

μ is a hydrodynamic viscosity, as it was in Ch. (3) and Ch. (4), but its interpretation is quite different. The large rotation of the interior of the FRC is coupled to the non-rotating exterior leads to large velocity shear. It is quite reasonable to expect that the large local reservoir of free energy will excite small wavelength modes, such as Kelvin-Helmholtz modes, that will lead to a turbulently fluctuating fluid, at least near the separatrix. However, in some cases, the existence of a velocity shear layer may stabilize some classes of MHD modes.[110] Here enhanced instability is assumed to be the case. μ is externally specified at the start of the simulation, but according to these intuitive notions. It will be large near the separatrix and smaller away from it. It is chosen as,

$$\mu \equiv \frac{\mu_0}{1 + (\Psi/\Psi_{\text{norm}})^2}. \quad (5.18)$$

Ψ_{norm} is chosen such that $\mu(\Psi = 0)/\mu(\Psi = \Psi_{\text{max}}) = R_\mu$, a given viscosity contrast ratio. For the equilibrium under studied, $\mu_0 = 0.0007874$ and $R_\mu = 194.9$, after renormalization. Fig. (5.7) shows a contour plot of μ . As can be seen, the viscosity is largest at the separatrix. However, it is also large in those regions where Ψ is near 0, such as the symmetry axis and the spindle point. It is about 1/2 of its maximum value at the O-point.

The other addition is the external force, $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$. $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ is designed to be a crude model of the beam drag force as a driving term. If I choose $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} = 0$, then the FRC will spin down. The viscosity will act to spin up the external field lines but this will occur at the expense of decelerating the interior. A second choice would be to set $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} = -\mathbf{F}_\mu = -\left[\nabla\cdot(\mu\nabla\otimes\mathbf{V}) + \frac{1}{3}\nabla(\mu\nabla\cdot\mathbf{V})\right]$

Figure 5.7: Contours of viscosity coefficient, μ .

This particular choice will preserve the equilibrium condition. The equilibrium formulation described in § (5.2) does not include either viscous effects or the external force. This choice for the external force allows the verification of the equilibrium solution and discretization of viscous force. This is possible because choosing $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} = -\mathbf{F}_{\mu}$ maintains the condition of $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho\mathbf{V}) = 0$, at least initially. Such checks have been performed. The initial accelerations are verified to be small, even though the viscosity gradients and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ are localized to only a few gridpoints.

Although choosing $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} = -\mathbf{F}_{\mu}$ allows testing of the simulation integrity, it is not a good model of the physical problem under focus. That is because the viscous force acts to spin down the plasma in the interior but acts to spin up the exterior. If $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} = -\mathbf{F}_{\mu}$ then the external force acts to *decelerate* the spinning in the corona. Therefore, for the dynamical run presented here, I

Figure 5.8: External Force Contours, F_θ .

will choose,

$$\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}} \equiv \max\{0, -\mathbf{F}_\mu\}. \quad (5.19)$$

This will allow the external force to act to oppose the slowing down of the internal rotation, allowing the external field lines to spin up from viscous forces without hindrance. Fig. (5.8) shows contours of $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ at $t = 0$. Both $\mu(\Psi)$ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ are static. That is they are not functions of $\Psi(t)$ but rather functions of $\Psi(t = 0)$. This allows their initial calculation. However, $\mathbf{F}_\mu$ is time dependent since it depends on the velocity which does vary dynamically. Therefore, even though $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ does exactly balance $\mathbf{F}_\mu$ initially, as time progresses and the velocity changes, there will be some net force. However, if μ and $\mathbf{F}_{\text{ext}}$ are followed dynamically, there are potential problems. The force involves second derivatives. So small fluctuations can get magnified into rather large numerical forces. This problem is surmountable by use of larger grid-sets and spatial

filtering, but these techniques have not yet been implemented. There are also other issues. For instance, if F_{ext} was dynamically chosen to cancel F_{μ} at all times everywhere in the separatrix, then as the system spun up, the separatrix would enlarge due to centrifugal force. As it enlarged, the total external power would increase, etc. Thus the simulation would be unstable because of the manner in which F_{ext} was modelled. This would not be physical. Since the physical motivator of this effect is a fusion product beam, its drag force would not grow exponentially. It appears that if one wishes to do more sophisticated modelling than is presented here, the first step will be to more adequately model the energetic beam drag force in a manner that can vary dynamically, but is not subject to unphysical model artifacts dominating the behavior.

This then sets up the stage for analysis of the source, transport, and sink of angular momentum.

5.6 Numerical Dynamical Solver — FRCJET

Eq. (5.14)-Eq. (5.17) are numerically solved using a modified 2-step Lax-Wendroff algorithm with artificial viscosity.[84] The simulation is 2-dimensional in cylindrical coordinates. Variation is allowed in r and z , but no variation in θ is allowed. Again the 2-dimensional grid is 40×40 .

In cylindrical coordinates, the vector differential operators, $\nabla \cdot$, $\nabla \times$, and ∇ acting on a vector, have terms that have a $1/r$ dependence. In this code, such terms are explicitly separated from the H^i terms in Eq. (5.13) and placed into the L^i terms. The finite difference operators are also modified to be well behaved at $r \sim 0$. Additionally, the boundary at $r = 0$ imposes conditions on some quantities. For instance, any variable that appears in an L^i term

multiplied by $1/r$ must go to 0 at $r = 0$ or else a singularity develops in the simulation region. Additionally, the r -components of $\mathbf{V}$ and $\mathbf{B}$ must vanish as $r \rightarrow 0$. Finally, some values are evaluated as $0/0$ at $r = 0$. These values are extrapolated from the values at small r . This extrapolation is subject to large fluctuation. Therefore the extrapolation scheme to $r = 0$ was low order. It was a blend of 0'th order and 1'st order extrapolation.

The boundary conditions at $z = 0$ are determined by symmetry conditions of the dynamical equations, Eq. (5.14)-Eq. (5.17). For specific parity choices of the dynamical variables, the equations are invariant under the transformation, $z \rightarrow -z$. In fact there is more than one symmetry choice. However, the equilibria of interest have even parity in Ψ . This determines the parity relations for the components of $\mathbf{B}$. By requiring parity invariance of the dynamical equations the specific parity (even or odd) of the other dynamical variables can be derived. The required parities of externally specified quantities such as μ and F_{est} can also be inferred.

The boundary conditions at $r = r_w$ and $z = z_w$ are a bit more complex. Energy outflow is allowed which leads to the choice of free boundaries. This scheme is implemented in both r and z . When there is a strong flow out of the boundaries, the boundary conditions do not have much effect on the interior region of the simulation. However, the initial equilibrium used here has no initial poloidal flow. This means that numerical noise, at least initially, can conspire to cause a net inflow of velocity from the boundary regions. This inflow will convect new information from outside of the simulation region. Any such quantities are necessarily noise, since no such information is available in the equilibrium. It is possible for the inward convection to cause a numerical

instability. This was found to be a severe limitation in initial simulations. An inflow would be generated that would eventually lead to inflow speeds that were close to the Alfvén velocity.

Two measures were taken to correct this problem. First, the boundary conditions on $\mathbf{B}$ were adjusted from free boundary to a free boundary with the restriction that $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ to machine accuracy.[111] Use has been made of the identity $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ in the derivation of Eq. (5.14)-Eq. (5.17). If $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} \neq 0$ then there will be a non-physical force. This force will cause large spurious flows even when the error in $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ is only truncation error. In the interior this was not a problem since the stencil automatically respected this requirement. At the boundary, however, one-sided stencils were used that did not necessarily insure this.

Even when $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ was enforced at the boundary, there was still a numerical inflow. It was concentrated near $z = z_w$. The spurious flow at $r = r_w$ was suppressed considerably owing to the large inertia of the plasma anchor. This problem was reduced by implementing damping boundary conditions in the end region.[112] The canonical dynamical equation, Eq. (5.13), was modified to add a damping term,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial}{\partial t} f^i &= -\frac{\partial}{\partial r} H^i - \frac{\partial}{r \partial \theta} D^i - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} G^i - \frac{\partial}{\partial z} L^i - \alpha(z) (f^i - \bar{f}^i) \\ &= \left. \frac{\partial}{\partial t} f^i \right)_{\text{physical}} - \alpha(z) (f^i - \bar{f}^i), \end{aligned} \quad (5.20)$$

where

$$\alpha(z) \equiv \alpha_0 \exp \left[\frac{-(z - z_w)^2}{d_n^2} \right], \quad (5.21)$$

and $\bar{f}^i$ is a historically averaged value for f^i . In theory this is a filtered output of all values of f^i at all previous values. The choice of filter is yet to be

specified. The effect of $\alpha(z)$ is to damp out initial numerical noise in the end region. Additionally, it helps with the outgoing boundary conditions. It is very difficult to express *a priori* conditions to insure perfect wave absorbing boundary conditions. There will be some impedance mismatch at the numerical boundary that will partially reflect outgoing waves and set up standing wave structures due to the boundary conditions. However, the damping zone will serve to decrease this effect. As a wave travels through the zone it will be dampened. Therefore, the reflected portion of outgoing waves will tend to dissipate. The input variables to specify α are the damping factor, d_f , the scale over which the wave is dampened by d_f , d_m , and the damping scale length, d_n . A wave disturbance traveling at $\Delta r/\Delta t$ (i.e. one grid per time step, the absolute maximum wave speed consistent with CFL stability) will be dampened to d_f of its original value from when it crosses $z_w - d_m$ until it passes $z_w - d_m$ after reflection. Thus if the wave is completely reflected, it will damp by d_f . However, the free boundary at $z = z_w$ will actually transmit most of the wave, so the actual composite reflection coefficient will be even less. There are some choices that must be made in choosing these parameters. It would be nice to have d_f as near as possible to 0 and d_n also near 0. However, this limit is simply a fixed boundary which is perfectly reflecting. One needs to be careful that the damping zone is not too severe or too short. If it is, waves will be reflected off of the damping zone itself. For the run presented below, I chose $d_f = 0.9$, $d_n = 0.25$, and $d_m = 0.125$. A small calculation reveals that α_0 should be chosen according to,

$$\alpha_0 = \frac{-\ln d_f}{d_m \sqrt{\pi} \operatorname{erf}(d_n/d_m)}, \quad (5.22)$$

where erf is the error function, Gaussian integral.

In addition to reducing numerical noise in the end regions and damping outgoing waves, the damping zone also causes a weak pinning of the dynamical functions to their historical values. That is the effect of the $\alpha(z) (f^i - \bar{f}^i)$ term in Eq. (5.20) is to (gently) force f^i towards $\bar{f}^i$. Therefore the choice of $\bar{f}^i$ is important. $\bar{f}^i$ depends on the history of f^i . I will assume that this dependence is linear. Therefore, the most general expression for $\bar{f}^i(t)$ is a Volterra integral,

$$\bar{f}^i(t) = \int_{t_0}^t dt' G(t, t') f^i(t'). \quad (5.23)$$

$G(t, t')$ is the historical interpolating function. I will choose $G(t, t')$ to depend on a parameter, δ . It will have two parts. The first is $G(t, t') = \delta \exp[-\delta(t - t_0)]$. The second part involves a Dirac-delta function that will give the initial value. This is needed since the Volterra integral does not proceed all the way to $-\infty$ but instead starts at t_0 , the start of the simulation. The net result is,

$$\bar{f}^i(t) = \delta \int_{t_0}^t dt' e^{-\delta(t-t')} f^i(t') + e^{-\delta(t-t_0)} f^i(t_0). \quad (5.24)$$

If $\delta = 0$, then $\bar{f}^i(t) = f^i(t_0)$. The limit as $\delta \rightarrow \infty$ gives $\bar{f}^i(t) = f^i(t)$. This filtering scheme has a simple discrete approximation. At each time step $\bar{f}^i(t)$ is updated according to,

$$\bar{f}^i(t)_{\text{new}} = \delta \Delta t f^i_{\text{new}} + (1 - \delta \Delta t) \bar{f}^i(t)_{\text{old}}. \quad (5.25)$$

In the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, Eq. (5.25) becomes Eq. (5.24). This damping function is simply a low pass filter with linear roll-off. This can be seen in a simple analytic calculation where $f^i(t) = \exp(i\omega t)$. The filtered function becomes,

$$\bar{f}^i(t) = \frac{\delta}{\delta + i\omega} f^i(t) + \frac{i\omega}{\delta + i\omega} f^i(t_0) \exp[-\delta(t - t_0)]. \quad (5.26)$$

For $t \gg t_0$, this implies that $\bar{f}^i(t)$ is close to $f^i(t)$ for low frequency motion, but for high frequency motion, $\bar{f}^i(t)$ is very small.

The proper choice for δ should be smaller than the frequency of the outgoing waves. This issue is worth of considerable attention. Although it has been implemented, I have not yet explored the consequences of varying the damping parameter extensively in physically meaningful cases. For the simulation results in this chapter, I have chosen $\delta = 0$.

5.7 Dynamical Simulation Results

Given the equilibrium described in § (5.4) and the viscosity and external force described in § (5.5) the simulation was integrated in time using the FRCJET code-set. The purpose was to look for steady-state configurations that included viscosity and external forces. The simulation ended as $t = 7.08$, in code normalized units. This time is only meaningful when it is compared to figures of merit for the simulation. Table (5.2) shows the value of some of the figures of merit. The end of the simulation, $t = 7.08$, was ≈ 35 axial Alfvén wave transit times. It is reasonable to expect that an axially equilibration of the magnetic field has occurred. The viscosity will spin up the magnetic fields and set up shear Alfvén waves propagating axially. By $t = 7.08$ this situation should have reached a steady state. At steady state the Poynting flux in the axial directions has not returned to 0, rather it has settled into an almost time independent state.

The situation is different for the viscous decay time. The simulation ends after only ~ 2 viscous decay times. Therefore, it is not reasonable to expect that the viscous modifications to the equilibrium are complete, although, the general effects should be discernible. This highlights one of the current limitations of the FRCJET code-set. $T_\mu \gg T_A$ is required in order to separate

Quantity	Symbol	Definition	Value
Viscous Decay Time at Separatrix	T_μ	$\rho_{\text{sep}} r_{\text{edge}}^2 / \mu_{\text{sep}}$	3.3
Alfvén Wave Transit Time, Midplane to Damping Zone Through Corona	T_A	L_z / V_A	0.2
Rotation Time	T_θ	$2\pi / \omega_0$	4.9
Reynolds Number at Separatrix	R_{sep}	$\rho_{\text{sep}} r_{\text{edge}} v_\theta / \mu_{\text{sep}}$	8.8
Separatrix Radius	r_{sep}		0.5
Separatrix Length	z_{sep}		0.75
Wall Radius	r_{wall}		1.0
Damping Zone Location	z_{damp}		0.75

Table 5.2: Figures of Merit for Viscous Jet Simulation (In Code Normalized Units).

viscous and wave propagation time scales. However, $T_{\text{end}} \gg T_\mu$ is also needed. Either the T_{end} must be increased or T_μ should be reduced. However, the reason the simulation ends is that flow patterns and end-jetting develops to such an extent that at some point in the simulation, the density drops to near 0. At that point, the time-step converges to zero and the simulation ends. In order to reduce T_μ , μ must be increased. However, this will simply act to decrease T_{end} since the flow and jetting will now occur even faster. The other alternative is to decrease r_{edge} . However this will require the run to increase the number of grids in order to resolve the interpolation more accurately. This means that this compression of time-scale problem can only be solved by increasing computational complexity. Somewhat larger simulations are feasible with present day supercomputers, but at some point it will become problematic.

Another issue affecting the results shown here is that the characteristic

Figure 5.9: Poloidal Flux Contours at End of Simulation.

width of the damping zone extends all of the way to Z_{sep} . In future work, it would be beneficial to separate the damping region from the region of dynamical interest.

Fig. (5.15)-Fig. (5.20) show the volume integrated energy for each form. Fig. (5.9)-Fig. (5.14) show the state of the plasma at the end of the simulation. When compared to the initial states, a few features emerge. First a significant velocity has developed in the poloidal plane, Fig. (5.13). It is principally directed out of the simulations as an axial jet. Its magnitude is a significant fraction of both the sound velocity and the Alfvén velocity. It is over 50% of the initial peak sound velocity, and is over 20% of the maximum Alfvén velocity at $t = 0$.

A second feature is that the rotation has actually increased. This is explained by the fact that the original rotation is being supported by the external

Figure 5.10: Pressure Contours at End of Simulation.

Figure 5.11: Toroidal Velocity, V_θ , Contours at End of Simulation.

Figure 5.12: Density Contours at End of Simulation.

Figure 5.13: Poloidal Velocity Vectors at End of Simulation.

Figure 5.14: Poloidal Current Vectors at End of Simulation.

Figure 5.15: Magnetic Energy Contained in Toroidal Magnetic Fields as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.16: Total Magnetic Energy as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.17: Kinetic Energy on Toroidal Motion as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.18: Kinetic Energy in Poloidal Motion as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.19: Thermal (Internal) Energy as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.20: Total Energy as a Function of Time.

force, F_{ext} which is a source of rotational energy. Fig. (5.17) shows that the total rotational energy has increased about 25%, although, it was even larger around $t = 4$. There is a competition between external force input of power and viscous dissipation. Initially, the source is stronger than the sink. This leads to a spin-up. The higher velocity shear then leads to increased viscous dissipation. Toward the end of the simulation both the kinetic energy in toroidal motion and the input and output powers are decreasing simply because much of the plasma has evacuated the FRC from the strong axial flow. Even though a strong axial jet has formed, most of the kinetic energy is still concentrated in rotational motion, Fig. (5.17) and Fig. (5.18) The last thing to note about the rotational feature is that the region of highest velocity has moved from the original O-point axially outwards. That is the central O-point has bifurcated into 2 teardrops. It has also moved to a smaller radius. This seems to be an

effect of the field line curvature from the low elongation equilibrium. The flow appears to be roughly following a path that is parallel to the magnetic field lines, Fig. (5.9).

The third feature to note is that the convection coupled with the increased spinning has modified the plasma pressure greatly as seen in Fig. (5.10). The peak pressure has decreased by a factor of 2. The volume integrated thermal energy has decreased 15%, Fig. (5.19). Energy has been added to the thermal motion by viscous heating and to a smaller extent, adiabatic compression. The major loss of thermal energy has been through end jetting. In fact, by the end of the simulation, as much thermal energy has been ejected axially as remains in the simulation. One can ask whether this effect is real. There are two explanations. First, a physical jet may be developing that is similar to accretion disk jets. The second is that there is a lot of energy being dumped into the thermal energy channel which has no effective dumping mechanism except expansion and flux out of the simulation domain. Thus the observed motion may just be an artifact of heating the plasma and watching it expand. While this simulation cannot determine which is the case for this run, it is most likely a combination of both. One way to settle this question would be to repeat a series of runs with different viscosities. The viscosity heating scales with the coefficient of viscosity, but the jetting, if physical, should only be slightly affected. That is the time until the jet is well formed will be extended, but the steady-state, time asymptotic jet should not depend sensitively on the viscosity.

The fourth feature worthy of mention is that, as expected, a significant B_θ has been generated. The generation of B_θ can intuitively be understood

as an effect of frozen flow coupled to plasma motion. Inside the separatrix, each magnetic field line intersects the midplane twice, once inside the O-point and once outside of it. Initially, the plasma inside the separatrix was rotating rigidly. Therefore each magnetic field line simply rotates along with the plasma without distortion. However, after the simulation begins, the relation $\omega = \omega(\Psi)$ is not true because of dynamic effects. Different parts of each magnetic field line are rotating with different angular frequencies. A magnetic field that initially lies only in the poloidal plane will be twisted so that it has some extent in θ . This means $B_\theta \neq 0$. This can also be seen by closely examining the structure of Faraday's equation for this flow situation in Eq. (5.16). The situation on the exterior field lines is similar. Initially, the fluid in the corona is not in motion. As the simulation proceeds, viscous diffusion of angular momentum causes the fluid beyond the separatrix near the midplane to also begin rotating. However, the field lines at large $\pm z$ are still not spinning. Thus some B_θ is generated. As time progresses, this B_θ will propagate axially. This is similar to shear-Alfvén wave. Physically, as $t \rightarrow \infty$ one would expect $B_\theta \rightarrow 0$. However, the damping zone boundary condition effectively pins the exterior magnetic field lines to their initial values.

Fig. (5.21) shows the θ component of the magnetic field at the end of the simulation. The peak value of B_θ is about 1/2 of the peak value of the poloidal magnetic field. However, B_θ tends to be large in regions where B_{poloidal} is small. The sign of B_θ can be understood by examining plots for v_θ , Fig. (5.11). $B_\theta < 0$ in regions where v_θ is smaller in the midplane than at larger values of z . This means that that portion at large z is pulled forward in θ . Likewise, the region where the midplane is rotating faster than larger values of z generates

Figure 5.21: Toroidal Magnetic Field at End of Simulation.

B_θ of the opposite sign. Of course the values of B_θ carry information not just about the instantaneous values of v_θ , but also some historical summary, since Eq. (5.16) implies that B_θ is actually a time integral of the velocity. Finally, the sign of B_θ is also modulated by the sign of B_z . When B_z reverses sign, so does B_θ . This can be understood by the fact that the transformation, $B_r \rightarrow -B_r$ together with $B_z \rightarrow -B_z$ will have the same set of poloidal field lines. However the arrow attached to them will be reversed. Therefore, this transformation also implies $B_\theta \rightarrow -B_\theta$.

Fig. (5.22) shows an integration of 5 exterior magnetic field lines. Two views are presented Fig. (5.22)a shows an end on view of the field lines in the x - y plane. The lines at large radius do not have much bending out of the $\theta = 0$ plane. However, the field line near the separatrix does have some twisting. It reaches a maximum θ value of $\sim 45^\circ$ at the midplane. Because B_θ is anti-symmetric about the midplane, the field line reverses its motion in the x - y

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.22: Integrated Exterior Field Lines viewed; (a) end-on in $x-y$ plane and (c) projected in $x-z$ plane.

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.23: Integrated Interior Field Lines viewed; (a) end-on in x - y plane and (b) projected in x - z plane.

plane and exits axially with $\theta = 0$ again. Fig. (5.22)b shows the projection of the field lines onto the x - z plane. The slight twisting can be seen, especially for the field line nearest to the separatrix.

The interior field lines are twisted much more significantly. This is shown in Fig. (5.23). Again panels a and b show views of these field lines in the x - y plane and the x - z plane, respectively. A considerable B_θ has been generated in a region where the poloidal magnetic field is quite small. In this region, the magnetic field lines are almost completely toroidal. This region spans most of the upper region of the FRC. Therefore, if one wishes to trace any field line

inside the separatrix from a midplane starting point outside of the O-point until it passes through the midplane again inside the O-point, that path will take it through the region where $B_{\text{poloidal}} \ll B_{\theta}$. Therefore it will have many twists. The total number of twists will vary with the maximum strength of B_{θ} and the minimum strength of B_{poloidal} along a given flux surface. This can be seen more clearly in Fig. (5.23)b. One might ask why the interior field lines twisted to such an extent while the exterior lines are only mildly twisted. The answer is not that B_{θ} is different in magnitude. Rather it is a consequence of the fact that B_{poloidal} becomes vanishingly small near the spindle point.

However, the integrated field lines shown here should only be taken as an indication of the dynamical behavior. This is because by the end of the simulation, the separatrix has moved into the damping zone. Therefore the magnetic field's evolution is fairly unphysical from the effects of the damping term in Eq. (5.20). The damping may create regions where the poloidal magnetic field becomes zero at a point besides the spindle point. Particularly, the damping term causes $\nabla \cdot \mathbf{B} = 0$ to be violated. So the field integrated field lines converge at this late time in the simulation. Physically, twisting is expected, but probably not as extreme as these plots indicate.

Another interesting feature is in the neck of the FRC. Fig. (5.13) and Fig. (5.14) show that there is an axially inward directed flow and current inside the separatrix. I believe that this is explainable as an ancillary effect of the normal axial jet generation. Normally a jet develops axial flow from plasmas moving parallel to the magnetic field. Usually this flow is on the exterior of the separatrix. However, with the large viscosity used in this simulation, this exterior jet also tends to drag some poloidal flow in the region just inside the

separatrix. Thus a flow is set up which runs from r_s to z_s . At that point it hits the symmetry axis much like a jet of water hitting a wall. Some of the plasma flows in the positive z direction and some flows in the negative z direction. The positive flow is added to the general axial jet. The negative flow forms this feature in the neck of the FRC. This interior poloidal flow will also convect other quantities. This explains why the toroidal flow has moved to smaller radius at the end of the run, Fig. (5.11). With the rotational flow becoming tighter, the angular rotation becomes larger and more sheared. This feeds the dynamo action that is creating B_θ . Now $B_\theta(r = 0) = 0$ necessarily. Therefore, a large current is directed axially toward the midplane. The return part of this current comes from outwardly directed radial current at the midplane. There also may be some current that crosses the separatrix. While this behavior seems reasonable. It is still open to interpretation and further study. It seems that this effect will be smaller if the viscosity is not so large, which is probably physical. Also, if the equilibrium elongation is longer, as it is in experimental devices, this convergence onto the $r = 0$ axis will be less violent and may not generate this feature.

This neck feature also leads to another quite interesting notion. The entire goal of the simulation was to follow the dynamical behavior until a steady jetting outflow was encountered. However, the energy traces show that, at least during this short simulation period, variables have only just begun to settle down, if at all. Another possibility is that the plasma response is intrinsically unsteady. There is actually an indication that this is in fact the case for this system that is driven so strongly by F_{ext} . Fig. (5.9) shows that $\nabla\Psi$ is very small near the point $r = 0.17, z = 0.50$. Actually, there is a local maximum of Ψ near

this point. This implies that the dynamical forces along with numerical field line reconnection is leading to the segmenting of the torus into two (actually 3, when one considers the $z < 0$ symmetry) separate tori. This is consistent with the large rotational velocities and toroidal magnetic field. The point is that the FRC may spawn a small plasma torus that has enough energy and the correct field structure to exist independent from the FRC. It is speculated that the later behavior would involve the ejection of plasmoid vortex that would propagate axially while the remaining magnetic field and plasma would snap back toward a more classical FRC shape. In the equilibrium, the FRC had no B_θ and therefore had no helicity. The external and viscous forces together will generate local helicities, although the net total helicity will remain zero. By the assumed symmetry of the simulation, plasmoids will be ejected in pairs for $\pm z$. The plasmoids will have the same magnitude of total helicity but opposite signs. The plasmoids would carry a majority of the local helicity off with them, leaving the remaining FRC with less local helicity. This suggests that there may be a natural tendency in FRC's towards small or no helicity. Plasmoid ejection may be a form of spontaneous plasma ejection. Moreover, it is plausible that the long-time behavior might be dominated by periodic plasmoid ejections that reduce the local helicity that is continually introduced by the drag force. There is also the possibility that more realistic plasma equilibria with longer elongations will be more susceptible to this reconnection and ejection process since such plasmas have much smaller field line curvature. However, they may be less susceptible since their effective jet nozzle will not constrict the flow as severely. Of course all of these suggestions await confirmation by longer simulations before they can confidently be identified. Additionally, the damping

Figure 5.24: Axial Flux of Poloidal Kinetic Energy as a Function of Time.

zone must be moved further from the spindle point in order to clarify the dynamical behavior. Nevertheless, the possibility of such behavior is quite interesting.

Finally, conclusions about direct energy conversion can be drawn by examining the form of energy outflow at the damping zone. There are several ideas about direct energy conversion from the axial exhaust out of an FRC. These include thermal conversion[18], high energy particle deceleration by an inverse linac[18] and a homopolar generator-like power extraction.[113] Fig. (5.24)-Fig. (5.27) show the total power flow out of the simulation in the various energy channels. As can be seen, the major power outflow comes from electromagnetic Poynting flux. It is 3 times larger than the next largest power flow which is from convection of thermal energy. The exhaust power contained in bulk motion is only about 10% of the total ejected energy. However, within

Figure 5.25: Axial Flux of Toroidal Kinetic Energy as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.26: Axial Flux of Electromagnetic Energy as a Function of Time.

Figure 5.27: Axial Flux of Thermal Energy as a Function of Time.

that mix, most of the power flow comes from the convection of toroidal energy and not from the kinetic energy in poloidal motion. What this means is that as the fluid is ejected, it acts more like a drifting rotor than a collimated jet. Thus it is conceivable that the attachment of electrodes at different radii could be used to extract the rotational energy directly into electrical current as has been suggested.[113] However, there may also be ways to use the magnetic field to convert rotational energy into jetting energy by nozzle shaping far downstream. The suggestion is that most of the ejected plasma energy will not be in the form of gross kinetic motion. This contrasts with a previous astrophysical jet simulation where the kinetic energy dominated the Poynting flux.[101] Of course the situation is different for untrapped energetic fusion products, some of which will be promptly lost at great energies.[18] It is not yet clear how these conclusions change for different equilibrium choices or external driving forces or

viscosities.

Finally, the ability to extract rotational energy downstream offers an interesting possibility. The $n = 2$ rotational mode may be violently excited when 3-dimensional variations are allowed and the beam has significant drag. However, the ability to apply a torque on the plasma downstream in the jet during direct energy conversion of rotational energy may also brake the plasma rotation. If this disturbance can propagate upstream, then it may be possible to control the internal rotation rates inside the FRC and just outside the separatrix.[114] In this case it might be possible to suppress rotational modes. It might also provide control and tailoring of other plasma characteristics. It has the advantage of being a control system that is not invasive.

Chapter 6

Conclusions and Further Problems

6.1 Conclusions

One of the main current programmatic obstacles to the development of the FRC as a reactor has been the prediction that unstable tilt activity will destroy plasma confinement in FRC's as the size approaches reactor relevancy. It has long been suggested that energetic particle beams could stabilize this mode.[1] to varying degrees of detail, this conjecture has more recently been verified analytically[46, 79] and numerically[41, 43, 45, 47]. This work continues along that path to show that not only is such stabilization possible, in principle, but that it is within the realm of experimental realizability with only moderate advances in current experimental techniques (Ch. (3)).

Secondly, it has also been suggested that the choice of equilibrium can critically affect tilt stability.[51, 40] This has recently been investigated within the framework of a variational theory with a limited set of trial functions.[97] Here, I have presented an initial value fluid simulation with similar results. They indicate that equilibria with hollow current profiles can be tilt stable (Ch. (4)). The initial value simulation does not restrict the set of possible trial functions. Therefore there is reason for optimism that there is a set of experimental parameters that will allow MHD stable operation of FRC's from

the current level of experiments to larger devices, and perhaps even reactor-sized devices.

Given this situation, there should be renewed interest in other fusion plasma problems related to the FRC concept such as transport, current-drive, and energy extraction. Some of these areas have been neglected by the fusion community in general because of open questions about tilt stability. Whether the FRC concept is a workable fusion concept will depend on the answers to these open questions.

One such question that has been initially investigated in this work (Ch. (5)) is what are the possible behaviors associated with ignition-induced rotation. The results presented here point to an energetic bipolar axial flow and associated features. It also indicates that if the forcing mechanism is large, it may eject most of the core plasma in this jetting phenomena. However, the simulation results for this problem raise many more questions than they answer. Particularly interesting are the possibilities of plasma control by manipulation of coronal plasma far away from the plasma core and the possibility and consequences of rapid plasma toroidal rotation.

6.2 Further Problems

Necessarily, a work of this type must conclude at a rather arbitrary point in the course of investigations. Such is the case here. There are many more problems that are of natural relevance to the physical situation under investigation. In fact, many of these extensions have already been prepared and programmed for simulation. I would like to take a short amount of time to outline some of these studies, the questions they would address and the ranges of possible

conclusions.

The first extra study should be to undertake a series of simulations which include higher toroidal mode numbers. This is important because if the $n = 1$ tilt mode is stable, questions about $n = 2$ rotational modes, interchange modes, and other modes need to be investigated. These studies can be accomplished with purely fluid modelling. They are an extension of the profile stabilization work presented Ch. (4). Detailed simulations could also search for an actual mechanism that corresponds to a conjectured equilibrium regulating mode that forces current profiles to be hollow.[51, 115]

Another area worth investigating is solution of the equilibrium problem with the addition of external beams. The equilibrium solver used in Ch. (3)[75] can easily be extended to include equilibrium currents from an energetic particle beam, when the beam is of certain forms. If it is assumed that the beam current $\mathbf{J}_b$ is of the form,

$$\frac{1}{c}\mathbf{J}_b \times \mathbf{B} = K(\Psi)\nabla\Psi, \quad (6.1)$$

then the beam current will simply act to partially displace the plasma pressure. $S(\Psi)$ defined as,

$$S(\Psi) \equiv P(\Psi) - \int^{\Psi} K(\Psi')d\Psi', \quad (6.2)$$

will take the place of $P(\Psi)$ in Eq. (4.14). However, only very special distribution functions will give a beam current that obeys Eq. (6.1). Nevertheless, it is possible to formulate both an analytical and numerical scheme to solve an extended version of Eq. (4.14) that can take integrals of the beam distribution function as input.

Generating the beam current profiles from an equilibrium solver will

allow much quieter initial states that will be more sensitive probes of linear mode behavior. It will help to settle the question of whether beam stabilization is the result of equilibrium modification or the result of beam dynamical response. Equilibria that are generated with an already embedded beam could be run in a non-interacting manner. The time evolution of the fluid could be followed with the beam held constant. This will then allow 3 simulation modes, totally interacting, fixed beam, or fixed fluid. This will cover a wide range of problems, although the dynamical system developed in Ch. (2) still will not model field perturbations that are on the short time scale of individual energetic particles. One particular set of runs that will be of interest is to run with a non-interacting beam, and see what are the marginal stability boundaries for the fluid dynamical response.

Additional studies about the response of the energetic particles to tilting activity also offer rich opportunities. Analytic estimates have suggested that if the axial betatron frequency is tuned to the axis encircling frequency, the required beam current for stabilization may be reduced considerably.[46] The issue here is a resonance between the $n = 1$ tilt mode with the axial betatron motion. Present simulations and experiments tend to have midplane curvatures that are too low and thus are far from resonance. It would be useful to develop a set of different equilibria and determine the critical beam current for stabilization for each case. This would be a computational investigation of whether such a suggested behavior is still seen when realistic equilibria and realistic perturbations are used.

Also of interest would be simulation of reactor-scale devices in support of planning and design of such devices, reactor studies, and smaller, next gen-

eration devices.[18] Simulations should also be undertaken to verify previous investigations on the effects of energetic beams upon rotational modes.[69, 70]

There are also many simulation problems that can be undertaken that utilize the modelling of drag portion of electron-beam collisions which have been incorporated both into the model and into the NBF code, even though no results were presented here. It could be used to discover characteristics of self-consistent beam distribution functions on a time scale long compared to collision times. This will be important since the beam distribution functional form can greatly affect the total current and the local current distribution of the beam. The derivation of such a slowing down distribution function is not trivial because of the large spatial gradients in this problem. This NBF with drag simulation technique could also be used to estimate the current drive that will result from neutral beam injection of spontaneous beam generation from ignition.

Finally, there exist versions of the FLX algorithm[82] that can include the effects of increasing current in the external coils. This will lead to radial plasma compression. Such a simulation tool, coupled with the particle modelling presented here could be used to investigate the behavior of an energetic particle beam during compression. This is an important question for three reasons. First, since the tilt mode has such a short growth time, on larger machines it may be necessary to inject the beam before compression is complete in the formation stage.[18] Second, for a reactor sized device, the required beam energy is too large for high neutralizer efficiency. This will limit the beam guns maximum output. However, if the beam were injected before compression, the plasma would be less dense and the required energy would be lower. Then the

acceleration to higher energies could be accomplished by the inductive electric field generated during plasma compression. This is another situation where a FRC with an embedded beam will be compressed.

There are other studies that involve the behavior of single particle orbits. The data presented in Ch. (3) indicate even when the magnetic field is static, the particle orbits are very complex. In fact, some particles are in orbits that may exhibit the complex, and even chaotic dynamics, as is seen in the Earth's magnetotail[53, 89, 116] When the fields are allowed to vary, the behavior is even more curious. Additional study into the behavior of particular orbits and the behavior of ensembles of energetic particles seems very important to understanding issues about energetic particle effects.

There are also issues that are crucial to progress in understanding FRC behavior that cannot be accurately modeled with the simulation tools presented. Most notable among these are issues involved in transport. While the NBF code does include transport terms, the transport coefficients are either classical or semi-empirical. True transport analysis would calculate these effects self-consistently. However, that is impossible in the present situation because the electric and magnetic fields evolve only on the slow fluid time scales, and particularly, there is no direct coupling between the fields and the energetic particles, only indirect coupling using the plasma fluid as an intermediary. Since transport calculation usually involves estimation of correlations of particle perturbations with electromagnetic perturbations, accurate transport estimation is beyond the capability of these simulation tools.

Additionally, there has been growing interest in FRC-like devices where all of the ions are energetic[86] or devices that are composed primarily of single

component energetic species.[117] Such simulations are not possible with these tools because the $\delta \rightarrow 0$ approximation in Ch. (2) is such a great simplification. Relaxation of this assumption would be a very non-trivial model extension, and it is an open question whether the numerical algorithm presented would remain stable for the simple sub-cycling scheme that was used.

That is not to say that these type of problems are not important, only that it appears unlikely that the methods used in this work could be applied successfully to them. Nevertheless, there are a large set of problems connected with FRC research that can fruitfully be explored with the methods used here, or very similar ones.

Appendix

Appendix A

Interpretation of Particle in Cell Algorithm

The particle in cell algorithm is ubiquitous and familiar.[118, 119, 120] It is usually applied to systems which obey a Liouville equation. While the Vlasov equation obeys Liouville's equation, the Fokker-Planck equation does not. Both the diffusion and drag terms cause non conservation of phase space volume. A question then arises. Given the particle algorithm, what partial differential equation does it model? This appendix will define the specific particle algorithm. Then it will present the two different equations that are often advanced as models of the particle algorithm, a Vlasov-like equation and a flux-conservative equation. A particular, simple, example problem where analytic solutions are possible both for the partial differential equations and the particle algorithm will be presented. It will be shown that the partial differential equations give different solutions and that the flux conservative form corresponds to the particle algorithm.

A.1 Particle Algorithm

The general particle algorithm is a method of simulation of physical reality by representing portions of matter by discrete objects. These objects then carry an identity along with various quantities which are assigned to them. They

interact via some prescribed functional form. Here I will assume that this interaction is a "mean field" interaction. The quantities which are attached to the particles are accumulated and interpolated to give average fields. The particle motion is governed by these mean fields. For example, in a plasma the mean fields are the electric and magnetic fields.

The particles may be interpreted to correspond to many different physical objects. In hydrodynamics and magnetohydrodynamics, the particles represent a "chunk of fluid", a small element of fluid, that carries along with it a mass, momentum, and internal energy (pressure or entropy). Some plasma kinetic simulations regard each particle as representing a "chunk of phase space", that is a small element of the distribution function in phase space. The particle carries along with it an identity (mass, charge, etc) and a weighting factor that represents the manner in which phase space is expanding or contracting locally. This is called the "phase space interpretation". Other plasma kinetic simulations view each simulation particle as a collection of actual physical particles that are artificially locked together in identical motion. I call this view the "lock step interpretation". This interpretation is almost identical to a third interpretation, called the "macro particle interpretation" where each simulation particle is regarded as an actual physical particle. If computational simulation could include as many simulation particles as the actual physical situation under study then the macro particle interpretation would be accurate and complete. Each macro particle could be given the charge and mass identical to the physical particles under study. The lock step interpretation would also be accurate and complete since the number of particles locked together in each simulation particle would be only 1. In practice the number of simulation

particles is much less than the number of physical particles. Therefore each simulation macro particle must have a much larger charge and mass than is physical. Often if the charge to mass ratio is kept constant, the dynamics of the macro particles reproduces the dynamics of the physical system. In the lock step interpretation, the number of physical particles locked together in motion is greater than 1. Therefore the simulation is creating unphysical motion when it forces some particles to move together that would physically move apart. However, like the macro particle interpretation, the lock step particle motion often reproduces the physical dynamics. Below I will only consider plasma kinetic particle simulation models.

The simulation particles interact in two ways. First the particle's motion is given by mean fields from all of the particles. That is the particles move in phase space according to their velocity and acceleration. The acceleration is a function of each particle's position and velocity and a functional of the mean fields. The second interaction is that the particle's "intrinsic" or "attached" quantities such as mass, charge, or phase space weight may also change along the orbit.

The particle algorithm will approximate the behavior of a governing partial differential equation. These interpretations suggest different candidates for that governing equation. The question to ask and answer is which governing equation is correct. If the system obeys a Liouville equation, then the interpretations are the same. However, if the motion does not conserve phase space volume, then these interpretations suggest different governing equations. First define precisely what is meant by "the particle algorithm". The simulation will consist of N particles. Each particle will carry a particle data

vector $d_{i1}, d_{i2}, \dots, d_{i\omega}$. The $d_{i\alpha}$'s are, as of now, unspecified but in practice they include such items as particle mass and particle charge. The $d_{i\alpha}$'s give information which is associated with individual particles. Here I will consider the $d_{i\alpha}$'s to be constant for each particle. It should be noted that later algorithmic extensions include the possibility that the $d_{i\alpha}$'s change for example when ionization is included, but this concept is not essential to this discussion and will be neglected. There are 3 other pieces of particle data which vary continuously during the particle motion. The first 2 are the particle's position, $\mathbf{x}_i$, and velocity, $\mathbf{v}_i$. The third is the particle's weight, w_i . The particle weight gives information about how the particle's influence is changing. In the phase space interpretation, it gives information about the expansion or contraction of phase space along the particle's trajectory. In the lock step interpretation, it gives information about how the number of particles linked together is increasing or decreasing. In the macro-particle view, it describes how the overall normalization of the particle is changing.

Simulation proceeds by advancing the state of the particle in time. Since the $d_{i\alpha}$'s are fixed in time only $\mathbf{x}_i$, $\mathbf{v}_i$, and w_i need to be updated. They are updated according to the following equations:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{x}_i}{dt} \equiv \mathbf{v}_i, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

$$\frac{d\mathbf{v}_i}{dt} \equiv \mathbf{a}_i(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{v}_i), \quad (\text{A.2})$$

$$\frac{dw_i}{dt} \equiv S_i, \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $\mathbf{a}_i$ and S_i are functions of particle quantities, $\mathbf{x}_i$, $\mathbf{v}_i$, w_i and $\{d_i\}$ and functionals of the mean fields evaluated at the particle positions and velocities,

$F_m(\mathbf{x}_i, \mathbf{v}_i)$. The mean fields, $F_1, F_2, \dots, F_n$ are functions of position and velocity. They also depend on the positions and velocities of all simulation particles. They may also depend on other mean fields or their derivatives. Specification of the mean fields closes the system. The entire system is specified when the detailed forms for $\mathbf{a}_i$, S_i , and F_m are given.

Simulation problems where $S_i = 0$ are called fixed weight problems. The more general $S_i \neq 0$ case can be dealt with by means of δ -f methods.[121]

The particle motion is said to be Liouvillian or phase space preserving if

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{v}} \mathbf{a}_i = 0. \quad (\text{A.4})$$

This condition expresses that fact that if particles are initially uniformly distributed in phase space, then at all later times they will still be approximately uniform. This uniformity will be exact in the limit of an infinite number of particles.

A.2 Partial Differential Equation Models

What partial differential equation corresponds to the particle algorithm? The interpretations suggest 2 forms. The phase space interpretation is reminiscent of Liouville's equation in statistical mechanics, or the Vlasov equation.

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, F_m) \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = S. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The particle algorithm, in this interpretation, can be viewed as the reduction of a partial differential equation to the ordinary differential equations for its characteristics.[122]

However the lock step and macro particle interpretations imply a flux conservative type of governing equation where the distribution is given locally by the number of particles in a region of phase space and the change in the distribution function is due to the flux of particles into and out of a region.

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{x}}(\mathbf{v}f) + \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{v}}(\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, F_m)f) = S. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

These equations are suggested by the interpretations given to the particle algorithm. Which one, if either of these equations is correct can only be determined by more precise statement of problems and solutions. The validity of such associations needs to be tested.

It should be noted that if the system under study preserves phase space volume, Eq. (A.4), then Eq. (A.5) and Eq. (A.6) are identical. In this instance discussion the distinction between Eq. (A.5) and Eq. (A.6) is moot. This is why most literature has neglected discussing this issue. However, for the formulation used in this work, the presence of the Fokker-Planck drag force violates conservation of phase space. In this instance the distinction is important.

A.3 Simple Example — Uniform Drag

Proving which equation, in the general case, corresponds to the particle algorithm is beyond the scope of this work. Here I will present an analytically solvable particle example and compare it to the possible model equations. Consider a 1-dimensional, homogeneous situation with a set of N particles. Since the system is homogeneous, variations in $\mathbf{x}$ are irrelevant and will be ignored. The particle acceleration is chosen to be a simple drag force,

$$\mathbf{a}_i \equiv -\gamma \mathbf{v}_i, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

and the source term to be zero,

$$S_i \equiv 0 \quad (\text{A.8})$$

The initial particle positions are chosen according to a cumulative distribution function,[88] $D(v)$, which is defined as,

$$D(v) \equiv \int_{-\infty}^v f(v') dv', \quad (\text{A.9})$$

and $f(v)$ is the particle distribution function. The velocity of the i 'th particle will be determined by the relation,

$$(i - \frac{1}{2})/N = D(v_i). \quad (\text{A.10})$$

For this example I will choose a simple function for the initial distribution in velocity space.

$$f_0(v) \equiv \begin{cases} 1/(2W_0) & |v| < W_0 \\ 0 & |v| > W_0 \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where W_0 is a profile parameter. In this case the initial cumulative distribution function is,

$$D_0(v) = \begin{cases} 0 & v < -W_0 \\ 1/2 + v/(2W_0) & |v| < W_0 \\ 1 & W_0 < v \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.12})$$

and the initial velocity of the i 'th particle is

$$v_i^0 = W_0(2i - N - 1)/N. \quad (\text{A.13})$$

The subsequent motion of each particle can be directly integrated from the equation of motion,

$$\frac{dv_i}{dt} = -\alpha v_i, \quad (\text{A.14})$$

yielding,

$$v_i(t) = v_i^0 \exp(-\alpha t) = W_0 \exp(-\alpha t)(2i - N - 1)/N. \quad (\text{A.15})$$

It is convenient to define a time dependent normalization, $W(t)$, as

$$W(t) \equiv W_0 \exp(-\alpha t). \quad (\text{A.16})$$

In that case the particle motion reduces to,

$$v_i(t) = W(t)(2i - N - 1)/N. \quad (\text{A.17})$$

The form of the particle distribution function at arbitrary time can then be read off by recalling the connection between individual particle velocity, cumulative distribution function, and particle distribution function,

$$f(v, t) \equiv \begin{cases} 1/(2W(t)) & |v| < W(t) \\ 0 & |v| > W(t) \end{cases}. \quad (\text{A.18})$$

Now I will discuss whether the distribution function, Eq. (A.18), satisfies Eq. (A.5). In this case Eq. (A.5) reduces to

$$\frac{df}{dt} \equiv \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} - \alpha v \frac{\partial f}{\partial v} \stackrel{?}{=} 0. \quad (\text{A.19})$$

Calculation reveals that

$$\frac{df}{dt} = \begin{cases} \alpha/(2W(t)) & |v| < W(t) \\ 0 & |v| > W(t) \end{cases} \neq 0. \quad (\text{A.20})$$

Clearly the particle algorithm does not satisfy Eq. (A.5) in this example. Now examine whether Eq. (A.18) satisfies Eq. (A.6). In this example, Eq. (A.6) reduces to

$$\begin{aligned} & \frac{\partial f}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial}{\partial v}(\alpha v f) \\ = & \begin{cases} \frac{-dW(t)/dt}{2W^2(t)} - \frac{\alpha}{2W(t)} & |v| < W(t) \\ 0 - 0 & |v| > W(t) \end{cases} \\ & \begin{cases} \frac{-dW(t)/dt}{2W(t)} \delta(v + W(t)) - \frac{\alpha}{2W(t)} \delta(v + W(t)) & v = -W(t) \\ \frac{-dW(t)/dt}{2W(t)} \delta(v - W(t)) - \frac{\alpha}{2W(t)} \delta(v - W(t)) & v = W(t) \end{cases} \\ & = 0. \quad (\text{A.21}) \end{aligned}$$

Thus in this example the particle algorithm solves Eq. (A.6) but not Eq. (A.5). While it is not proven here, I claim that this is the general situation, except for phase space conserving flows, where both equations are correct.

It should be noted that Eq. (A.5) can be modified so that the particle algorithm models it if an additional source term proportional to the non-conservation of phase space is added to the right-hand side,

$$\frac{\partial f}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{x}} + \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, F_m) \cdot \frac{\partial f}{\partial \mathbf{v}} = S - f \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{v}} \mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}, F_m) \right), \quad (\text{A.22})$$

since this is mathematically equivalent to Eq. (A.6). The point of this appendix is to explicitly highlight why the particle weights are constant even though the governing equation in Vlasov form has a non zero right-hand side. It is simply a consequence of the fact that the right-hand side of the equation is due solely to phase space non-conservation. It is simpler to view the particle algorithm as simulating the flux conservative dynamical equation, Eq. (A.6), since then there is a clear correspondence between terms in the equation and the rate of change of particle quantities ($\mathbf{a}$ and S).

Other researchers have been aware of this issue for sometime[123] but it has not been emphasized or explicitly discussed in the recent literature. Since most previous work has pertained to phase space conserving flows, it has been of little importance. However new simulation methods that produce reduced kinetic equations or augmented fluid and gyro-fluid models or the inclusion of collision operators that are not phase space conserving are becoming more and more common. Attention to this detail is important if modeling by particle simulation is to be accurate.

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Vita

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